

VALKYRIES

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1. Executive Summary

The certification and evaluation scheme of equipment for SAR and disaster response can be complicated, time consume and even hindering the development and adaption of new solutions. This deliverable will give an overview of the standards and certification scheme for SAR and emergency response related products and systems.

This deliverable **D3.10** is part of *Task T3.5 Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities* that aims to investigate current certification framework and initiatives and identify gaps and opportunities, and to reduce the time from research to certification, as well as enhancing their sustainability. Eventually, we will suggest that how this knowledge can be exploited in the Valkyries user cases and for future development of products and systems for SAR.

This deliverable will cover follows; in chapter 3, general concept of the certification is explored including conformity assessment, accreditation, and evaluation (test procedure and test facilities). The challenges in the certification process for the SAR equipment, system and operation are described, and definition of scope for this deliverable is briefly presented.

Chapter 4 deals with current SAR situation and a brief overview of relevant aspects from the four use-cases.

In chapter 5, research projects and activities for the certification are introduced before the current standardization and certification for the SAR equipment and operation are presented. The SAR equipment covered in here is as follows: 1) Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (drone), 2) Unmanned Surface Vehicle (sea drones), 3) Unmanned Ground Vehicle (rover), 4) communication equipment, 5) tagging equipment and 6) wearable equipment.

In chapter 6, the certification and evaluation define in terms of the sustainability, and the requirements and criteria for usability, accessibility and human-system interaction of SAR equipment are discussed. **It is explored that how to make disaster management certification processes more sustainable and effective. The importance of well-equipped test facilities is emphasized, and new capabilities in test facilities are proposed. Implementing appropriate capabilities can improve disaster management while promoting sustainability by optimizing resource use and reducing environmental impact. In addition, collaborative utilization of test facilities offers numerous advantages, including resource sharing, expertise exchange, and the development of harmonized standards.**

In chapter 7, identified gaps and opportunities are summarized through this deliverable. **These gaps encompass technical standards, operational challenges, as well as broader considerations of sustainability and effectiveness within the context of emergency response. In here, certification holds a central position in addressing these multifaceted issues.**

Changes from previous version D1.9 version A/1 have been highlighted in yellow according to the general project review consolidated report for easy identification.

2. Identification

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3. Introduction and Project Scope

The certification considers as the confirmation of certain characteristics of a product, process, person or organisation. In most cases, this confirmation is provided by some form of external review, assessment, or audit. The confirmation is carried out by an accredited agency. This accredited agency assesses and verifies the attributes, characteristics, quality, qualification, or status of something or someone. This assessment and verification are in accordance with established requirements or standards. In this context, the certification demonstrates that the product/process/person/organisation have been thoroughly tested and/or inspected to show compliance with necessary safety or performance requirements.

This deliverable will analyse the European and international certification initiatives concerning the first response enablers to identify gaps and challenges in a harmonized certification. In addition, opportunities related to the certification and accreditation are explored to prompt sustainable certification, accreditation and homogeneity assessment.

The scope of the certification in Task3.5 (Sustainable International/European Certification and Evaluation facilities) is set to: 1) technologies/equipment for first responders, 2) operation of first responders (Figure 1). For the technologies and equipment part, the certification of equipment itself and certification for the technologies used in SAR equipment (e.g., cybersecurity, software) are dealt with in. The certification for emergency response teams and human-related aspects certifications (e.g., training and education) are included in the operation part. In addition, it is expected that new certification opportunities could be proposed to connect the technologies and the human such as certifications for skills of managing new capabilities (e.g., trained operatives of autonomous vehicles).

Figure 1 - Certification scope in Task 3.5

To identify gaps and challenges in current certification scheme derived from novel solution for emergency response equipment and operation, the present state of certification schemes will be mapped. As a first step, general certification procedure for the emergency response equipment and operation will be explored. After mapping the current certification scheme and identifying possible gaps, opportunities to improve the certification process will be suggested.

One of important research questions in this deliverable is “What kind of assessment criteria should we consider for harmonized certification in emergency response equipment and operation?” To answer this question, currently considered criteria will be identified, then four use cases in Valkyries are investigated to find requirements to be satisfied in emergency

response. In addition, the current research projects and initiatives are explored to map ‘as-is’ conformity assessment criteria and necessary criteria for novel technologies.

The following table shows the requirements stated in D2.8 related to this task.

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_BASE_T3.5_1	N/A	VALK-OBJ-4	D3.4 D3.9 D3.10	REQUIRED	Analysis done in D3.4, D3.9 and D3.10
REQ_BASE_T3.5_2	P1	VALK-OBJ-4	D3.10	RECOMMENDED	Initiatives mapped in D3.10
REQ_BASE_T3.5_3	P1	VALK-OBJ-4	D3.9 D3.10	REQUIRED	Testing procedures and facilities described in D3.9 and D3.10
REQ_BASE_T3.5_4	N/A	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5	D3.9 D3.10	REQUIRED	Gaps and opportunities identified in D3.9 and D3.10
REQ_COM_T3.5_1	P2	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5	D3.10	REQUIRED	Questionnaires and workshops have been held during the project. D3.10 - Annex B
REQ_COM_T2.4_5	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	D3.4 D3.9 D3.10	OPTIONAL	Common guidance for certification, quality control and continuing performance described in D3.9 and D3.10
REQ_COM_T2.4_2	P2	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	D3.10	OPTIONAL	Desing the first steps for a possible future interoperability certification described in D3.9 and D3.10
REQ_BASE_T2.5_1	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5	D3.10 D2.12 D2.9	RECOMMENDED	Study analyze and use common certification

		VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7			frameworks described in D3.10
REQ_BASE_T2.5_3	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	D3.10 D2.12 D2.9	REQUIRED	Desing a certification framework for the project described in D3.10
REQ_COM_T2.5_2	P2	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	D3.10	OPTIONAL	Establishing new requirements for the certification scheme described in D3.10

Table 1 – Requirements traceability matrix

3.1. General Certification Procedure

Before mapping the current certification scheme, the general certification procedure for the emergency response equipment and operation will be explored in this section. In addition, important concepts in the certification process are investigated.

3.1.1. Certification Procedure for technologies and equipment

Figure 2 shows general certification procedure for a product and important stakeholders in the certification and evaluation process. The certification process is as follows; the manufacturer needs to navigate national, European and international rules and regulations in order to obtain the necessary certification. Then, the manufacturer may choose conformity assessment procedures based on the relevant rules and regulations. The assessment is carried out by the notified body¹/conformity assessment body² according to the legislation requirements. The notified body needs to be accredited by the accreditation body for their competence. The notified body issue the certification when all of specified requirements comply with the laws and standards. Then, the manufacturer can put the product on the market, and the end-user can purchase the certified product.

In this process, the scope of D3.4 is the part shown in dotted line in Figure 2. However, the certification is fundamentally based on the laws and standards, so the regulations and the standards for the SAR equipment are also partly included in this report.

¹ The notified body is an organization designated by an EU Member State (or by other countries under specific agreements) to assess the conformity of certain products.

² The Conformity assessment bodies may apply for designation as notified bodies under Regulations (EU) 2017/745 and 2017/7

Figure 2 - Scope of this work in relations to the certification process

The CE marking is important concept related to the product certification. The CE marking is slightly different to the certification³, but the process of obtaining for CE marking is similar to the certification process. The CE marking is a key indicator (but not proof) of a product's compliance with EU legislation (Commission, 2016). In the European market, CE marking is a legal requirement for manufacturers in certain product categories⁴.

Some of the SAR equipment/system put on the market with CE marking. For example, a rescue craft from Swedish company⁵ is in the market with CE marking under *Directive 2013/53/EU recreational craft and personal watercraft*.

The CE marking applies to a wide range of products that in the EU have certain specifications to meet. These specifications assess your conformance to safety, health, and security. It is a tool that does not apply an offer of services.

International standards such as ISO standards are widely recognized and are endorsed for certification by entities accredited for it. In this case, they do apply to products and services, depending on the scope of each standard. The accrediting entities have the necessary skills to ensure compliance with the requirements of products and services according to the reference standard. These are applied in the Certification Procedure for Operation.

3.1.2. Certification Procedure for operation

The different tools will be certificate in the unique process by European Commission established and follow the rules of this organise.

³ CE marking does not show evidence of third-party conformity assessment because, the manufacturer can assess their product by themselves depending on the type of products, so it should not be confused with any independent certification mark issued by international or European notified bodies

⁴ EU Directives specify particular product categories that must bear the CE Mark, and each category refers to a relevant New Approach Directive. (https://ec.europa.eu/growth/single-market/ce-marking/manufacturers_en)

⁵ The manufacturer is responsible and liable for the safety of the product under Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 when placed on the EU market. Some products are subject to several EU requirements at the same time and the directives are updated from time to time. So, the manufacturer must make sure that their product complies with all the relevant requirements.

First responders and several organizations who will take part in the use cases going to evaluate the tools. After that they will do a report in which report the different conclusion and recommend to improve the tools.

The evaluation of the tools will be follow different ways and characters of them like this;

- Applicability of the tools in coordination between first responders
- Operability of the tools
- Degree of achievement of the objectives of each of them with respect to the task assigned to them
- Ease of use of the tools
- Ease of integration of the data provided
- Fast and secure understanding of the data provided
- Facilitate a rapid, coordinated, effective and efficient response by first responders

In conclusion, they will be adapted to process, interventions and coordination of the agencies involved: EU Civil Protection, Emergency Response Coordination Centre, Common Emergency Communication and Information System and European Civil Protection Pool and rescuEU.

In the next points you will see the different agencies.

3.1.2.1. EU Civil Protection Mechanism

The European Commission established the EU Civil Protection Mechanism. The Mechanism aims to strengthen cooperation between the EU countries and 6 Participating States (Iceland, Norway, Serbia, North Macedonia, Montenegro, and Turkey) on civil protection to improve prevention, preparedness, and response to disasters (Figure 3).

Figure 3 - UCPM Participating States and Neighbourhood Countries (Apr. 2021) (Maps (europa.eu))

The process of the Mechanism is shown in Figure 4. When a disaster overwhelms a country's ability to contain it, other participating states step in and provide assistance under the EU Civil Protection Mechanism. The Mechanism is operated by the Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC) which organises and coordinates the delivery of EU civil protection teams and equipment to a disaster-stricken country. On this wise, the ERCC can make use of the European

Civil Protection Pool (ECPP)⁶ and/or rescEU⁷ capacities for immediate deployment in disaster situations⁸.

For communication between the ERCC and the National Authorities, the European Union has created a website to facilitate this connection, Common Emergency Communication and Information System (CECIS), in order to have a rapid and effective response to disasters⁹.

Figure 4 - ECPP and rescEU in EU Civil Protection Mechanism

The European Civil Protection Pool (ECPP) was established to improve the coordination of response activities. The ECPP includes rescue or medical teams, experts, specialized equipment or transportation, and 110 capacities are registered up to January 2022 (Figure 5). When all the capacities are already in use, the “rescEU reserve”¹⁰ can be used¹¹.

The rescUE (rescUE reserve) is a complementary protection layer with the aim to improve and reinforce the protection for citizens from disasters with support resources and manage emerging risks¹². These resources are additionally trained to respond to disasters of greater scope than those represented by Valkyries (chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear incidents).

The European Commission has set up a certification and registration process. In order to register the capacities to the ECPP and rescEU, the capacities need to go through the certification

⁶ Previously referred to as the European Emergency Response Capacity. It renamed as the ECPP (European Civil Protection Pool) by Decision (EU) 2019/420

⁷ In 2019, the European Commission created rescEU, and the rescEU establishes a new European reserve of resources (the ‘rescEU reserve’)

⁸ Difference between ECPP and rescEU: The ECPP capacities are available for national purposes at all times and it is up to the Member states concerned to take the ultimate decision on their deployment (Decision 2013/1313 (n 2), arts 11(5) and 11(7)). The rescEU capacities may only be used for national purposes ‘if not being used or needed for response operations under the Union Mechanism’ and can be deployed and demobilised pursuant to a Commission’s decision (Decision 2019/420 (n 3), art 1(7))

⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/echo/policies/disaster_response/cecis_en.htm

¹⁰ The rescEU reserve includes a fleet of firefighting planes and helicopters, medical evacuation planes, a stockpile of medical items and field hospitals that can respond to health emergencies

¹¹ Details are defined in Decision (EU) 2019/420 (‘Article 12) <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32019D0420>

¹² https://civil-protection-humanitarian-aid.ec.europa.eu/what/civil-protection/resceu_en

process. In this regard, if the resources in the ECPP and rescEU are certified according to a particular standard, then they can be able to work together in any disaster situations.

Any member state and state participating in the European Civil Protection Mechanism can contribute a wide variety of resources to the Emergency Response Pool, ECPP. To do this, the competent public authority of the interested country (civil protection) previously writes to the European Union with the explanation of the political decision to contribute resources to the community mechanism.

The process begins with the delivery of the request with the inclusion of the relevant documentation, which includes, among others, the operational procedures used by the country. Once the application has been evaluated and approved, the European Commission begins the certification process. This certification process is made up of a three-step process developed by certification guides as a compliance standard: an advisory hearing, a simulation exercise, and a field exercise.

INSARAG-classified urban search and rescue teams, as well as WHO-verified medical teams, are considered certified in the context of ECPP.

Figure 5 - European Civil Protection Pool – Offered 110 Capacities in the Pool (January 2022)¹³

3.1.2.2. Certification in UCPM

In order to ensure that the resources of the ECPP and rescEU meet high standards and will function properly when applied in disaster response, a certification process has been set up by the European Commission. The certification process may differ depending on the type of

¹³ <https://erccportal.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ERCC-Response/CP-Pool#/>

resource, but it generally has three steps: 1) a consultative visit, 2) a table-top exercise and 3) a final certifying field exercise. The three step process is described in the Certification Guidelines¹⁴, and will be discussed in more detail in a later section 5.4.1.2.

Legal basis

The rules for the certification and registration of the ECPP are laid down in Commission Implementing Decision 2014/762/EU (Article 16)¹⁵;

- The Commission shall assess whether the assets in question can be considered inclusion in the ECPP
- In this assessment, the Commission shall consider;
 - The fulfilment of the quality requirements¹⁶
 - The capacity goals¹⁷
 - The completeness of the information provided
 - The geographic proximity and participation of all Member States
 - Other relevant factors
- If all certification conditions are fulfilled, the Commission shall declare certified the assets for the ECPP
- The certification of the resources should be reassessed at the latest after 5 years, if the asset is submitted for reregistration into the EECPP
- The Commission in cooperation with Member States shall assess the suitability of the certification and registration procedure at least every second year and, if necessary, revise it

The rules for the certification and registration of rescEU capacities are laid down in Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2019/1310 (Article 10)¹⁸;

- Member States shall ensure certification and registration of rescEU capacities in accordance with applicable national and international rules and regulations
- Where rescEU capacities are multi-purpose, certification and registration shall be completed accordingly
- Member States shall certify rescEU capacities under the Union Mechanism certification process as soon as possible and in accordance with Article 11(4) of Decision Mo 1313/2013/EU and Chapter 5 of Commission Implementing Decision 2014/762/EU

¹⁴ [Certification Guidelines - October 2019.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)

¹⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762>, amended by *Implementing Decision 2018/142* <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32018D0142>

¹⁶ Commission Implementing Decision 2014/762/EU (ANNEX II), amended by *Implementing Decision 2018/142* (ANNEX I)

¹⁷ Commission Implementing Decision 2014/762/EU (ANNEX III), amended by *Implementing Decision 2018/142* ('ANNEX III)

¹⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32019D1310>

3.2. Conformity Assessment and criteria

ISO/IEC 17000 defines conformity assessment as demonstration that specified requirements relating to a product, process, system, person, or body are fulfilled. In Figure 6, a fundamental concept for the conformity assessment is described.

Figure 6 - Example of a conformity assessment model (Standardization & Organization, 2010)

The IEC and ISO have developed and published a series of international standards specifying how conformity assessment should be carried out. ISO has produced standards to help make conformity assessment activities as uniform as possible across industries and across the world¹⁹.

The conformity assessment refers to any activity that determines whether that the product/process/person/organisation fulfil the requirements and characteristics described in a standard or specification. Such requirements can include performance, safety, efficiency, effectiveness, reliability, durability, or environmental impacts such as pollution or noise. These

¹⁹ The ISO/IEC 17000 standards series provide a full set of tools for anyone wishing to know how to carry out consistent and reliable conformity assessment.

requirements need to be assessed according to a set of well-defined rules to ensure consistent and replicable results.

For the efficient and precise conformity assessment, necessary requirements for the product/system/operation need to be established. Depending on the equipment, a different conformity assessment procedure is carried out with the corresponding criteria.

In case of the emergency response, several requirements for the equipment and operation could be defined to fulfil specified functions;

- SAR equipment may run into unexpected situation (like high/low temperature, strong wind, etc.), so it should be reliable in abnormal operating condition.
- SAR equipment is life-related product, so the safety margin may need to be larger than other product and reliability also must be assured.
- Qualified operators may be needed for remote controlled SAR equipment (e.g., drone, rover, sea drone, etc.)
- When the information is gathered by SAR equipment, and processed on the network, cyber security is important for the accurate information and privacy.
- SAR equipment should be easy to use in non-optimal conditions under emergencies
- Maintenance of functions with the need for equipment intercommunication
- Keep/Recover information with strong security under some malfunction or accident

In case of the certification In the UCPM, the conformity assessment carry out by the European Commission, and the criteria are as follows;

- Self-sufficiency - Whether the response capacity is self-sufficient during deployment and as such does not cause an additional burden to the host nation
- Coordination - How the response capacity ensures efficient coordination with other deployed capacities or response actors
- Interoperability - In how far the response capacity is interoperable with other deployed capacities
- Preparedness - The capacity's preparedness for deployment in terms of financial, legal and administrative aspects, and regarding appropriate training of team members

These criteria will be dealt with in more detail in section 5.5.

3.3. Evaluation procedures and facilities

During the certification procedure, evaluation procedures and facilities play a critical role in determining whether a subject being certified meets the required standards and regulations. Properly executed evaluation procedures, guided by established standards, ensure that the subject meets the required conditions. The evaluation and assessment are typically conducted by a third-party organization. This third-party organization is responsible for impartially reviewing and verifying that the entity or product complies with the established criteria and is eligible for certification. Some of the globally recognized third-party organizations include: UL²⁰,

²⁰ <https://www.ul.com/>

DEKRA²¹, TÜV SÜD²², TÜV Rheinland²³, DNV²⁴, Kiwa²⁵, and more. These third-party organizations not only oversee evaluations but also maintain state-of-the-art test facilities, which are for conducting thorough assessments, tests, and inspections.

By maintaining cutting-edge test facilities and employing skilled professionals, third-party organizations can uphold their commitment to objectivity and impartiality in evaluating entities and products for certification. These facilities are integral to the certification ecosystem and contribute to the assurance of quality, safety, and compliance on a global scale.

3.3.1. Equipment and technologies for emergency response

To guarantee requirements and ensure system reliability and robustness, it is essential to evaluate the performance of the equipment via proper evaluation methodologies.

According to the ISO/IEC 17025, the evaluation covers the range of activities concerned with gathering evidence of conformity. This standard specifies that “the requirements that testing and calibration laboratories have to meet if they wish to demonstrate that they operate a management system, are technically competent, and are able to generate technically valid results.” These activities can include testing, inspection, and auditing.

Testing is the most common conformity assessment technique. General requirements for the conduct of testing may be as follows;

- Competent people
- Validated methods which are repeatable and reproducible
- Properly maintained and calibrated equipment

For the most reliable test results, the test methods should be specified in the standard or other document to which conformity is being assessed.

To take an instance from IP (Ingress Protection²⁶) tests for smartphones (Yu, Xiong, Li, & Pecht, 2019). In this paper, the importance of test method²⁷ was emphasized. For IP code, there is international standards (IEC 60529 and ISO 20653), and countries and regions have also issued their own water protection standards even there is no significant difference between international and national standards. Under this condition (without standardized regulation), they presented impact of inaccurate test, and compared experimental conditions and actual use conditions as well. Like this, the evaluation may affect the quality assessment process. This circumstance could be applied to the emergency response equipment.

For reliable evaluation, the evaluation procedures need to be specified objective way based on the clearly established criteria. The evaluation procedures and criteria vary according to the equipment, so the attribute of each equipment should be clearly defined. In addition, the evaluation facilities (e.g., test laboratories) need to be accredited by the accreditation body to

²¹ <https://www.dekra.com/en/home/>

²² <https://www.tuvsud.com/en>

²³ <https://www.tuv.com/world/en/>

²⁴ <https://www.dnv.com/>

²⁵ <https://www.kiwa.com/en/>

²⁶ An IP (Ingress Protection) code (a part of the IEC 60529:2013) is the typical method to rate the ability of water resistance for industrial electrical products

²⁷ The IEC has developed the IP ratings, which grade the resistance of an enclosure against the intrusion of dust or liquids. <https://www.iec.ch/ip-ratings>

ensure that the evaluation facilities have the technical capacity to perform their duties (accreditation will be covered in section 3.4).

As novel technologies have been introduced in the emergency response, new evaluation procedure and modifications on the evaluation facilities are necessary to certify novel technologies and equipment. Accordingly, the accreditation for the evaluation facilities also need to be considered.

With the entry into operation of the equipment, they suffer from a natural deterioration that compromises their integrity. To guarantee the level of quality and usefulness of the equipment and technologies, the creation of SOPs, the creation and dissemination of manuals, as well as the logistics management of spare parts and substitutes are required. It is necessary that the operating personnel be competent in the execution of operations and maintenance tasks to adequately evaluate the level of service.

3.3.1.1. Evaluation procedures for drone

From 1st January 2024, an enhanced CE marking system will be in effect for drones within the EU, introducing a more comprehensive regulatory framework. This progression aims to promote safety, accountability, and a clear understanding of drone operations within various regions²⁸

To obtain the CE mark, an evaluation is required, and the evaluation process for drones encompasses a series of assessments, tests, and inspections. As previously stated, these evaluations are typically conducted by accredited third party organizations.

Different third party organizations may have variations in their evaluation methods and procedures, while the fundamental goal remains the same, which is to determine whether a drone complies with the necessary standards and requirements.

Applus+²⁹ Laboratories, located in Spain, is an accredited testing laboratory that provides a variety of testing services in the certification process. Applus+ is one of notified bodies for certifying UAVs under EU 2019/945, and provides information regarding the requirements and services they provide for obtaining drone certification (Figure 7).

The EASA³⁰ has established three categories for the operation of drones; Open, Specific and Certified Category. These categories have specific requirements and limitations in terms of training, equipment, and operational conditions. Based on this, Applus+ provide test services according to the category.

²⁸ <https://www.easa.europa.eu/en/newsroom-and-events/news/easa-publishes-list-available-open-category-drones-class-mark>

²⁹ <https://www.applus.com/global/en/>

³⁰ The description of EASA(European Union Aviation Safety Agency) is in section 5.3.2.1

|
CERTIFIED Category |
|---|---|---|
| Requirements <ul style="list-style-type: none">• CE Marking for C0 to C4 classes | Requirements <ul style="list-style-type: none">• CE marking requirements for classes C5 to C6<ul style="list-style-type: none">• SORA for operators• Design verification for civil aviation authority approval | Requirements <p>Not covered by UAS regulation. Each OEM has specific requirements defined according to their product</p> |
| Applus+ Services <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Complete Validation Testing (Laboratory & In-Flight)• Certification through Notified Body Evaluation | Applus+ Services <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Testing and certification through a Notified Body assessment (C5 and C6)• Risk assessment for operations• Full validation (laboratory and flight testing)• Support in liaising with the civil aviation authority | Applus+ Services <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Complete Validation Testing (Laboratory & In-Flight)• Bespoke test systems and manufacturing solutions for product development• Support in test pyramid definition + communications with Aviation Authority |

Figure 7 - Information about the requirements and services available for obtaining drone certification (Source: <https://www.appluslaboratories.com/global/en/what-we-do/industries/drones-uam>)

The open category is designed for lower-risk drone operations with fewer requirements and restrictions, while the specific category addresses higher-risk operations with more tailored requirements and a safety risk assessment. The specific category offers more flexibility for complex operations but requires a thorough assessment of risks and compliance with specific mitigations. The certified category is specifically for the highest-risk operations that require extensive certification, airworthiness evaluations, and pilot licensing. It has similar requirements to those of manned aviation standards. Therefore, search and rescue drones may fall into the specific and certified category depends on the regulations and guidelines established by the aviation authorities in the respective countries.

Figure 8 shows which tests are being performed for the specific category drone. In addition, Applus+ offers remote testing solutions which enhance collaboration, real-time monitoring and control of tests, while providing a seamless user experience³¹.

As the drone technology landscape advances, the demands of certification may become increasingly complex. The inclusion of remote testing solutions, exemplified by Applus+, highlights a commitment to fostering innovation and efficiency within the certification process. These solutions not only enhance collaboration but also facilitate real-time test monitoring and control, providing a user-friendly and seamless experience for all involved parties. Given the evolving regulatory framework for drones, collaboration among industry experts, certification authorities, and aviation regulators becomes paramount. This collaborative effort is important in ensuring the safe and responsible integration of drones into airspace.

³¹ <https://www.appluslaboratories.com/global/en/what-we-do/service-sheet/remote-testing-solutions>

	OUTDOOR (FLIGHT) TESTING		
	Geo-Caging (In Lab Conditions) – Specific to C6		Geo-Caging (In Flight Conditions) – Specific to C6
	Programmable Trajectory (In Lab Conditions) – Specific to C6		Programmable Trajectory (In Flight Conditions) – Specific to C6
	Flight Termination System (In Lab Conditions)		Flight Termination System (In Flight Conditions)
	MTOM		Maximum Speed
	Maximum Dimension Characteristic		Maximum Attainable Height
	Mechanical Strength (In Lab Conditions)		Safety Controllable
	UA Tethering System		Mechanical Strength (In Flight Conditions)
	Impact at Terminal Velocity (In Lab Conditions)		Impact at Terminal Velocity (In Flight Conditions)
	Minimise Injury to People (In Lab Conditions)		Minimise Injury to People (In Flight Conditions)
	Command and Control (C2) (In Lab Conditions)		Command and Control Monitoring (C2) (In Flight Conditions)
	Sound Power		Battery Low-Level
	Electrical Power		Lighting (In Flight Conditions)
	Lighting (In Lab Conditions)		Follow-Me Mode
	Flight Termination System (In Lab Conditions)		Low Speed Mode
	Unique Physical Serial Number (In Lab Conditions)		Auto, Control Modes Conditions
	Direct Remote Identification (In Lab Conditions)		Direct Remote Identification (In Flight Conditions)
	Network Remote Identification (In Lab Conditions)		Network Remote Identification (In Flight Conditions)
	Geo-Awareness and Airspaces Limitation Function (In Lab Conditions)		Geo-Awareness and Airspaces Limitation Function (In Flight Conditions)
	Manufacturer’s Instructions		
	Information Notice		

Figure 8 - Tests for the specific category drone

3.3.2. Operation for emergency response

As previously stated in section 3.1.2.1, the European Commission established the EU Civil Protection Mechanism to strengthen cooperation between the EU countries and Participating States in a disaster situation. Certified rescue teams and response capacities are deployed when the UCPM is activated. The certification process is needed to go through for guarantee that the capacities registered in the pool meet the quality requirements for international deployment.

The certification process follows a three-step: 1) consultative visit, 2) table-top exercise, 3) field exercise. The evaluation in this process as follows;

- 1) Consultative visit (CV)
 - The responsible desk officer in the Commission verifies and discusses the information given in the application with relevant interlocutor at technical and political levels in the country concerned
 - A questionnaire guides this visit
- 2) Table-top exercise (TTX)
 - The decision-making and managerial preparations associated with a deployment of the resource are tested
 - A certification grid ³² for table-top exercises guides the Commission representative and peer certifiers in this process
- 3) Field exercise (FX)
 - An opportunity to test operational aspects during the different phases of an international deployment is provided
 - A certification grid for field exercises provides guidance to certification team

European Commission coordinates the certification process. The Commission provides the necessary support to ensure that all steps in the process can be finalised in a reasonable time, and organises the ModEx³³ simulation exercises as a key platform supporting the process. In the ModEx, the quality of the rescue teams and response capacities is evaluated. In addition, key staff is trained through the training program³⁴ of the UCPM.

One of key staff is peer certifiers. Experts from the Participating States act as the peer certifiers to support the Commission in the certification process. The Peer certifier is part of the certification team that is coordinated by a DG ECHO Pool certifier. The main responsibility of a Peer certifier is to assess the capacity under certification, based on a grid of pre-defined criteria, and using his/her technical expertise and field deployment experience. The role and responsibilities of the peer certifiers are defined in “Terms of reference for Member States and

³² ECPP Certification Process Assessment Tool

https://ercportal.jrc.ec.europa.eu/DesktopModules/ResponseCapacity/Documents/Template%20ECPP_Certification%20Tool_Dec2019.pdf

³³ Modules field and table top exercises. EU MODEX is used for the certification of Modules and Other Response Capacities for the European Civil Protection Pool. It also has the capacity to support the INSARAG International re-classification of Urban Search and Rescue teams and a WHO certification for Emergency Medical Teams. TTX and FX are usually conducted through the ModEX.

³⁴ The structure of the current Training Programme and its individual courses are introduced at <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/759f51d1-282f-11e9-8d04-01aa75ed71a1>

Participating States experts supporting the certification and recertification of capacities in the European Civil Protection Pool”³⁵.

This comprehensive evaluation process, involving multiple stages and expertise, is instrumental in guaranteeing that response capacities meet the stringent standards required for international deployment. It reflects a commitment to preparedness, quality assurance, and the utmost effectiveness in responding to disasters.

3.3.3. Test facilities

Test facilities are important in the certification process by conducting impartial evaluation of products, systems, or services in accordance with established standards and regulations. These facilities are required to deliver assessments that are accurate, unbiased, and trustworthy. The test facilities are equipped with specialized equipment and personnel trained to conduct a wide range of tests. These tests may include performance evaluations, safety assessments, environmental impact studies, and more. The goal is to thoroughly assess whether the product or service meets the required standards and regulations.

In disaster management, the role of test facility for certification is important in safeguarding lives, reducing property damage, and facilitating efficient response and recovery efforts. The test facilities may evaluate a wide range of safety equipment used in disaster management, including personal protective equipment, firefighting equipment, and emergency medical devices. Certificates issued after testing performed by specialized facilities ensure that certified equipment perform as expected, ultimately reducing the risks faced by FRs and disaster survivors. Specific examples of the test facilities in disaster management:

In environmental disasters, such as chemical/oil spills, test facilities for certification may validate the safety and compliance of environmental clean-up technologies and procedures. Then, the certification can ensure that the clean-up process is effective and minimizes long-term environmental damage.

With the growing importance of cybersecurity in disaster management, test facilities for cybersecurity are important to certify the cybersecurity measures implemented in critical systems and technologies, providing protection against cyberattacks and strengthening the overall resilience of disaster response efforts.

Disaster management involves various technologies and systems that must work seamlessly together. Interoperability testing is crucial for certifying that diverse technologies can communicate and collaborate effectively during disasters, facilitating coordinated responses. It's important to note that interoperability testing may not always involve physical facilities but often consists of specialized testing services provided by accredited test facilities.

While test facilities are essential for evaluating how products and systems perform, it's crucial to understand that accreditation plays a pivotal role in enhancing the credibility and reliability of these assessments.

3.3.4. Test methods

D7.3 (System Validation and Evaluation) outlines five types of testing methodologies aimed at ensuring the effectiveness, compliance, and quality of the VALKYRIES outcomes. These testing

³⁵<https://ercportal.jrc.ec.europa.eu/DesktopModules/ResponseCapacity/Documents/Revised%20ToR%20Peer%20Certifiers.pdf>

types may play a crucial role in the certification process, contributing to the verification and validation of harmonization opportunities identified within the project:

1. Verification by Inspection

Inspection involves a thorough examination of the product or system using basic senses. This visual and manual inspection ensures that the product adheres to its required physical characteristics and control mechanisms. For software systems, this involves checking user interfaces and verifying that they meet specified requirements. The inspection is one of the methods used during the certification process to assess the product's compliance with predefined requirements. During the inspection process, inspectors or evaluators closely examine various aspects of the product or system, including its physical characteristics, interfaces, user interfaces (in the case of software), and control mechanisms. They compare these aspects against the established standards and guidelines to confirm compliance.

Inspectors may also review documentation and records related to the product's development, testing, and maintenance. This documentation should demonstrate that the product has been designed, built, and maintained in accordance with the standards and guidelines.

2. Verification by Test

Testing is a controlled process used to verify the capabilities of a system or product. It involves systematically assessing whether a functionality operates as expected based on predefined specifications, pre-conditions, and post-conditions expectations. As mentioned in D7.3, VALKYRIES considers the execution of four types of tests:

- 1) Unit tests – Automated tests that verify specific functionalities of the system.
- 2) Integration tests – Evaluate how different unitary elements work together correctly.
- 3) Reliability tests – Assess the reliability of functions under various environmental conditions.
- 4) Security tests – Evaluate vulnerability and risk in different attack surfaces.

Testing in the certification process serve as a critical means of verifying that a product aligns with its design requirements and can perform reliably in situations. Testing can assess the product's performance under different loads and usage patterns. They also evaluate its ability to function reliably in scenarios that may involve unexpected events or conditions, such as those encountered in disaster management situations.

3. Verification by Analysis

Analysis-based verification is applied in situations where rigorous and accurate analysis is possible or when conducting traditional tests is neither feasible nor profitable.

In certification, verification by analysis can provide a cost-effective and efficient means of certification while maintaining a high level of confidence in the product's performance and safety. Examples of how analysis-based verification can be applied in certification:

- 1) Statistical Analysis – Statistical methods can be used to assess the product's reliability and performance. For example, statistical modelling can predict failure rates, which are crucial in industries like aerospace and healthcare.
- 2) Computer Simulations – Simulations are often employed in industries like automotive and aerospace to model and simulate the behaviour of complex systems. This can include crash simulations for vehicles or airflow simulations for aircraft.

- 3) Qualitative Analysis - Qualitative analysis techniques such as failure mode and effects analysis (FMEA), can be used to identify and mitigate potential risks and failure modes in a product or system.

In many cases, verification by analysis is used in conjunction with traditional testing methods. It can complement physical testing by providing additional insights and confirming compliance in situations where physical testing alone may not be sufficient.

4. Verification by Demonstration

Demonstration verifies that a system or part of it operates as expected based on observable functional operation. It doesn't require specialized test equipment or extensive subsequent analysis.

The goal of the demonstration in certification could be to confirm that the product behaves as specified. For example, in the case of software, it ensures that clicking a button results in the expected action or output. In addition, by mimicking user actions during demonstration, evaluators can assess not only the technical correctness of the product but also its user-friendliness and how well it supports end-users in accomplishing their tasks. Thus, demonstration could be an essential part of the certification process by providing valuable insight into technical correctness and user satisfaction.

5. Verification by Feedback Questionnaire

In VALKYRIES, this method involves collecting feedback from FRs who participate in use cases. Questionnaires are designed to evaluate technological tools, operative procedures, and educational materials. In the context of certification, verification by feedback questionnaire can assess the product's real-world applicability, usability, impact on collaboration, and overall user experience. This feedback is valuable for both improving the product and demonstrating its compliance with certification requirements.

Additionally, recognizing the broader applicability of verification by feedback questionnaires across various fields, we have disseminated a structured questionnaire that explored the current certification landscape (ANNEX B). By incorporating diverse perspectives from stakeholders in certification, this feedback data may serve to enhance the overall certification process.

D7.4, titled "Reference Integration and lessons learned" assesses the effectiveness of the project's outcomes, particularly in terms of integration, validation, and evaluation methodologies. When seeking certification for a system or software product, having a well-defined validation and evaluation methodology is critical to demonstrate compliance with industry standards and guidelines. D7.4 discusses various testing techniques, integration methods, and lessons learned during the VALKYRIES project. These insights can be invaluable for certification efforts. Certification processes often require extensive testing and validation to ensure that a product meets specific criteria. The integration testing techniques mentioned in D7.4:

1. Black Box Testing

Black box testing focuses on evaluating how a system functions without delving into its internal structure and design. It tests the system's responsiveness to various inputs or actions. For instance, it can be used to ensure that a software product meets the needs of its users and functions as intended within the specified requirements.

In certification process, the black box testing can be utilized as follows: Test cases are defined based on the certification requirements, standards, and specifications relevant to the product or system. These test cases should focus on the product's expected behaviour and functionality as outlined in the certification criteria. During black box testing, focus on identifying defects, deviations from expected behaviours, or any issues that might prevent the product from meeting certification requirements. Thoroughly documented results can serve as evidence of its suitability for certification.

2. Whitebox Testing

Whitebox Testing delves into the internal workings of an application. In the certification process, it is used to validate the internal logic of a system and ensure that all components work together as expected. White box testing becomes valuable when assessing how different parts of a system integrate and function cohesively. By providing a transparent view of the system's internals, white box testing helps certification authorities ensure that the product or system complies with the required standards and is fit for certification.

3. Incremental testing

Certification efforts often benefit from incremental testing, which involves testing smaller code pieces as they are developed rather than waiting for the entire system to be completed. This approach helps identify and address issues more quickly, reducing the risk of integration problems and improving overall system quality.

4. Stubs and Drivers

Stubs are used to simulate the behaviour of larger components that are part of the system being certified. Drivers, on the other hand, simulate missing components or external systems that the certified system interacts with. Stubs and drivers allow for the isolation of specific components or modules within the system. This isolation is valuable during certification because it enables focused testing of individual components and their interactions without the need for the entire system to be fully integrated. In addition, for certification, it is essential to verify that the system's interactions with other components, whether internal or external, meet specified standards and requirements. Stubs and drivers facilitate this verification by providing controlled interfaces for testing. Stubs and drivers are also valuable for regression testing during the certification process. When changes or updates are made to the system, these simulated components can be quickly adapted to ensure that integration with other components remains intact.

5. Bottom-up Integration Testing

Bottom-up Integration testing allows for a detailed examination of each system component, module, or unit. This approach helps in the early detection of issues and defects within the individual components. Certification often requires that each component functions correctly in isolation before being integrated into the larger system. Bottom-up testing ensures that problems are identified and addressed at the earliest stages. After certifying the correctness and compliance of individual components, the integration process occurs sequentially. This may mean that certified components are gradually combined and tested together, ensuring that each step of integration maintains the required standards.

6. Top-down Integration Testing

Top-down Integration testing is an approach that initiates testing with higher-level system components, like the user interface, and then gradually progresses to testing

lower-level functions and modules. Certification often places emphasis on user experience and user interactions. Top-down testing aligns with this focus by starting with the user interface, ensuring that it meets usability and functionality requirements from the outset. The progressive nature of top-down testing may mean that system functionalities are tested incrementally. This is advantageous in certification because it allows for step-by-step verification of features and their integration into the larger system, making it easier to pinpoint problems or deviations from certification standards.

7. Sandwich Testing

Sandwich testing is a methodology used to evaluate the middle layer of an application or system where various modules and components interact. This approach ensures that different layers, modules, and external systems function harmoniously together, which is valuable for assessing integration aspects crucial to meeting certification standards. Many certified systems need to interact with external systems, databases, or services. Sandwich testing can be particularly valuable in these scenarios because it evaluates how the system communicates and exchanges data with these external entities. Certification may involve verifying the integrity of data as it moves through the system's layers. Sandwich testing can assess whether data is transformed accurately, meets validation criteria, and is securely transmitted between different components. In addition, certified systems often need to meet performance and scalability requirements. Sandwich testing allows for the evaluation of how the middle layer handles increased data loads and concurrent user interactions. This is essential to ensure that the system performs reliably under real-world conditions.

Those testing methodologies can provide valuable tools and approaches that can be effectively utilized in the certification process.

3.4. European Accreditation Infrastructure

Accreditation is defined as the procedure by which an Authorised Body formally recognises that an organisation is competent to perform a particular conformity assessment activity;

- Conformity assessment bodies include certification bodies, inspection bodies and laboratories
- The final objective is the free circulation of products in other countries without the need to undergo further testing, inspection, certification, etc.

The main international accreditation bodies are;

- **European Cooperation for Accreditation**³⁶ (EA) that integrates nationally, European Union (EU) and European Free Trade Association (EFTA) recognised laboratory accreditation bodies and certification and inspection bodies.
- **International Laboratories Accreditation Cooperation**³⁷ (ILAC) integrates laboratory accreditation bodies from all over the world.
- **International Accreditation Forum**³⁸ (IAF) integrates accreditation bodies from certification bodies around the world.

³⁶ <https://european-accreditation.org/>

³⁷ <http://www.ilac.org/>

³⁸ <http://www.iaf.nu/>

Within these organisations, international agreements based on mutual recognition of certificates and reports issued by accredited bodies have been established which facilitate trade and create an environment that facilitates the achievement of the ultimate goal: "accredited once, accepted everywhere".

This allows the issuance of a report or certificate from an accredited entity in a Multilateral Recognition Arrangement (MLA) member country, which will be homogeneous and accepted by the rest of the MLA member countries.

The legal framework for the accreditation within Europe is the EU Regulation (EC) 765/2008³⁹.

The Regulation identifies the European co-operation for Accreditation (EA) as the sole association entrusted to manage accreditation at European level and defines its responsibilities and obligations in this respect.⁴⁰ It places an obligation on EU Member States to accept the results issued by the Conformity Assessment Bodies accredited by any of the EA MLA signatories.

Requirements for accreditation are set in Regulation 765/2008⁴¹. The main principles of accreditation are;

- 1 accreditation body per EU country (it is possible however to use another country's National Accreditation Body)
- accreditation is a public sector activity and a not-for-profit activity
- there is no competition between national accreditation bodies
- stakeholders are represented
- accreditation is the preferred means of demonstrating technical capacity of notified bodies in the regulated area

National Accreditation Bodies (NAB) are members of the EA committees that cooperates with the Commission and they are the (single) body in a Member State with authority derived from the state to perform accreditation (see Figure 9jError! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.).

³⁹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2008:218:0030:0047:EN:PDF>

⁴⁰ <https://european-accreditation.org/about-ea/relations-with-european-commission/>

⁴¹ [EUR-Lex - 32008R0765 - EN - EUR-Lex \(europa.eu\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2008:218:0030:0047:EN:PDF)

Figure 9 – National Accreditation Bodies

NAB of countries related to the use cases in Valkyries are listed in Table 2.

Use-Case	Country	NAB	Link
Use Case 1 Fire	Portugal	IPAC - Instituto Português de Acreditação, I.P.	http://www.ipac.pt/
	Spain	ENAC – Entidad Nacional de Acreditacion	https://www.enac.es/web/english
Use Case 2 Toxic plume	Italy	ACCREDIA – Italian Accreditation body	https://www.accredia.it/
	Slovakia	SNAS – Slovak National Accreditation Service	https://www.snas.sk/sk
Use Case 3 Earthquake	Bulgaria	BAS - Bulgarian Accreditation Service	https://www.nab-bas.bg/en/
	Greece	ESYD – Hellenic Accreditation System	https://esyd.gr/main/
Use Case 4 On sea	Denmark	DANAK – Danish Accreditation	https://danak.org/
	Netherland	RVA – Raad voor Accreditatie	https://www.rva.nl/
	Norway	NA – Norsk akkreditering	https://www.akkreditert.no/

Table 2 - National Accreditation Bodies related to the use cases in Valkyries

The EU Regulation (EC) 765/2008 is part of the “New European Legislative Framework” (NLF) that rules for the accreditation of Conformity Assessment Body (CAB) (laboratories, inspection or certification bodies).

These CABs are appointed ("notified") by the EU Member States (Notifying Authorities) that depend on the NAC and listed in an information system maintained by the European Commission⁴². The requirements to become a CAB are assessed and compliance is regularly monitored by the notifying authorities. This guarantees that they have the technical capacities to perform their duties and meet certain standards.

3.4.1. Accreditation for ITSEF

In the context of IT security and cybersecurity, accreditation is a crucial process that ensures organizations meet internationally recognized standards and requirements. Accreditation bodies typically assess organizations against internationally recognized standards and requirements, such as ISO/IEC 17025 (testing and calibration laboratories), ISO/IEC 17020 (inspection bodies), or ISO/IEC 17021 (certification bodies). These standards help guarantee the competence and reliability of IT security testing and evaluation laboratories.

The accreditation bodies are usually recognized by national or international authorities, and may be members of organizations such as the International Accreditation Forum (IAF) or the European Co-operation for Accreditation (EA) which are mentioned earlier. In the field of IT security testing and evaluation, there are specific standards that accreditation bodies and IT security evaluation laboratories adhere to:

⁴² <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/nando/>

- ISO/IEC TS 23532-1 and 2:2021
Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection – Requirements for the competence of IT security testing and evaluation laboratories
Part 1: Evaluation for ISO/IEC 15408
Part 2: Testing for ISO/IEC 19790
- ISO/IEC 19896 series 1-3 :2018
IT security techniques – Competence requirements for information security testers and evaluators
Part 1: Introduction, concepts and general requirements
Part 2: Knowledge, skills and
Part 3: Knowledge, skills and effectiveness requirements for ISO/IEC 15408 evaluators
- ISO/IEC 15408-1:2022
Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection – Evaluation criteria for IT security – Part 1: Introduction and general model
- ISO/IEC 19790:2012
Information technology – Security techniques – Security requirements for cryptographic modules

These standards, among others, contribute to the establishment of robust cybersecurity practices, ensuring that IT systems, products, and services meet stringent security requirements and can be trusted in critical applications, including disaster management and data protection.

IT security evaluation laboratories primarily evaluate products and systems according to ISO/IEC 15408 (Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection – Evaluation criteria for IT security – Part 1: Introduction and general model)⁴³ and ISO/IEC 18045 (Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection – Evaluation criteria for IT security – Methodology for IT security evaluation)⁴⁴.

The accreditation body for evaluation laboratories typically follows ISO/IEC 17025 (Testing and calibration laboratories)⁴⁵. The EUCC for ITSEF adheres to ISO/IEC TS 23532-1 and ISO/IEC 19896-3. The accreditation body for certification bodies uses ISO/IEC 17065 (Conformity assessment – Requirements for bodies certifying products, processes and services)⁴⁶ to assess and accredit them. In essence, accreditation ensures that organizations involved in IT security testing, evaluation, and certification adhere to stringent international standards, enhancing the reliability and trustworthiness of their services in the ever-critical field of cybersecurity.

3.5. Challenges

Digitalization can bring a number of benefits to search and rescue such as rapid-response, risk reduction, efficient information sharing, etc. Novel technologies have been implemented in SAR system, such as SAR equipment are expected to operate remotely and new technology ICT components are integrated ((Nzengu et al., 2021), (Yang, Jiang, Sun, Cheng, & Feng, 2020), and (Al-Kaff, Gómez-Silva, Miguel Moreno, De La Escalera, & Armingol, 2019)). Figure 10 shows an unmanned ground vehicle that can be applied to SAR system.

⁴³ <https://www.iso.org/standard/72891.html>

⁴⁴ <https://www.iso.org/standard/72889.html>

⁴⁵ <https://www.iso.org/ISO-IEC-17025-testing-and-calibration-laboratories.html>

⁴⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standard/46568.html>

The UGV is core components, but functionality of whole system is achieved by an integration with other devices and sub-system. For this complex system, in addition to the certification for each component, it may need an integrated certification for this intricate system. Moreover, the process for the certification could take more time if there are no laws and standards for the novel technology.

One of the objectives for certification is to reduce risk through the adequate conformity assessment and evaluation. In order to enhance safety and build trust in this kind of complicated system (UAVs, UGVs, USVs, etc.), not only product itself but also software quality and operating skills should be thoroughly evaluated. In addition, some acceptable level of security and privacy should be achieved based on the regulations and the standards. In this context, it is important to establish customized criteria for the SAR equipment/system/operation of the certification.

Figure 10 - Unmanned ground vehicle equipped with an electronic command, control and communication solution and secure autonomous mobility software⁴⁷

A similar example of complexity can be found in existing emergency coordination platform (e.g., GEMMA), there are complex connection between the integrated components such as UAV, sensor, communication component, etc. For efficient and accurate information sharing between each component, it may need to operate with qualified components under standardized regulation.

One of important parts of the certification process is to show whether the subject to be certified complies with necessary requirements. In this regard, it is important to understand the requirements to be satisfied in emergency response based on the expectations and needs of the end-user (e.g., first responders).

Novel equipment, technologies and guidelines are being developed for the first responders to protect them and to enhance their abilities (Refer to Section 5.2). Accordingly, new tests, conformity assessment criteria and modifications on the evaluation facilities are necessary to certify those novel solution.

⁴⁷ <https://www.army-technology.com/news/milrem-unmanned-ground-system-ec/>

To improve sustainability in the harmonized certification process, interoperability and possible joint usage of evaluation facilities need to be considered.

3.6. Definition of scope

The compliance with green developing and provisioning regulations will also be present at certification level, exploring how the technological, procedural and collaborative disruptions in the sector may coexist with the global efforts against climate change.

- 1) Equipment
 - a) Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (drone)
 - b) Unmanned Surface Vehicle (sea drone)
 - c) Unmanned Ground Vehicles (rovers)
 - d) Communications equipment
 - e) Tagging equipment
 - f) Wearable equipment (tablet, bracelet, etc.)
- 2) Operation
- 3) Sustainability in certification, conformity, and evaluation
 - a) How to define sustainability regarding certification and evaluation
- 4) Map other initiatives for certification and evaluation
- 5) Identify gaps and opportunities

4. Current situation

4.1. Forest fire (Valkyries use-case #1)

The demonstration case is based on a forest fire that starts in Spain and rapidly spreads towards the border of Portugal and the national park Serra de S. Mamede. The emergency is called in to 112 Extremadura and the operation coordination centre will notify and activate the needed emergency response resources. The 112 Extremadura has implemented the GEMMA Atos emergency management system for cooperation between police, firefighters, medical emergency services, command centre and in-field units⁴⁸

Figure 11 - The Global emergency management system (GEMMA by Atos)

The emergency management system is built on open source components and international standards. Standards mentioned in marketing documentation indicate that the GEMMA system is using encrypted communication over 4G LTE, can integrate Internet of Things (IoT) devices and personal mobile phones, and support critical communication also over MCPTT (Mission Critical Push-To-Talk).

The Portuguese operational centres (CONor and COSul) for emergency calls and emergency services are implementing emergency management technology from the Avaya company (Avaya Aura®, Avaya Breeze® and Avaya Scopia®). The different emergency management systems used

⁴⁸ https://atos.net/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/Emergency-management_en1-web.pdf

by Spain and Portugal could lead to difficulties in sharing information and must be evaluated further.

Open questions:

- *How will Portugal's Avaya system work together with Spain's GEMMA system?*
- *How is drone surveillance integrated into the Avaya and GEMMA systems, and how does Portugal and Spain*

4.2. Fire and toxic plum (Valkyries use-case #2)

Cross border collaboration between Italy and Slovakia first responders. The emphasis is on enhanced reaction in a multi-casualty incident, basic and specific equipment deployment, first aid and medical technologies and procedures and cross border collaboration.

Challenges for this case includes activation of national responders and information exchange, with possibility to ask for support based on bilateral agreements, with neighbouring countries, but also communication and response management within the different national responding units. Possible communication difficulties (SITNO system in Slovakia which is based on Tetrapol and probably 3G/4G connectivity as well), difficulties with sharing data, reliable and quick measurements of toxicity in environment and coordination between units.

Open questions:

- *Equipment and standards for toxicity measurements*
- *Standards and SOPs (standard operational procedures) for and within different responders units*
- *Drones and unmanned technologies to get situational awareness as well as reconnaissance, detection and identification of hazardous materials.*

4.3. Cross-border earthquake response (Valkyries use-case #3)

The use-case is planned around an earthquake incident on the border between Bulgaria and Greece. Both radio-stations and mobile phones will be used for communication and information exchange. Aerial drones can help to gain situational awareness and reconnaissance of the area.

There are several challenges with this emergency scenario, the mobile network has low coverage in the area and power outages are likely due to the nature of the disaster. The affected area of an earthquake can be large, so information from airplanes, helicopters, drones, vehicles, surveillance cameras and people on ground could provide useful information to get an overview of the extent of the disaster.

Possible drone types to test during UC3:

- 1) Drone DeltaQuad
- 2) Drone DJI Mavic Zoom
- 3) Drone DJI Enterprise Advanced

The drones are equipped with sensor for alpha and Beta particles; moisture, temperature and atmospheric pressure module and module for detection of concentrated CO gas; dust particle concentration detection module.

The data collected by the drones will be transferred to a 3D Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of the terrain and will be integrated with a GIS. Besides, visualization of drone's trajectory will be provided.

The plan for communication and information system is to use the mobile deployable cellular network for crises management developed by BDI.

The use of 112 in Greece

A service called 112 offers integrated emergency communications and has both an inbound and an outbound component. In the inbound component, civilians can report a situation and trigger the corresponding authorities and first responders to assist in an emergency event anywhere in Greece by calling the 112 free of charge in an emergency. In the outbound component, the Hellenic Civil Protection can inform the civilians who are located in a danger (or a potential danger) zone in order to take the required safety measures or to evacuate the area. When an incident or dangerous situation that poses an immediate threat to your health and safety is about to happen or is already in progress, the outbound component enables so civilians will receive warnings via a variety of technologies and communication channels so they can take protective action.

Open questions:

- *How should seismic information be distributed.*

4.4. Search and rescue at sea (Valkyries use-case #4)

Response to disasters on the high seas is in nature a cross-national undertaking. It is therefore regulated by the conventions set by the United Nations. Two agencies under UN: the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) and the International Maritime Organization (IMO) are concerned with aeronautical and maritime safety, and thus interested in saving lives and rendering effective SAR services to people in distress. Member states of ICAO (currently 193 states⁴⁹) and IMO (currently 175 states⁵⁰) cooperate to develop and sponsor vital standards and recommendations, and state authorities are encouraged to promote harmonization of aeronautical and maritime SAR services⁵¹.

The legal basis for coordinated SAR services is partly based on the International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS), the International Convention on Maritime Search and Rescue, the Convention on International Civil Aviation, and the UN Convention on Law of the Sea from 1982.

Article 98, paragraph 2, of the UN Convention on Law of the Sea states that "Every coastal State shall promote the establishment, operation and maintenance of an adequate and effective search and rescue service regarding safety on and over the water and, where circumstances so require, by way of mutual regional arrangements, cooperate with neighbouring States for this purpose"

The UN convention and the UN member states expects the states to organize a national SAR organization or organize one in cooperation with neighbouring nations.

The global SAR system according to the IAMSAR Manual (IAMSAR Manual Vol I, 2019) rely on SAR capability for each vessel. The vessel first on the scene or the most capable vessel will take

⁴⁹ <https://www.icao.int/about-icao/pages/member-states.aspx>

⁵⁰ <https://www.imo.org/en/OurWork/ERO/Pages/MemberStates.aspx>

⁵¹ Page 1-1 IAMSAR Manual Vol I, 2019

the role as on-scene coordinator (OSC) and will be supported by a Rescue Coordination Centre (RCC) that is responsible for efficient organization of search and rescue services and coordination of these services.

Efficient search and rescue will depend on the equipment and facilities available at the scene or could be dispatched to the scene. Therefore, the RCC must quickly get an overview of the resources available and deploy them as needed. The list of capabilities and equipment given below is extracted from the IAMSAR Manual (IAMSAR Manual Vol I, 2019).

Equipment on board standard vessels and SAR vessels (coast guard and rescue vessels)

- Navigational equipment used on SAR craft, including their accuracy and limitations
- Provision of assistance to aircraft (homing, communication, ditching)
- Survival craft and equipment
- Equipment for removal of survivors from ships, other craft, survival craft, and the sea
- First aid-, artificial respiration-, general care equipment for survivors and injured
- Fire-fighting methods and associated equipment.
- SAR communications procedures and regional communications plans
- Rescue lifting systems and other devices for removing survivors from water
- Fundamental first aid equipment, with emphasis on revival of the partially drowned and treatment for shock, prolonged immersion, hypothermia, and burns
- Cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR)
- Automated external defibrillators (AEDs)
- Administration of oxygen

Equipment and capabilities in air support

- Ability to detect objects from the air under monotonous conditions for prolonged periods of time
- Day and night scanning procedures
- Precision in flying search patterns, tracks and height, flying at low altitude and contour searches
- Dropping of supplies
- Landing and take-off from confined areas
- Winching by helicopters
- Knowledge of the appearance from the air of wreckage, associated marks, life raft, lifeboat, dye marker trails, persons
- Communication capabilities and procedures

Equipment and capabilities in land search and rescue facilities

- Search technique
- First aid and general care of survivors.
- Radio communication equipment and procedures
- Determining the position in the wreckage of both survivors and bodies, may be of vital importance to the accident investigation

Requirements for SAR personnel and facilities:

- Undergo training and SAR exercises
- Coordinate air-surface SAR activities

- Know signalling methods and codes
- Handle survival craft and equipment
- Storage and maintenance of special equipment
- Removal of survivors from ships, other craft survival craft, and the sea
- Radio operators must be qualified in accordance with Article 55 of the ITU Radio Regulations for operating the specific equipment with which individual SAR craft are fitted.
- Keeping a good look-out for locating objects and persons in the sea.
- Regular training in first aid, also with demonstrations and exercises

Key points from IAMSAR search and rescue requirements:

- Based on international UN conventions
- Common international definitions of organisation of SAR activities with clear responsibility of the affected parties (national states, aircrafts and vessels)
- Established radio communication system and distress alert system (Inmarsat, VHF, DSC on VHF/MF or HF)
- Certified equipment for distress beacon for cospas-sarsat satellite system (C/S T.001 EPIRB, ELT, PLB)
- Type approval of distress beacons according to the process shown in Figure 12.

Specifications for distress beacons used for maritime distress:

C/S T.001 - Specification for Cospas-Sarsat 406 MHz Distress Beacons

C/S T.007 - Cospas-Sarsat 406 MHz Distress Beacon Type Approval Standard

C/S T.008 - Cospas-Sarsat Acceptance of 406 MHz Beacon Type Approval Test Facilities

C/S G.005 - Cospas-Sarsat Guidelines on 406 MHz Beacon Coding, Registration and Type Approval

Figure 12 - Type approval process C/S T.007 (Reich, 2022)

Accredited beacon test facilities according to Cospas-sarsat (cospas-sarsat, 2022):

Electronic Proving Ground (EPG) Fort Huachuca, AZ, USA

Mayak Bincos Moscow, Russia

Omega Sevastopol, Ukraine

TC NIIR Moscow, Russia

TÜV SÜD Fareham, Hampshire, UK

Example of operational awareness system for maritime incidents

The Norwegian coast guard and the Coastal Administration is using the SeaCOP software system for monitoring, detection and surveillance of maritime incidents. The SeaCOP is a centralised system capable of monitoring multiple operations and locations, and uses the MBR (Maritime Broadband Radio) system for communication (see Figure 13).

Figure 13 - SeaCOP maritime surveillance and emergency response (Norbit Aptomar)

5. Overview of standardisation and certification

According to ISO, certification is a procedure by which a third party gives written assurance that a product, process or service is in conformity with certain legal acts and standards. Therefore, the exploration of the standards is essential for the certification scheme. In addition, ongoing and past activities aiming for improvement of certification process are explored.

5.1. Standards and certification

Standards are voluntary guidelines providing technical specifications for products, services, and processes. The standard comprises rules, guidelines, processes, or characteristics that allow users to achieve the same outcome.

According to the *Regulation (EU) No1025/2012*, standard means a technical specification, adopted by a recognised standardisation body, for repeated or continuous application, with which compliance is not compulsory, and which is one of the following;

- International standard – a standard adopted by an international standardization body. Three largest organizations are:
 - ISO⁵² – the international organization for standardization
 - IEC⁵³ – the international electrotechnical commission
 - ITU⁵⁴ – the international telecommunication union
- European standard – a standard adopted by a European standardization organization
 - CEN⁵⁵ – the European Committee for Standardization
 - CENELEC⁵⁶ – the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
 - ETSI⁵⁷ – the European Telecommunications Standards Institute
- Harmonized standard – a European standard adopted on the basis of a request made by the Commission for the application of Union harmonization legislation
 - Harmonized standard can be used to demonstrate that products, services, or processes comply with relevant EU legislation
- National standard – a standard adopted by a national standardization body
 - The European standard carries with it the obligation to be implemented at national level by being given the status of a national standard and by withdrawal of any conflicting national standard. Therefore, the European standard automatically becomes a national standard in each of the CEN-CENELEC member countries. However, International standards can be adopted as national standards, but national adoption is not obligatory.

An example from standard to certification: ambulance

For example, EN 1789:2020 *Medical vehicles and their equipment - Road ambulances* specifies requirements for the design, testing, performance and equipping of road ambulances used for the transport, monitoring, treatment and care of patients. Therefore, this standard is useful for

⁵² <https://www.iso.org/home.html>

⁵³ <https://iec.ch/homepage>

⁵⁴ <https://www.itu.int/en/Pages/default.aspx>

⁵⁵ <https://www.cencenelec.eu/>

⁵⁶ <https://www.cencenelec.eu/>

⁵⁷ <https://www.etsi.org/>

road ambulance manufacturers, hospitals, ambulance services, emergency response services, manufacturers and suppliers for road ambulance component, etc.

Road ambulances are subject to a higher risk in use. The exact circumstances of operation cannot always be planned or anticipated in detail. Testing of special purpose vehicle, such as an ambulance, is complex. Multiple functions (e.g. fixations, maintain systems, noise, illumination, heating, cooling etc.) may require numerous tests, which can be destructive. In EN 1789:2020, carefully planned tests according to worst-case scenario strategies have reduced the number of destructive tests without sacrificing test qualities. In addition, EN 1789:2020 checks all the references and regulations, paying special attention to EU regulations and updated standardization rules.

This standard is a voluntary standard. However, due to the importance of the requirements for ensuring the safety of both patients and paramedics, it has been widely viewed as a purchasing requirement for new ambulances within the health industry. Therefore, the manufactures obtain the certification for this standard even it is not mandatory.

5.2. Research projects and initiatives

This section provides relevant research projects, existing certification schemes and initiatives. The research projects include aspects such as certification, crisis management. For a complete overview of the identified initiatives, see additional excel file.

To protect the first responders and to enhance their capacities, there are several projects which are related to novel tools and technologies for first responders. Even though only few projects have included certification-related topics, it is worth referring to: 1) Operation conditions, 2) Required functions, 3) Information related to validation (e.g., evaluation procedure, evaluation facilities, exercise, etc.) for the novel solution.

DRIVER+ (May 2014 – April 2020)

- Project Title: Driving innovation in crisis management for European Resilience
- Scope: Improving the way capability development and innovation management is tackled in crisis management
- Objective;
 - Development of a pan-European Test-bed for crisis management capability development
 - Development of a well-balanced comprehensive portfolio of crisis management solutions
 - Facilitate a shared understanding of crisis management across Europe
- Relevant information;
 - To develop a pan-European Test-bed, the requirements specifications (meaning both must-do requirements and should/could-do wishes) of the to-be-developed Test-bed are provided ([DRIVERPLUS D923.11 Functional-Specification-of-the-Test-bed.pdf \(driver-project.eu\)](#))
 - In terms of sustainability for the certification, the pan-European test-beds can be used to evaluate/test the SAR capabilities in the certification process
 - The Trial Guidance Methodology (TGM) Handbook and the Trial Guidance Tool (TGT) provide a description the pan-European Test-bed, a training how to use all methods, tools and user network of this Test-bed best and a tool guiding users through the process of preparing, executing and evaluating their own

realistic, structured trial in an objective, data-driven manner ([DRIVER+ – Trial Guidance Methodology \(ercis.org\)](#))

- The identification, specification, and assessment of DRIVER+ results, which have the potential to become a standard for crisis and disaster management is presented ([DRIVER D955.21 Report-on-DRIVER-standardisation-potentials-Final.pdf \(driver-project.eu\)](#))

STRATEGY (September 2020 – August 2023)

- Project Title: Facilitating EU pre-standardization process through streamlining and validating interoperability in systems and procedures involved in the crisis management cycle
- Scope: pre-standardisation activities in the crisis management
- Objective;
 - STRATEGY will develop a pan-European framework of the pre-standardisation activities for systems, solutions and procedures, addressing crisis management, validated by sustainable tests and evaluation frameworks which will improve the crisis management and disaster resilience capabilities
- Relevant information:
 - STRATEGY hosts workshops with end users (i.e., First Responders) and standardisation bodies to define disaster scenarios that will be used to test existing crisis management standards
 - STRATEGY will simulate the disaster scenarios in Table-Top Exercises to test selected standards with First Responders and gather user feedback. This feedback will narrow down which standards should be validated in the final Full-Scale Exercise and boost selected standards already showcasing positive results
 - STRATEGY implements a final Full-Scale Exercise alongside industry, research organisations, end users and crisis management bodies. Feedback from stakeholders in the Full-Scale Exercise will be used to determine which pre-standardisation items should be recommended to standardisation bodies and policy makers.

FASTER (May 2019 – April 2022)

- Project Title: First responder advanced technologies for safe and efficient emergency response
- Scope: Novel technologies for the first responders
- Objective: FASTER aims to address the challenges associated with the protection of first responders in hazardous environments, while at the same time enhancing their capabilities in terms of situational awareness and communication
- Relevant information;
 - User requirements and specification of system requirements could be useful for harmonized conformity assessment criteria.
 - Demonstration and evaluation of the novel technologies

Search and Rescue (July 2020 – June 2023)

- Project Title: Search and Rescue: Emerging technologies for the Early location of Entrapped victims under Collapsed Structures and Advanced Wearables for risk assessment and First Responders Safety in SAR
- Scope: To develop and promote the underlying framework (interoperability among systems and equipment, training and awareness)
- Objective: Establishment of an efficient synchronisation framework managing the data, developed services and information flow between the different authorities involved in emergency management operations and the crisis managers (Rescue forces, Police, Fire-department, etc.)
- Relevant information:
 - One of the expected impact of this project is;
Provide a comprehensive test-bed organisation, in terms of full scale exercises and demonstrations of simulated complex crisis management situations. EU bodies and national organisations may use for testing diverse response frameworks allowing for better operational and societal adaptation to rapidly evolving threats
 - One of the partners – German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence (DFKI) DFKI has been operating an evaluation facility for the assessment of security of IT products in critical infrastructures. Based on this experience, “the Laboratory for Certification and Digital Sovereignty” promotes the development, standardisation and application of certification criteria for AI systems

RESPONDRONE (May 2019 – April 2022)

- Project Title: Novel integrated solution of operating a fleet of drones with multiple synchronized missions for disaster responses (RESPONDRONE)
- Scope: Development of a fleet for drones operated by a single pilot in emergency situations
- Objective: RESPONDRONE will develop and validate an integrated solution for first responders to easily operate a fleet of drones with multiple synchronized missions to enhance their situation assessment capacity and own protection.
- Relevant information:
 - The ResponDrone project funded by the EU and Korean government aims to develop a system for first responders to operate several drones by a single pilot to increase the efficiency of gathering information and overview of the disaster⁵⁸.
 - The solution consists of planning tools for quick and efficient deployment and operation of multiple drones where flight trajectories are provided by a Traffic & Mission Management system. Current EU regulations for safe UAV operation and privacy are considered and documented.
 - A general system architecture has been developed for the ResponDrone platform including UAV drone controller. Communication, ground control with

⁵⁸ <https://respondroneproject.com/>

team and mission control, video processing, data repositories and web services for access.⁵⁹

- Regulatory landscape⁶⁰
- Framework for legal, ethics, privacy and security consideration of drone-based first response⁶¹
- RESPONDRONE will be demonstrated through participation in actual civil protection exercises on Corsica, involving several agencies simultaneously.

INGENIOUS (September 2019 – February 2023)

- Project Title: The First Responder of the Future: A Next Generation Integrated Toolkit (NGIT) for Collaborative Response, increasing protection and augmenting operational capacity
- Scope: Develop a toolkit for augmenting the common operational picture (COP) and enhancing command, control and coordination among first responders
- Objective: Increase resilience against natural and man-made attacks by augmenting response capabilities in all types of disasters. Deliver NGIT (Next Generation Integrated Toolkit) for collaborative response validated in the field.
- Relevant information:
 - INGENIOUS is developing, integrating, testing and validating a Next Generation Integrated Toolkit (NGIT) for Collaborative Response, which ensures high level of Protection and Augmented Operational Capacity to respond to the disaster scene.
 - The NGIT will be provided at the service of the FRs for extensive testing and validation (at component/system and Toolkit level) in the framework of a rich Training, Testing and Validation Programme.

RESCUER (July 2021 – June 2024)

- Project Title: First responder-centered support toolkit for operating in adverse and infrastructure-less environments
- Scope: Development of the First-Responder-centered technology toolkit (sense augmentation, precise and infrastructure-less self-positioning, cognitive support and multi-sense AR interfaces, and robust ad-hoc intra-team communications for both verbal and data exchanges)
- Objective: RESCUER aims to design and develop a first-responder-centered technology toolkit that will empower the next generation of first responders (FR) by enhancing their operational capacity and safety, specifically in adverse conditions, both environmental and infrastructure-wise
- Relevant information:
 - RESCUER will employ a rigorous process for validating its developed tools' effectiveness. The main goal will be to enforce a continuous and efficient

⁵⁹ https://respondroneproject.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/ResponDrone_D7.1_General_Architecture_Design.pdf

⁶⁰ https://respondroneproject.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/ResponDrone_D8.1_The_Regulatory_Landscape_Gaps_and_Challenges.pdf

⁶¹ https://respondroneproject.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/ResponDrone_D12.2_Legal_Ethics_Privacy_Security_Framework.pdf

bilateral communication between the technology developers and the end users FRs that will allow a systematic exchange of experiences between them.

CURSOR (September 2019 – August 2022)

- Project Title: Coordinated Use of miniaturized Robotic equipment and advanced Sensors for search and rescue Operations
- Scope: Development of 'CURSOR SaR Kit' using drones, miniaturised robotic equipment, and advanced sensors to increase first responders' ability
- Objective: CURSOR's primary objective is to develop 'CURSOR SaR Kit' using drones, miniaturised robotic equipment, and advanced sensors to increase the effectiveness of First Responder's work in search and rescue missions
- Relevant information;
 - WP1 will collect and characterise the needs of first responders during Search and Rescue missions and based on these outcomes establish the technical specification and architecture of the CURSOR SaR Kit
 - WP4 will develop a drone-based system, assisting in the accelerated and cost-efficient detection and rescue of victims. The developed drones will be tested as part of the field trials
 - WP6 will validate the CURSOR SaR Kit concept of operation (components and the whole system) in realistic search & rescue conditions.

MANIFESTS (January 2021 – December 2022)

- Project Title: Managing risks and Impacts from Evaporating and gaseous Substances to population Safety
- Scope: Development of an operational decision-support system (DSS) for volatile Hazard Noxious Substances (HNS) spills
- Objective;
 - The objective of MANIFESTS project is to address uncertainties and improve response and training capacities through the development of an operational decision-support system (DSS) for volatile HNS spills
 - The main objective is to facilitate access to relevant information and databases. It allows planners and responders to find the information they need through a dedicated open-source web platform
- Relevant information
 - MANIFESTS supports response teams by creating innovative tools such as modelling software validated through experimental tests at lab and field trials along with operational guidelines
 - Valkyries may refer to what kind of certification requirements are needed for new technologies in oil spill accident;
 - WP3 - evaluation of different monitoring technologies (sensors) and testing of their performance in open sea.

SIXTHSENSE (May 2020 – April 2023)

- Project Title: Smart integrated extreme environment health monitor with sensory feedback for enhanced situation awareness
- Scope: development of a wearable health monitoring system for first responders

- Objective: The project proposes an innovative wearable health monitoring system based on multimodal biosensor data that enables first responders to detect risk factors early on and allows real-time monitoring of all deployed responders
- Relevant information;
 - SIXTHSENSE will develop novel technologies for wearable systems. This technology will be developed and implemented into demonstrator systems that will be validated first in the laboratory, then in the first responder training facilities, and finally through in-situ experimental deployment.
 - Further accompanying measures define a clear understanding of constraints, limitations, requirements and specifications that stem from EU/national regulations and standards as well as the definition of key performance indicator (KPIs) for validations and testing procedures including development of risk definitions.
 - Validation is a sub-process of the certification process, so the validation procedures for the novel wearable system could be referred to the certification.

MED1stMR (June 2021 – May 2024)

- Project Title: Medical first responder training using a mixed reality approach featuring haptic feedback for enhanced realism
- Scope: Development of MR(Mixed reality) training to enhance the capabilities of the medical first responders
- Objective: development of innovative mixed reality training technology to combine real-world medical simulators with virtual environments to train medical first responders for their challenges
- Relevant information;
 - This project will develop a pioneering MR training approach for enhanced realism. This MR training environment allows trainees to immerse into virtual scenarios and to feel and perceive accrual movements through tactile and visual interaction as they are actuated. This MR training could be one of new capabilities that could/would be used in certification labs
 - MR training scenarios will be developed collaboratively with end users in the workshops. Theses developed MR training scenarios will be transferred into the training of medical teams, taking into account European legal, safety and ethical standards within the end user partners.
 - To enhance the effectiveness of MR training, wearable technologies with body sensors will be developed allowing to monitor stress level of MFR during training. Additionally, the influence of several contextual and personal factors on MFRs' perception and evaluation of the situation, decision-making and performance in highly demanding emergency situations will be researched.

CRISP (April 2014 – March 2017)

- Project Title: Evaluation and certification schemes for security products
- Scope: Security system
- Objective: Development of an innovative evaluation and certification methodology for security systems
- Relevant information:

- This project aims to facilitate a harmonised playing field for the European security industry by developing a robust and innovative evaluation and certification methodology for security systems. This products itself are not related to SAR equipment/system, but Valkyries can refer this evaluation and certification methodology.
- Following challenges of this project are relevant to SAR equipment
 - The European security market is highly fragmented, and no common framework applies to security products and systems. Specifically, certification of security products and systems is the lack of common certification systems for security products as well as a lack of mechanism for mutual recognition across countries of products certified ant a national level.
 - There is no effective policy to regulate liability by setting quality standards and defining which services and products fall under certain criteria.
 - An appropriate organisational structure for standardisation and certification of security products and services is missing resulting in a plethora of standards and certification schemes.
 - There is a lack of transparency in respect of security products and their implementation
 - A lack of effective participation from stakeholders in setting security standards and certification. Market success relies strongly on acceptance by the public and policy makers. For this, fostering and promoting stakeholder involvement at all levels of the standards and certification process is needed.
- Harmonisation of security certification in Europe is a complex task, so this project focuses on that how flexibility must be inherent in the CRISP scheme, to account for different technologies, means of operation, national cultures, as well as legal and regulatory frameworks in each member state. At this point, we can assess that general certification scheme for SAR equipment can be practicable or not.

HECTOS (September 2014 – January 2018)

- Project Title: Harmonized evaluation, certification and testing of security products
- Scope: Security products
- Objective: Development of harmonised certification schemes for physical security products
- Relevant information:
 - HECTOS project is related to above CRISP project⁶²
 - They mentioned specialty about security products. Security products differ from other types of product. Based on the features of the security products, they suggested several tests.
 - What is the feature of SAR equipment? Is there any special test for SAR equipment?

⁶² CRISP focuses on the security systems, and has holistic approach, and HECTOS focuses on the security products, and has technical approach

- SAR equipment may run into unexpected situation (like high/low temperature, strong wind, etc.), so it should be reliable in abnormal operating condition. Then it could be required intensive durability test against harsh condition.
- SAR equipment is life-related product, so the safety margin needs to be larger than other product and reliability also must be assured.
- When the information is gathered by unmanned vehicles and processed on the network, cyber security is important for the accurate information and privacy.

CertMILS (January 2017 – June 2021)

- Project Title: Compositional security certification for medium-to high-assurance COTS-based systems in environments with emerging threats
- Scope: This project developed a security certification methodology for Cyber-physical systems (CPS). Cyber-physical systems (CPS) is a computer system in which a mechanism is controlled or monitored by computer-based algorithms (e.g. autonomous automobile systems, medical monitoring, robotics systems, automatic pilot avionics, etc.).
- Objective: It aimed to increase the economic efficiency and European competitiveness of CPS development, while demonstrating the effectiveness of safety and security certification of composable systems.
- Relevant Information:
 - Cyber-physical systems are characterised by safety-critical nature, complexity, connectivity, and open technology. These characteristics are relevant to SAR equipment and system as well.
 - certMILS reduces certification complexity. This was achieved by applying a methodology to examine the security architecture of CPS, based on the principle of multiple independent levels of safety/security MILS (Multiple Independent Levels of Security).

SCOTT (May 2017 – October 2020)

- Project Title: Secure connected trustable things
- Scope: The SCOTT project focuses on wireless sensor & actuator networks and communication in mobility, smart infrastructure and health
- Objective: SCOTT will provide efficient solutions of wireless, end-to-end secure, trustworthy connectivity and interoperability to bridge the last mile to the market (TRL 6-7)
- Relevant Information:

“D31.4 Final Report on Standardization/Regulation/Certification Activities”

 - In here, they review and update the standardization activities and the standards used across the use cases (e.g. wireless standards, higher layer protocol standards, device layer standards, network and service layer standards, IoT and Cloud standards, security, privacy, trustiness and safety standards, etc.)
 - They identify new standardization activities as well as the regulation and certification bodies concerning these new activities.

SECRETAS (May 2018 – October 2021)

- Project Title: Cyber security for cross domain reliable dependable automated systems

- Scope: Sectors of automotive, health and rail for which the automation is major challenge regarding the safety of operation, the security of persons and the privacy of citizens
- Objective: SECREDAS aims to develop and validate multi-domain architecting methodologies, reference architectures & components for autonomous systems, combining high security and privacy protection while preserving functional safety and operational performance
- Relevant Information:
“D10.7 Guidelines for multi-concern analysis, assessment and qualification/certification”
 - This deliverable provides hands-on guidelines for continuous multi-concern qualification/certification with an initial focus on safety and security concerns for the automotive domain.
 - This deliverable presents;
 - The standardization landscape relevant for automotive domain
 - General safety and security standards
 - The guideline for the automotive domain is a template also for the railway- and health domains

EMPHASIS (February 2018 – January 2020)

- Project Title: Empowering heterogeneous aviation through cellular signals
- Scope: General Aviation/Rotorcrafts (GA/R) operations both with commercial aviation and with emerging drones operations
- Objective: The key objective of the project EMPHASIS is to increase safety, reliability and interoperability of General Aviation/Rotorcrafts (GA/R) operations both with commercial aviation and with emerging drones operations
- Relevant Information:
“D3.1 Concept for alternative certification”
 - It describes the current state of art of certification process in Europe
 - Ongoing and past activity aiming for improving, simplification and cost reduction of certification process in aviation are summarised.
 - A new potential approach to system certification suitable for connected environment is proposed and discussed

EU-SEC (January 2017 – December 2019)

- Project Title: The European security certification framework
- Scope: Cloud infrastructure
- Objective: The project aims to create a European framework for certification schemes and evaluation concepts to secure cloud infrastructures.
- This project supports the strategy of the European Union implementing the Digital Single Market Strategy, the European Cloud Initiative, the upcoming NIS Directive as well as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
- Relevant Information:
 - Many different certificates and labels are used by cloud service providers. Thus, for the Cloud user companies, it is challenging to figure out, which services and providers can be trusted in terms of security, privacy, compliance and transparency. The EU-SEC framework defined principles, rules and processes for

mutual recognition between the different certifications schemes and will provide guidance tested and validated in pilots involving industrial partners.

FAVIT (October 2019 – March 2022)

- Project Title: Feasibility analysis of innovative practices in virtual testing methods for aircraft certification
- Objective: Main objective is to deliver a set of knowledge-based proposals for the improvement of aerospace standards and guidelines for the system suppliers and aircraft manufacturers.

FAVIT analyses the current aerospace standards and guidelines to identify how the design and verification processes can be enhanced to accelerate the processes using the state-of-the-art technologies based in virtual testing.

- Relevant Information:
 - “D1.2 A Gap analysis”
 - Virtual Testing Technologies (VTTs) can provide a cheaper and more accessible testing environment that can be used throughout the software development process to perform the bulk of functional testing, error finding and debugging.
 - This deliverable presents why, according to the current standards, VTTs are not being used to fully certify such software; and how those standards might also be enhanced to more readily facilitate the use of VTTs in the certification of an airborne software system.
 - In terms of accuracy, concept of virtual certification is applicable to SAR equipment and system or not.

The landscape of research projects and initiatives in the field of crisis management, first responder technology, and certification schemes is extensive and diverse. These projects are collectively working towards enhancing the capabilities and safety of FRs, ensuring the reliability of their equipment, and improving the overall response to crises and disasters.

From projects like DRIVER+ and STRATEGY, which focus on crisis management capability development and interoperability testing, to initiatives like RESPONDRONE and MED1stMR, which aim to revolutionize the use of drones and mixed reality training for first responders, it is evident that innovation is at the forefront of these efforts.

Moreover, projects like CURSOR and MANIFESTS emphasize the importance of rigorous testing and certification, especially when it comes to search and rescue equipment, ensuring that they can withstand harsh conditions and operate reliably during emergencies.

The focus on cybersecurity, as seen in project like SECREDAS and EU-SEC, underlines the growing importance of protecting critical systems and data in emergency response operations.

Ultimately, the collaboration among these projects, in conjunction with their dedication to conforming to evolving standards and certification procedures, will endure as a fundamental factor in shaping the future of crisis management and the technology employed by FRs.

5.3. Certification for technologies and equipment in emergency response

5.3.1. Existing certification scheme and Initiatives

5.3.1.1. Product Certification Scheme

International level

While the IEC (International Electrotechnical Commission)⁶³ does not perform testing and certification activities itself, the IEC provides four conformity assessment systems;

- IECEE
IECEE is the Conformity Assessment Schemes for Electrotechnical equipment and components
- IECRE
IECRE is for use in renewable energy applications
- IECEx
IECEx is for use in explosive atmospheres
- IECQ
IECQ is for electronic components

These IEC Conformity Assessment Systems support all types of conformity assessment and allows for testing to be transparent, predictable, and affordable.

IECEE (IEC system of conformity assessment schemes for electrotechnical equipment and components)

- IECEE is a multilateral certification system based on IEC International Standards.
- IECEE makes international trade in electrotechnical equipment and components easier and less costly by reducing technical barriers to trade.
- A typical example of a technical barrier is the differing certification requirements across various countries.
- Using IEC International Standards for certification at the national level ensures that a certified product has been manufactured and type-tested to well-established international standards.
- The IECEE CB scheme⁶⁴ is applicable to electrotechnical equipment and components primarily intended for use in homes, offices, workshops, healthcare facilities and similar locations.
- The success of the IECEE CB scheme is due to its popularity in the various worldwide marketplaces where CB test certificates and test reports are considered as proof of compliance with the safety requirements according to the IEC International Standards.
- Advantages:
 - The true “passport” for getting market access to different countries
 - It answers the market needs for international product certification
 - It proves that certification and testing costs can be reduced

⁶³ The IEC (International Electrotechnical Commission) is a global, not-for-profit membership organization. The IEC provides a global, neutral and independent standardization platform. <https://iec.ch/conformity-assessment/ca-systems>

⁶⁴ <https://www.iecee.org/about/cb-scheme/>

- The IECEE CB scheme is an international system for mutual acceptance of test reports and certificates dealing with the safety of electrical and electronic components, equipment and products

European level

Equipment and goods within the EU Market are affected by the EU legislative framework. They have to meet all the applicable requirements (legislative including testing, inspection and certification) of the conformity assessment before the equipment can be sold in Europe. The procedure for each product varies according the nature of the good. The assessment is carried out by the manufacturer, but for some product, the legislation may require an independent CAB (laboratory, inspection or certification body) involved in the process.

This conformity assessment will proportionate a Declaration of Conformity that will identify⁶⁵:

- the product
- the legislation according to which it is issued
- the manufacturer or the authorised representative
- the notified body if applicable
- a reference to harmonised standards or other normative documents, where appropriate

The following table shows the list of notifying authorities that supervises the CABs related to EU regulations that may apply to emergency response equipment.

Country	legislation 210/53/EU Radio equipment	Regulation 2014/30/EU Electromagnetic compatibility	Regulation (EU) 2019/945 on unmanned aircraft systems and on third-country operators of unmanned aircraft systems
Austria	Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Regions and Tourism - Directorate-General IV - Telecommunications, Postal Services and Mining	Bundesministerium für Digitalisierung und Wirtschaftsstandort - Abteilung IV/A/3	Austro Control Österreichische Gesellschaft für Zivilluftfahrt mit beschränkter Haftung
Belgium	BIPT (Belgian Institute for Postal services and Telecommunication)	SPF Economie, PME, Classes moyennes et Energie	-
Bulgaria	State Agency for Metrological and Technical Surveillance	State Agency for Metrological and Technical Surveillance	-
Croatia	Ministry of the Sea, Transport and Infrastructure	Ministry of the Sea, Transport and Infrastructure	-

⁶⁵ https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/goods/building-blocks/conformity-assessment_en

Country	legislation 210/53/EU Radio equipment	Regulation 2014/30/EU Electromagnetic compatibility	Regulation (EU) 2019/945 on unmanned aircraft systems and on third-country operators of unmanned aircraft systems
Czech Republic	Czech Office for Standards, Metrology and Testing	Czech Office for Standards, Metrology and Testing	-
Denmark	Energistyrelsen / The Danish Energy Agency	Energistyrelsen / The Danish Energy Agency	-
Estonia	Consumer Protection and Technical Regulatory Authority	Consumer Protection and Technical Regulatory Authority	-
European Union	European Commission	European Commission	European Commission
Finland	Finnish Transport and Communications Agency	Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment of Finland	-
France	Ministère de l'économie, de l'industrie et du numérique – DGE – Bureau de la réglementation des communications électroniques	Ministère de l'économie et des finances – DGE – Pôle de la normalisation et de la réglementation des produits	Direction générale de l'Aviation civile / Direction de la Sécurité de l'Aviation civile
Germany	Bundesnetzagentur für Elektrizität, Gas, Telekommunikation Post und Eisenbahnen	Bundesnetzagentur für Elektrizität, Gas, Telekommunikation Post und Eisenbahnen	Luftfahrt-Bundesamt (Federal Aviation Office)
Greece	Ministry of Development and Investments, General Secretariat for Industry - Quality Policy Directorate	Ministry of Digital Policy, Telecommunications and Media - General Secretariat of Telecommunications and Post	Hellenic Civil Aviation Authority - Flight Standards Division - Private Aviation Section (D)
	Ministry of Digital Policy, Telecommunications and Media - General Secretariat of Telecommunications and Post		-
Hungary	National Media and Infocommunications Authority (NMHH)	Government Office of the Capital City Budapest	Ministry for Innovation and Technology, Aviation Supervisory Department

Country	legislation 210/53/EU Radio equipment	Regulation 2014/30/EU Electromagnetic compatibility	Regulation (EU) 2019/945 on unmanned aircraft systems and on third-country operators of unmanned aircraft systems
Ireland	Commission for Communications Regulation	Commission for Communications Regulation	Aviation Safety and Security Division
Italy	Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico - Direzione Generale per il Mercato, la Concorrenza, il Consumatore, la Vigilanza e la Normativa Tecnica	Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico - Direzione Generale per il Mercato, la Concorrenza, il Consumatore, la Vigilanza e la Normativa Tecnica	ENAC Italian Civil Aviation Authority
Latvia	-	Ministry of Economics, Internal Market Department	Ministry of Economics, Internal Market Department
Liechtenstein	-		Amt für Volkswirtschaft
Lithuania	Ministry of the Economy and Innovation of the Republic of Lithuania, EU and International Affairs Department	Ministry of the Economy and Innovation of the Republic of Lithuania, EU and International Affairs Department	Ministry of the Economy and Innovation of the Republic of Lithuania, EU and International Affairs Department
Luxembourg	-	OLAS - Office Luxembourgeois d'Accréditation et de Surveillance	-
Malta	Technical Regulations Division, Malta Competition and Consumer Affairs Authority (MCCAA)	Technical Regulations Division, Malta Competition and Consumer Affairs Authority (MCCAA)	-
Netherlands	Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy - Agentschap Telecom	Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy - Agentschap Telecom	-
Norway	Ministry of Local Government and Regional Development	Ministry of Local Government and Regional Development	-
	-	Norwegian Directorate for Civil Protection	-
Poland	Ministry of Digital Affairs	Ministry of Digital Affairs	-

Country	legislation 210/53/EU Radio equipment	Regulation 2014/30/EU Electromagnetic compatibility	Regulation (EU) 2019/945 on unmanned aircraft systems and on third-country operators of unmanned aircraft systems
	Ministry of Economic Development, Labor and Technology	Ministry of Economic Development, Labor and Technology	-
Portugal	-	Instituto Português da Qualidade (IPQ)	-
Romania	-		Ministry of Transports, Infrastructure and Communications
Slovakia	Slovak Office of Standards, Metrology and Testing	Slovak Office of Standards, Metrology and Testing	Slovak Office of Standards, Metrology and Testing
Slovenia	Ministry of the Economy	Ministry of the Economy	-
Spain	Secretaría de Estado de Telecomunicaciones e Infraestructuras Digitales (SETELECO)	Secretaría de Estado de Telecomunicaciones e Infraestructuras Digitales (SETELECO)	Agencia Estatal de Seguridad Aérea (AESA)
	-	Subdirección General de Calidad y Seguridad Industrial / Ministerio de Industria, Comercio y Turismo	-
Sweden	SWEDAC - Swedish Board for Accreditation and Conformity Assessment	SWEDAC - Swedish Board for Accreditation and Conformity Assessment	SWEDAC - Swedish Board for Accreditation and Conformity Assessment
Switzerland	State Secretariat for Economic Affairs (SECO) - Federal Department of Economic Affairs FDEA (MRA)	State Secretariat for Economic Affairs (SECO) - Federal Department of Economic Affairs FDEA (MRA)	-

Table 3 – Notifying authorities related to EU regulations applicable to emergency response equipment

5.3.1.2. Software certifications

The software certification stands for a guarantee that the software performs according to its specification. For instance, one of notified bodies, TÜV SÜD⁶⁶ issues software certification, and they tested the software quality⁶⁷ in the following categorized test⁶⁸;

1. Functionality test (based on the ISO/IEC 25051)
2. Usability test (based on the EN/ISO 9241)
3. Data security test (based on the GDPR)

In addition to the above, the test is also based on the documentation of the software design and development process (specification, test, and quality assurance), the product specifications and the user documentation.

Relevant standards

1. ISO/IEC 25000:2014 Systems and software engineering – Systems and software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) – Guide to SQuaRE
 - This standard provides guidance for the use of the new series of International Standards named Systems and software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE).
 - It creates a common framework to assess the quality of software products, focus on maintainability and functional suitability (functionality).
 - Certification of software product quality with ISO/IEC 25000 enables companies that develop software to find out about the quality of their products and allows companies that purchase software to choose a solution based on their requirements.
2. ISO/IEC 25051:2014 Software engineering – Systems and software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) – Requirements for quality of Ready to Use Software Product (RUSP) and instructions for testing
 - This standard establishes;
 - a. Quality requirements for Ready to Use Software Product (RUSP)
 - b. Requirements for test documentation for the testing of RUSP, including test plan, test description, and test results
 - c. Instructions for conformity evaluation of RUSP
3. ISO/IEC/IEEE 29119 series

The purpose of these standards is to define an internationally agreed set of standards for software testing that can be used by any organization when performing any form of software testing.

In addition, it's important to recognize that these principles extend to emerging technologies such as AI and IoT.

⁶⁶ TÜV companies (TÜV Nord, TÜV Rheinland and TÜV SÜD) are internationally active, independent service companies that test, inspect and certify technical systems and facilities.

⁶⁷ The software quality is defined as capability of software product to satisfy stated and implied needs when used under specified conditions in ISO/IEC 25000:2014

⁶⁸ <https://www.tuvsud.com/en-gb/services/testing/software-quality-testing>

AI standards

1. ISO/IEC 23894:2023⁶⁹ Information technology – Artificial intelligence – Guidance on risk management
 - This standard offers guidance to organizations that develop, produce, deploy or use AI products, systems, and services to manage risk specifically related to AI
 - This can be helpful in ensuring that AI is developed and used in a responsible and ethical manner
 - It does not have a certification scheme on its own, but it could be possible that use this standard as a reference for the certification
2. ISO/IEC TR 24028:2020⁷⁰ Information technology – Artificial intelligence – Overview of trustworthiness in artificial intelligence
 - This technical report surveys topics related to trustworthiness in AI systems
 - It could be useful for organizations looking to implement trustworthy AI systems and may include technical requirements for certification

While ISO/IEC 23894 guides stakeholders in mitigating risks and upholding responsible AI practices, ISO/IEC TR 24028 offers a comprehensive view of trustworthiness, potentially laying the groundwork for certification processes. As the scope of AI's influence continues to broaden, following these standards is crucial to ensure that AI technologies are both state-of-the-art and uphold ethical, reliable, and safe qualities.

IoT standards

1. ISO/IEC 30162:2022⁷¹ Internet of Things (IoT) – Compatibility requirements and model for devices within industrial IoT systems
 - This standard provides a framework for the governance of AI systems, including principles, requirements, and guidelines for the responsible use of AI
2. ISO/IEC 21823-1:2019⁷² Internet of things (IoT) – Interoperability for IoT systems – Part 1: Framework

This standard offers essential guidance for designing, implementing, and managing IoT solutions to ensure seamless communication and interaction between diverse IoT devices and components.
3. ISO/IEC 30161-1:2020⁷³ Internet of Things (IoT) – Requirements of IoT data exchange platform for various IoT services – Part 1: General requirements and architecture

This standard specifies requirements for an IoT data exchange platform for various services in the technology areas.

These standards provide a structured framework for evaluating and certifying software and technology products, ensuring they meet specific quality and performance criteria. As technology continues to advance and expand its influence on various industries, adherence to these standards becomes instrumental in not only delivering state-of-the-art solutions but also upholding ethical and responsible development practices.

⁶⁹ <https://www.iso.org/standard/77304.html>

⁷⁰ <https://www.iso.org/standard/77608.html>

⁷¹ <https://www.iso.org/standard/53282.html>

⁷² <https://www.iso.org/standard/71885.html>

⁷³ <https://www.iso.org/standard/53281.html>

5.3.1.3. Cybersecurity certification

During the past years, national initiatives have emerged to establish a high-level requirements for the cybersecurity of ICT products /services. Certification has a key role in increasing the level of trust and security in ICT products/ services.

Certification in this field follows specific national certification schemes depending on the origin of the service product.

International level

The international agreement Common Criteria Recognition Arrangement (CCRA) is the first agreement on the international recognition of certificates issued on conformity assessment with the common criteria among the participants of the agreement.

Under CCRA, an IT product/system can be certified regarding the level of cybersecurity it meets.

A total of 2066 certificates have been reported on the portal by European laboratories.

European level

At European level, there is an additional agreement in the field of security of information systems, the SOG-IS⁷⁴. This agreement focuses on European Certification Bodies and protection profiles.

Since 2019, with the Regulation (EU) 2019/881 (Cybersecurity Act⁷⁵), the EU is working on introduces an EU-wide cybersecurity certification framework for ICT products, services and processes: the EUCC scheme. This EUCC scheme may serve as a successor to the EU national schemes operating under the SOG-IS MRA.

The European Union Agency for Cybersecurity, ENISA, is the Union's agency dedicated to achieving a high common level of cybersecurity across Europe.

The EU certification schemes related to Cybersecurity are:

- Implementing:
 - EUCC (Common Criteria based European candidate cybersecurity certification scheme): covers ICT (Information Communications Technology) products and it has been published in May 2021. It is based on the existing international scheme Common Criteria and corresponding standards, respectively, ISO/IEC 15408 and ISO/IEC 18045. For the legal implementation, the EC will adopt an implementing act presumably in 2022.
- Under development:
 - EUCS (European Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Services): looks into the certification of the cybersecurity of cloud services. Final Draft Candidate for European Cybersecurity Certification Group (ECCG)⁷⁶ revision. Expected to be finalized early 2022. It will be the successor to the existing national schemes.
 - EU5G (EU 5G): covers cybersecurity in 5G networks.
- Planned:

⁷⁴ <https://www.sogis.eu/>

⁷⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2019/881/oj>

⁷⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/cybersecurity-certification-group>

- Internet of Things (IoT). The committee proposes to define a scheme with different levels of assessment that takes into account the different criticality environments (e.g. health, connected car, toys, etc...). ETSI and JTC13 have been working on the development of standards for evaluating IoT products that can be the basis of the future scheme.
- Industrial components (IACS). The term IACS refers to all components (programmable logic controller, supervisory control and data acquisition system, etc.) that are integrated into critical infrastructures and industrial production facilities. This scheme will potentially build on previous work already developed ERNCIP (European Reference Network for Critical Infrastructure Protection) and could be part of the update of the NIS 2 directive.

Looking to the future, the Commission envisages the creation of certification schemes for artificial intelligence, cryptography or secure development lifecycles.

The Commission is also considering the unification of the different lightweight methodologies created in Europe into a single scheme using the FITCEM (Fixed Time Common Evaluation Methodology) evaluation methodology.

Once the Cybersecurity certification scheme is ready, a draft scheme has to become a piece of EU legislation called “[Implementing Act](#)” to be effective. This Act has to be endorsed by all Member States. Once this Act is adopted, Member States have time to prepare the operation of the scheme before issuing certificates.

EU cybersecurity certification schemes provide for a transition period after which equivalent national schemes will cease to be valid.

Figure 14 shows the process and actors to issue a cybersecurity certification scheme.

Figure 14 – Cybersecurity certification scheme (ENISA, 2021)⁷⁷

⁷⁷ https://www.enisa.europa.eu/topics/standards/certification/certification_graph_08.jpg

An EU cybersecurity *certificate* attests that an ICT product, process or service has been certified in accordance with such a scheme and that it complies with the specified cybersecurity requirements and rules. Certification is performed by a Conformity Assessment Body (CAB), which can audit and/or test and/or certify. All certificates will be published by ENISA on a dedicated website.

For cybersecurity certifications, it appears a new member in the certification process, the National Cybersecurity Certification Authorities (“NCCAs”), which supervise and monitor the compliance with the scheme of the certificates issued by the CABs in its Member State.

The following image shows the certification diagram with involved actors.

CABs can operate in 2 different ways: as evaluators (by auditing/testing) and/or as certifiers.

Requirements before becoming eligible CAB:

- CABs have to be accredited by their NAC.
- Once accredited, the NCCA has to notify it to the EC.
- In case of operate in assurance level “high”, the NCCA requires “authorisation”, which is a process to meet some additional requirements. This “authorisation” will be notified as well to the EC.

Figure 15 – Cybersecurity certification diagram with involved actors

Depending on the cybersecurity risk associated with the intended use of the ICT solution to be certified, a different cybersecurity level can be chosen. Each EU scheme indicates if the certification is possible for an assurance level ‘basic’, ‘substantial’ or ‘high’ (Table 4).

Level	What is tested	Objective	Minimum assessment
HIGH	Compliance and robustness	Preserving sovereignty, protecting the citizen and industry from criminal organizations	Penetration testing State-of-the-Art attacks
SUBSTANTIAL	Compliance and robustness	Prevent scalable attacks on medium/high cost devices	Absence of public vulnerabilities Compliance testing
BASIC	Compliance	Prevent massive attacks on low-cost devices	Technical documentation review Self-assessment

Table 4 - Cybersecurity levels for certification

Certification is voluntary, unless otherwise specified by EU or Member State regulations.

Recommendations for the implementation of the Cloud Service Provider (CSP) Certification scheme

The outcome of the work performed by the Cloud Service Provider Certification Working group proposes the following recommendation for the governance structure of the certification process according to the assessment level required:

- Between the National Cybersecurity Certification Authority (NCCA), ENISA and various bodies at European level;
- Between the NCCA and different national stakeholders, at national level.

High Level

High-level outline of stakeholders involved in the certification process of products, processes and cloud services, at national level, is shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16 – High Level CSP certification diagram (from CSPCERT Project⁷⁸)

⁷⁸ [PT-2019-CSP-CERT-WG-Recommendations-for-the-implementation-of-the-CSP-Certification-scheme-20190607-Final-version.pdf \(ecp.nl\)](https://ecp.nl/PT-2019-CSP-CERT-WG-Recommendations-for-the-implementation-of-the-CSP-Certification-scheme-20190607-Final-version.pdf)

Four entities are involved at this level:

- The NCCA, which executes, at national level, the decision of the Management Committee regarding the CSP service certification and manages the scheme at national level;
- The National Accreditation Body (NAB), who is in charge of accrediting the conformity assessment bodies and the NCCAs, in order to be able to issue certificates;
- One or many Conformity Assessment Bodies, who are in charge of performing the evaluations under the supervision of the NCCAs.
- Cloud Service Providers, applying to the certification process for one or many of their services.

Substantial Level

For Substantial, not only NCCAs issue certificates but also CABs. To ensure consistency between certificates, the established rules in ISO/IEC 170xx and the governance of the scheme should be at EU level and not at national level.

Figure 17 – Substantial Level CSP certification diagram (from CSPCERT Project)

Specific to Substantial is the ability of a NCCA to choose to approve a CAB to conduct an evaluation, which could include audit firms. Where that occurrence happens, the CAB conducts the evaluation, issues the certificate, and becomes responsible for the supervision and monitoring of the certificate. There are also instances, where the same body may elect to conduct those evaluations themselves and, thereby inherit the supervision and monitoring efforts.

Basic Level

For the assurance, level ‘basic’:

Figure 18 – Basic Level CSP certification diagram (from CSPCERT Project)

National level

Some EU schemes participating to the SOG-IS MRA cover the same type or categories of ICT products, but may go beyond the EUCC in terms of national certification, or cover partly the EUCC assurance levels.

Following Common Criteria based certification schemes cover the same type or category of ICT products, security requirements, evaluation criteria and methods, and assurance levels:

Within the EU, the:

- French scheme, operated by ANSSI: <https://www.ssi.gouv.fr/administration/produits-certifies/cc/>
- German scheme, operated by BSI: https://www.bsi.bund.de/DE/Themen/ZertifizierungundAnerkennung/Produktzertifizierung/ZertifizierungnachCC/zertifizierungnachcc_node.html
- Italian scheme, operated by OCSI: www.ocsi.isticom.it/
- Dutch scheme, operated by TÜV Rheinland NL and NLNCSA: http://www.tuvnederland.nl/nl/17/common_criteria.html
- Spanish scheme, operated by CCN: <https://oc.ccn.cni.es/>
- Swedish scheme, operated by FMV: <http://fmv.se/en/Our-activities/CSEC---The-Swedish-Certification-Bodyfor-IT-Security/>

European Economic Area (EEA) European Free Trade Association (EFTA) States, the:

- Norwegian scheme, operated by SERTIT: <http://www.sertit.no/>

Some of these schemes may not currently cover all Technical Domains defined under Chapter 4, ASSURANCE LEVELS. This information may be retrieved from the SOG-IS MRA following page: https://www.sogis.eu/uk/status_participant_en.html

5.3.1.4. Data Spaces certification

The amount of digital data generated by public agencies, companies and citizens increases daily. The use of this data could be reused to improve and support other companies, products and services. To make it possible, it is necessary a common approach to work with them.

The EC has established The European Data Strategy, a strategic way to share data within the EU and across sectors. It is based in four fundamentals:

- Governance framework for access and use

- Investments in Europe's data capabilities and infrastructures
- Competences and skills of individuals and SMEs
- Common European data spaces in nine strategic areas

Figure 19 - Common European data spaces⁷⁹

As part of this strategy, the EC proposed in November 2020 a Regulation on European Data Governance⁸⁰ that creates the processes and structure to facilitate data, and On 23 February 2022 proposed the Data Act⁸¹, a regulation on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data, clarifying who can create value from data and under which conditions.

The International Data Spaces (IDS) initiative aims at cross-sectoral data sovereignty and data interoperability. It sets forth a Reference Architecture Model basing on open standards and contributing to global standards.

The initiative was founded as a non-profit organization, the IDS Association (IDSA). IDSA has more than 110 members from more than 20 different countries. IDSA is also an integral part of GAIA-X which is aiming at a Federated Data Infrastructure for European ecosystems.⁸²

IDS in Europe can provide with:

- Contributing knowledge and technology to high-impact projects
- Providing data-infrastructure services to nine European data spaces
- Providing advice, knowledge and expertise to the European Data Act
- Establishing a network of hubs across Europe and beyond

Actually the EU is funding several research projects to bring fundamental IDS concepts to life.

To allow the data Exchange through federated international data spaces, it is required a common standard. IDSA has created a standard to enable data sharing through federated

⁷⁹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/building-data-economy-brochure>

⁸⁰ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/proposal-regulation-european-data-governance-data-governance-act>

⁸¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-act>

⁸² [Implementing the European Strategy on Data. The Role of the International Data Spaces](#)

international data spaces characterized by uniform rules, certified data providers and recipients and trust among partners.

Any organization or individual seeking permission to operate components in the International Data Spaces needs to pass the Operational Environment Certification which ensures secure processes and management of components.

IDS Certification is compatible with commonly used security standards like ISO 27001 and IEC 62443, to reuse existing documentation and setups and minimize the effort significantly.⁸³

The certification consists of two parts:

- Core component certification: to guarantee the required functionality, security and interoperability.
- Operational environment certification: to guarantee the trustworthiness of the physical environment, defined processes and organizational rules.

The certification follows the same process for all certification profiles in operational environment and component certification.

Figure 20 – IDS certification process

The certification process consists of the following three phases:

1. APPLICATION: Start the process

⁸³ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/use/certification/>

2. EVALUATION: evaluation of an applicant or core component according the criteria. According the assurance levels there is some differences:
 - a. Assurance/Trust level 1: the applicant is responsible for the evaluation phase by conducting a self-assessment and providing the results to the certification body.
 - b. Assurance/Trust levels 2 and 3: require an independent evaluation facility to conduct the evaluation of the component or operational environment, and it provides the results to the certification body.
3. CERTIFICATION: the Certification Body examine the results and issues a certificate if positive.

The following figure shows all possible combinations of assurance and trust level that an applicant can select.

		Evaluation effort and assurance		
		Assurance Level 1 "Checklist self-assessment and automated interoperability testing"	Assurance Level 2 "External concept review including functional and security testing"	Assurance Level 3 "External evaluation including concept review, testing and source code audit"
Requirements to be fulfilled	Trust Level 1 "Data space interoperability"	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	Trust Level 2: "Feature complete for data usage control"		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Trust Level 3: "Additional protection from internal attacks"		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Figure 21 – Trust and assurance levels⁸⁴

5.3.2. Certification scheme for SAR equipment

5.3.2.1. Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (Drone)

UAS – Unmanned Aircraft Systems

The European Union has adopted a framework for regulation of UAS (Regulation EU 2019/945) and the operation of UAS (Regulation EU 2019/947) which defines three categories of UAS; open, specific and certified. For simple drones operated in the open category where the risk is very small the CE mark is sufficient. According to article 40 (EU 2019/945) UAS operated under the certified and specific categories shall comply with the applicable requirements set out in *Commission Regulation (EU) No 748/2012*, *Commission Regulation (EU) 2015/640* and *Commission Regulation (EU) No 1321/2014*. It is only applicable to civil drones.

EU member states have assigned the responsibility to EASA⁸⁵ for certification of regulation for all drones.

Drones for police, fire fighters, search and rescue are excluded from the regulation, but each member state can decide to put this under the EU regulation as well.

Unmanned aircraft system (UAS) is divided by the EASA in three categories;

⁸⁴ <https://internationaldataspace.org/use/certification/>

⁸⁵ European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) <https://www.easa.europa.eu/>

1) Open category:

- Low risk operations
- No authorisation required, but must self-register and pilots must pass a test
- Divided into 3 subcategories based on weight:
 - A1: max 250g
 - A2: max 2.0Kg
 - A3: max 25 Kg
- See Figure 22 for details

2) Specific category:

- Medium risk operation that requires authorisation from the National Aviation Authority.
- Require proper risk assessment (SORA or similar)

3) Certified category:

- High risk operation that can include transport of humans in urban environments by heavy machines with high power. The pilot can be on-board or off-board.
- This requires authorisation from the National Aviation Authority

UAS		Operation		Drone operator/pilot		
Max weight	Subcategory	Operational restrictions	Drone operator registration	Remote pilot competence	Remote pilot minimum age	
< 250 g	A1 (can also fly in subcategory A3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — No flight expected over uninvolved people (if it happens, overflight should be minimised) — No flight over assemblies of people 	No, unless camera / sensor on board and the drone is not a toy	— No training required	No minimum age	
< 500 g			Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Read carefully the user manual — Complete the training and pass the exam defined by your national competent authority or have a 'Proof of completion for online training' for A1/A3 'open' subcategory 	16*	
< 2 kg	A2 (can also fly in subcategory A3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — No flying over uninvolved people — Keep a horizontal distance of 50 m from uninvolved people 	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Read carefully the user manual — Complete the training and pass the exam defined by your national competent authority or have a 'Remote pilot certificate of competency' for A2 'open' subcategory 	16*	
< 25 kg	A3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Do not fly near or over people — Fly at least 150 m away from residential, commercial or industrial areas 	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Read carefully the user manual — Complete the training and pass the exam defined by your national competent authority or have a 'Proof of completion for online training' for A1/A3 'open' subcategory 	16*	

Figure 22 – Requirement for the Open Category for UAS (www.easa.europa.eu)

EU 1139/2018 EASA “On common rules in the field of civil aviation and establishing a European Union Aviation Safety Agency”:

(10), Where Member States consider it preferable, in particular with a view to achieving safety, interoperability or efficiency gains, to apply, instead of their national law, this Regulation to aircraft carrying out military, customs, police, search and rescue, firefighting, border control and coastguard or similar activities and services undertaken in the public interest, they should be allowed to do so. Member States making use of this possibility should cooperate with the Agency, in particular by providing all the information necessary for confirming that the aircraft and activities concerned comply with the relevant provisions of this Regulation.

This Regulation shall not apply to:

(a), aircraft, and their engines, propellers, parts, non-installed equipment and equipment to control aircraft remotely, while carrying out military, customs, police, search and rescue, firefighting, border control, coastguard or similar activities or services under the control and responsibility of a Member State, undertaken in the public interest by or on behalf of a body vested with the powers of a public authority, and the personnel and organisations involved in the activities and services performed by those aircraft

Operation of drones

UAV is primarily regulated by the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) and individual member states. Each National Aviation Authorities (NAAs)⁸⁶ has their own "online pilot training and tests" program for the drone pilot.

Common EU registration database for operators. The operator registration number should be uploaded into the drone. The unique serial number from the manufacturer is also required to be transmitted (especially important for specific and certified category).

The following requirements are relevant for the assumption that the SAR/ER drones fall under the “Open A3” category and that the state authority has decided that the common EU rules will apply also for fire-fighting, police, coastguard and search and rescue:

- The organisation must be registered with local aviation authorities
- The organisation must comply with a set of roles:
 - Responsible leader, operational leader, technical leader, Pilot-in-command and pilot.
- Pilots must undergo training and pass online test.
- There must be an Operational Manual that identifies the above roles, and contains a given set of subsections or appendices.
 - Concept of operation that describes all operations the organisation will perform. Limits of operations, e.g. not flying in darkness, no-fly-zones (embassies, prisons etc), necessary permissions (e.g. from land-owner).
 - The document will outline how and where to dump/crash drone in case of emergency.
 - In Norway, other cameras than RGB-visual requires explicit permission from the National Safety Authority (NSM).

⁸⁶ <https://www.easa.europa.eu/en/domains/civil-drones/naa>

- Quality assurance system with proper routines for training pilots, maintaining documentation and documents, dealing with deviations, storing flight logs and other information relevant for improving operation quality, continuous learning from operations and improving operations
- Risk assessment to identify potential hazards that may occur during an operation.
- How to ensure proper training - how to reserve airspace, coordination of pilots and other personnel, airmanship, limitations of the drone.
- Checklist before during and after flight, and for emergencies
- Proof of insurance
- Packing list
- Flight logs, battery status, duration
- It is a legal requirement that the organisation has insurance, covering damage to 3rd party people and property.
- ISO 23665:2021 Unmanned aircraft systems-Training for personnel involved in UAS operations
 - This document describes the procedures for training personnel who will be involved in the operation of unmanned aircraft systems
 - This document defines:
 - Knowledge, skill, attitude and qualification criteria that are needed for UAS pilots and training organizations that provides training to trainees of UAS remote pilots and other personnel involved in UAS operations
 - Training curriculum and contents for specific learning courses
 - Qualification and confirmation criteria for the training organizations
 - General procedures for providing training of UAS personnel. The requirements for a specific course as described in the annexes can be more restrictive in some cases

International regulation

ICAO(International Civil Aviation Organization)⁸⁷ has developed “Model UAS Regulations and Advisory Circulars”⁸⁸ to provide a regulatory framework for unmanned aircraft systems(UAS) operations outside of the international flight rules(IFR) arena. These regulations and advisory circulars serve as a template for member states to implement or supplement their existing UAS regulations, aiming for internationally harmonized material based on industry developments.

ICAO encourages member states to share their UAS regulations with them to facilitate information exchange and harmonization. Advisory Circulars (ACs) are also provided to offer additional guidance on specific aspects of the Model UAS Regulations. These ACs include topics such as UAS operations in the Open Category, the Specific Category, the carriage of dangerous goods, and RPAS(Remotely Piloted Aircraft Systems) safety assurance.

Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UAS) for Humanitarian Aid and Emergency Response Guidance (U-AID)⁸⁹

⁸⁷ ICAO is a United Nations agency, established to help countries share their skies to their mutual benefit. <https://www.icao.int/Pages/default.aspx>

⁸⁸ <https://www.icao.int/safety/UA/Pages/ICAO-Model-UAS-Regulations.aspx>

⁸⁹ <https://www.icao.int/safety/UA/UAID/Pages/default.aspx>

- This guidance is intended to support member states in enabling UAS operations for humanitarian purposes and facilitating an expedited review process for urgent operations
- It emphasizes the importance of prior planning, coordination, and the involvement of approved or qualified operators to ensure safe, dependable, efficient, and effective delivery of aid

Operation example from Norway

Grenland Fire and rescue⁹⁰ has the responsibility for preparedness and response in case of fires and accidents in four municipalities in south-eastern Norway (Bamble, Drangedal, Kragerø and Porsgrunn). The organisation has 118 employees and 14 of them are certified pilots. The organisation has applied for and maintains the obligations to keep certification to fly in the most demanding category and are able to fly at night, close to buildings and close to people.

The organisation has standardised on DJI drones which are compatible with the National Rescue Centre video streaming system. The streaming system, Incident-share shown in Figure 23, also provide audio and video streaming capability directly from surveillance cameras and cell phones. The system can share audio and video with crew and staff and will comply with the [Directive \(EU\) 2019/882](#) on accessibility requirements for emergency communications.

Secure streaming

Typical usage scenario

Figure 23 - The drone streaming system from Incident-share (www.incendium.dk)

The use of DJI off-the-shelf commercial drones has clear cost advantages but can raise a security concern in case of terrorist related incidents. The DJI drones has a “no-fly-zone” map that is

⁹⁰ www.gbr.no

updated regularly, but there has been reported cases of this map being hacked with the result that the drones will not take off and will be useless. The security of the no-fly-zone map and the communication with the manufacturers' data servers will be up to the manufacturer and it could be a security risk.

Testing of drones

There are several standards for testing drones under development by ISO:

- ISO/DIS 4358 - Test methods for civil multi-copter unmanned aircraft system
- ISO/AWI TS 4584.2 - Improvement in the guideline for UA testing/design of accelerated lifecycle testing (ALT) for UAS/Sub-system/components
- ISO/AWI TR 4594 - UA wind gust test
- ISO/AWI TR 4595 - Suggestion for improvement in the guideline for UA testing classification
- ISO/CD 5110 - Test method for flight stability of multi-copter UA under wind and rain conditions
- ISO/CD 5286 - Test methods for flight performance of civil light weight and small fixed-wing UAS
- ISO/CD 5309 - Vibration test methods for lightweight and small civil UAS
- ISO/CD 5312 - Evaluation and test method of rotor blade sharp injury to human body for civil lightweight and small UA
- ISO/CD 5332 - Test methods for civil lightweight and small UAS under low pressure conditions

5.3.2.2. Unmanned Surface Vehicle (Sea drone)

On the EUR-Lex site⁹¹, there is no legal act related to the USV. The reason there is no legal act seems to be that the sea drones are not as commercialized as the UAV yet. The manufacturer can apply relevant existing laws as the alternative plan.

To find relevant laws for the sea drones, we can approach from two perspectives: 1) rescue craft and 2) autonomous/unmanned vessel

- 1) The point of view for the rescue craft
 - A Swedish company puts their rescue craft on the market under the *Directive 2013/53/EU Recreational craft and personal watercraft*.
 - For instance, one of the notified body, DNV offers certification service⁹² according to *Directive 2013/53/EU Recreational craft and personal watercraft*
 - a) They conduct the conformity assessment on engines, exhaust and sound emissions.
- 2) The point of view for the autonomous/unmanned vessel
 - The scale of USVs in this deliverable is much smaller than ordinary autonomous ship, but there may be some part that can be applied
 - Regulations for Autonomous/Unmanned vessel are under development, and there are a few guidelines so far. Nzengu et al. (2021) explored the existing

⁹¹ EUR-Lex is online gateway to EU Law. It provides the official and most comprehensive access to EU legal documents. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/homepage.html>

⁹² "Demonstrate that your product fulfils all the requirements for recreational craft to be sold within the European Economic Area" <https://www.dnv.com/services/recreational-craft-directive-rcd--2820>

maritime safety and security regulatory framework including the national and international regulations for designing, building, testing and operating the unmanned next-generation inland waterways vessel.

- “Guidance in connection with the construction or installation of automated functionality aimed at performing unmanned or partially unmanned operations” from Norwegian Maritime Authority. This guidance refers to the certification as follows;

4. Authority and certification

Temporary assessment and final approval of new technology and new solutions in accordance with this Circular will be provided by the Norwegian Maritime Authority.

Autonomous or remotely operated ships accepted by the Norwegian Maritime Authority (NMA) in accordance with this Circular may be provided with a certificate or an approval to operate on domestic voyages. This applies also when a vessel is constructed in accordance with the guidelines and rules of a classification society.

- DNV-CG-0264 Class Guideline: Autonomous and remotely operated ships⁹³

The objective of this document is to provide a framework which ensures that application of autonomous concepts and technologies result in a safety level equivalent to- or better than conventional vessel operations.

Relevant directives

- Directive 2013/53/EU Recreational craft and personal watercraft
- Directive 2006/42/EC on Machinery
- Regulation (EU) 2021/1158 Design, construction and performance requirements and testing standards for marine equipment

Relevant Standards

- ISO 15736:2006 Ships and marine technology – Pyrotechnic life-saving appliances – Testing, inspection and marking of production units
- ISO 6185 EU CE certification requirements on inflatable boats
- ISO 12217-2 Assessment requirements for stability and buoyancy of sail boats
- ISO 12217-1/ISO 12217-3 Assessment requirements for stability and buoyancy of non-sail boats
- ISO 21487 Inspection standards and requirements for permanently installed fuel tanks on yachts
- ISO 14509 Inspection standards and requirements for noise emission of yacht engine

⁹³ <https://rules.dnv.com/docs/pdf/DNV/CG/2021-09/DNV-CG-0264.pdf>

5.3.2.3. Unmanned Ground Vehicle (rover)

Like USVs, there is no legal act related to the unmanned ground vehicle (UGV) on the EUR-Lex site, although UGVs are used for a wide range of civilian applications such as search and rescue, firefighting, nuclear plant operation and military vehicle.

Relevant standards

ASTM Committee F45⁹⁴ has published UAV related standards as follow;

- ASTM F3200-18 Standard Terminology for Driverless Automatic Guided Industrial Vehicles
- ASTM F3218-17 Standard Practice for Recording Environmental Effects for Utilization with A-UGV Test Methods
- ASTM F3244-17 Standard Test Method for Navigation: Defined Area
- ASTM F3265-17 Test Method for Grid-Video Obstacle Measurement
- ASTM F3327-18 Standard Practice for Recording the A-UGV Configuration

Conformity assessment

- Testing for the rover
 - Test Operations Procedure (TOP) – Testing of Unmanned Ground Vehicle (UGV) System from the Defence Technical Information Center (DTIC)⁹⁵.
 - This TOP describes a systematic approach to safety and performance testing of UGVs. The objective is to ensure that the design of each UGV includes positive measures to enhance system safety, and that hazards which could reduce system safety are eliminated or controlled to an acceptable level of risk.

Rules for operation

- Certification or licence for operators
 - ASTM F 3193: 2016 - Standard Guide for Training of a Land Search and Rescue Team Leader

5.3.2.4. Communication equipment

Most of the communication equipment in SAR (e.g., tablet computers, smartphone, navigation devices, etc.) have already been certified. An additional task for the certification of the SAR communication equipment may be to evaluate whether the certification already received is sufficient or not. To evaluate this, we need to identify the process of the certification for the commercialized product first. Then, we could assess the necessity of additional test in the certification process based on the technical/functional requirement of the SAR equipment.

Take the apple iPhone as an example⁹⁶:

⁹⁴ ASTM International Committee F45 on Driverless Automatic Guided Industrial Vehicles was formed in 2014. This Committee addresses issues related to performance standards and guidance materials for 'automatic' through 'autonomous' unmanned ground vehicles with industrial applications. [Committee F45 on Robotics, Automation, and Autonomous Systems \(astm.org\)](https://www.astm.org/committees/f45)

⁹⁵ The Defense Technical Information Center (DTIC) is the repository for research and engineering information for the United States Department of Defense (DoD). <https://discover.dtic.mil/>

⁹⁶ <https://www.apple.com/euro/compliance/>

Declarations of Conformity for the Apple iPhone 13 in Europe

Directives:

- 2014/53/EU
- 2011/65/EU as amended by 2015/863/EU
- 2009/125/EC

Applied standards

- Safety and Health
 - EN 50360:2017
 - EN 50566:2017
 - EN 50663:2017
 - EN 50665:2017
 - IEC 62368-1: 2018 [2020+A11:2020]
- EMC
 - EN 55032:2012/AC:2013
 - EN 55024:2010
 - EN 55035:2017
 - EN 301 489-1 V2.2.3
 - EN 301 489-3 V2.1.2 [DRAFT]
 - EN 301 489-17 V3.2.4
 - EN 301 489-19 V2.2.0 [DRAFT]
 - EN 301 489-52 V1.1.2 [DRAFT]
 - EN 301 489-1 V2.2.0 [DRAFT]
 - EN 301 489-19 V2.1.1
 - EN 301 489-33 V2.2.1
- RF Spectrum efficiency
 - EN 300 328 V2.2.2
 - EN 301 893 V2.1.1
 - EN 300 440 V2.2.1
 - EN 300 330 V2.1.1
 - EN 302 065-1 V2.1.1
 - EN 301 908-1 V13.1.1
 - EN 301 908-2 V13.1.1
 - EN 301 908-13 V13.1.1
 - EN 301 908-25 V15.1.1_0.0.6(2021-03) DRAFT
 - EN 301 511 V12.5.1
 - EN 303 413 V1.1.1
 - EN 301 908-13 V13.1.1
- Additional Compliance
 - RoHS: EN IEC 63000:2018
 - Energy: Regulation 1275/2008

Then, we could check the necessity of additional standard/test based on the requirements for the SAR equipment/system.

Radio communications

Communication networks for emergency services usually uses radio spectrum. The most known technologies are those with wireless broadband cellular (e.g. based on the 4th or 5th generation technology standard) and Wi-Fi systems.

The EU has developed an EU-wide spectrum policy to coordinate the harmonisation and implementation for the single market of the use of radio spectrum.

EU Member States coordinate the use of this spectrum by implementing the Commission Decisions at national level. They also organise and manage the use of the spectrum at national level.

The essential requirements for radio equipment can be found in Radio Equipment Directive (RED), Directive 2014/53/EU. It regulates the requirements that products must meet to be placed on the market.

The most common way for manufacturers to comply with these requirements is to apply the voluntary Harmonised Standards developed by ETSI under the standardization request contained in the M/536 Commission Implementing Decision of the EC. The Directive is enforced at national level by Member States, in particular by Market Surveillance Authorities.⁹⁷

The following image shows the obligations and key responsibilities for placing equipment on the market under RED.

Figure 24 – Key responsibilities for placing equipment on the market under RED

Directives and regulations that applicable to radio equipment/services are:

- Radio Equipment
 - Radio Equipment Directive (2014/53/EU)
 - Radio Spectrum Decision (676/2002/EC)
- Electrical equipment
 - EMC Directive (2014/30/EU)
 - Low Voltage Directive (2014/35/EU)
- Networks and services
 - Framework Directive (2002/21/EC), amended in 2009
 - Authorisation Directive (2002/20/EC), amended in 2009
 - Access Directive (2002/19/EC), amended in 2009

⁹⁷ https://www.etsi.org/images/files/Brochures/ETSI_ECC%20Brochure_2017_Web.pdf

- Universal Service Directive (2002/22/EC), amended in 2009
- Privacy Directive (2002/58/EC), amended in 2009

As a particular case on radio communications, emergency communications in Europe usually uses Trans European Trunked Radio (TETRA) communications (of 380-400 MHz spectrum). TETRA is an Open standard developed by ETSI used in critical communications to operate in dangerous situations within challenging environments. TETRA provides good geographical radio coverage to provide high service availability. TETRAPOL is another solution that operates at the same spectrum with less base stations and different channel access method, but only 5 countries in Europe uses it, and in two of these they have both systems (Spain and France).

TETRA equipment and systems require an managed by The Critical Communication Association⁹⁸ (TCCA)'s Technical Forum. The Istituto Superiore delle Comunicazioni e tecnologie dell'Informazione (ISCOM), laboratory of the Italian Ministry of Communications, is the TETRA certification authority and supervises the testing sessions and issues the certificates.

Radio communication equipment requires a Declaration of Conformity issued by a CAB as it has been detailed in 5.3.1.1.

5.3.2.5. Tagging equipment

Most of tagging equipment are also commercialized. We can follow the same process as the communication equipment.

Take the apple Air Tag as an example⁹⁹:

Declarations of Conformity for the Apple Air Tag in Europe

Directives:

- 2014/53/EU
- 2011/65/EU as amended by 2015/863/EU

Applied standards

- Safety and Health
 - EN 62479:2010
 - IEC 62368-1: 2018 [2020+A11:2020]
- EMC
 - EN 301 489-1 V2.2.0 [DRAFT]
 - EN 301 489-17 V3.2.2 [DRAFT]
 - EN 301 489-3 V2.1.1
 - EN 301 489-33 V2.2.1
- RoHS: EN IEC 63000:2018
- EN 300 330 V2.1.1 Article 3.2: RF Spectrum Efficiency

Tagging equipment uses radio spectrum (under Directive 2014/53/EU). In this sense, the EC adopted an Implementing Decision to harmonise radio spectrum for short-range devices within the 874-876 and 915-921 MHz frequency bands. This decision provides appropriate spectrum

⁹⁸ <https://tcca.info/tetra/home/>

⁹⁹ <https://www.apple.com/euro/compliance/>

for applications based on short-range devices, including IoT and next-generation Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) equipment.

RFID devices are already in use in Europe in the 863-870 MHz band to mark objects with RFID tags. The directive proposed 900MHz range to allow enhanced technical limits. However, equally important, the 900 MHz range is used almost globally for RFID, which is beneficial especially in transport and logistics.¹⁰⁰

5.3.2.6. Wearable equipment

The wearable equipment is actively utilized in SAR. In FASTER project¹⁰¹, one of their objectives is to provide innovative, accepted and efficient tools to first responders. In this context, FASTER will design and develop a prototype regarding the use of electronic devices (i.e., sensors) in wearable textiles, equipped inside an underwear of the first responder's uniform, that will be able to collect biometric data (i.e., temperature, humidity).

The Moving Pictures Expert Group (MPEG)¹⁰² explores new standardisation needs for wearables, and they have developed a conceptual model for wearables (Figure 25). According to the MPEG definition, a wearable may contain several types of sensors that sense physiological phenomena from the user or from surrounding environment. The user can interact with the wearable by a set of commands and the processing unit. The wearable can also communicate an aggregated set of sensed information and receive data to/from the processing unit.

Figure 25 - Conceptual model for wearables ((Standardization & Organization, 2010))

¹⁰⁰ [The Commission harmonises radio spectrum in support of the Internet of Things | Shaping Europe's digital future \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/digital-storytelling/en/the-commission-harmonises-radio-spectrum-in-support-of-the-internet-of-things-shaping-europes-digital-future)

¹⁰¹ [H2020 FASTER 833507 | H2020 FASTER Project Website \(faster-project.eu\)](https://faster-project.eu/)

¹⁰² The Moving Picture Experts Group (MPEG) is a working group of ISO/IEC in charge of the development of international standards for compression, decompression, processing, and coded representation of moving pictures, audio and their combination. <https://mpeg.chiariglione.org/>

Based on this concept, the wearable equipment (e.g., bracelets, wristbands, wearable textiles, etc.) are in close contact with the user and treat private data. Therefore, the wearable devices need to go through testing and certification processes to prove compliance with requirements such as electrical safety, biocompatibility, radio frequency exposure, energy efficiency, and data security and privacy of applications. Moreover, IoT and wireless communication standards are necessary to enable interoperability between wearables and their environment since most wearables will have communication capabilities.

However, it is difficult to find corresponding regulation for the product because the wearable device is advanced technology. In most cases, the manufacturer could rely on conformity with health and safety requirements. Byrom et al. (2018) Wearable technology and sensors may be classified as medical devices. Then the applicable regulations are MDD 93/42/MDD and MDR2017/745/EU.

The requirements for the medical wearable device depend on the specificities of the product, its intended purpose, the technology used, the risks and benefits associated with its use, and the data it processes.

In 2014, TÜV Rheinland launched the world's first certification standard for wearable devices. To meet this certification standard, devices must fulfil three requirements: safety, wearable function, and smart function. These requirements are assessed through several tests.

The notified body, UL issues certification for the wearable with the following tests: electrical safety, battery safety, electrical and motor systems, SAR (specific absorption rate) testing, toxicology, cybersecurity, EMC (electromagnetic compatibility) test, Wireless device testing, interoperability, Smart clothing and footwear quality and performance testing and claims verification, etc.

As in the case of tagging equipment, wearable equipment can use radio spectrum, which is regulated under Directive 2014/53/EU. The almost global availability of the 900 MHz range is not only beneficial for RFID systems, but will also enable new innovative global applications based on networked short-range devices, such as active global asset tracking.

Relevant standards

The standardization of wearable technologies is still in its early phases. In 2021, IEC TC 124 issued three international standards and one technical report.

- IEC 63203-101-1:2021
It provides terminology used in literature related to wearable electronic devices and technologies in the IEC 63203 series.
- IEC 63203-201-3:2021
It specifies a test method for determination of the electrical resistance of conductive fabrics under simulated microclimate within clothing
- IEC 63203-204-1:2021
It specifies a household washing durability test method for leisurewear and sportswear e-textile systems. This document includes testing procedures for leisurewear and sportswear products with electrically conductive components and sensors to collect the data of the user.
- IEC TR 63203-250-1:2021

It reviews the use cases of conductive snap fasteners applied as electrical connectors for e-textile products available on the market and provides guidance on future standardization works

5.3.2.7. *Certification scheme for mechanical SAR equipment*

General SAR and emergency response equipment like hooks, ladders, ropes, motorised climbing equipment needs to follow the general EU process for either self-declaration or independent assessment by a notified body.

The manufacturer of SAR equipment must follow the standard process for certification shown in chapter 3.1, but it is not always clear which standard is the most suitable to show conformance to. The EU websites¹⁰³ can help to identify requirements for different product groups.

For instance, products containing electronics must be compliant with the electromagnetic compatibility ([EMC Directive 2014/30/EU](#)) directive which requires independent testing by a laboratory, usually in addition to a safety standard. The EU [Machinery Directive 2006/42/EC](#) is also used for SAR and disaster response equipment.

5.4. Certification for operation of emergency response

5.4.1. Existing certification scheme and initiatives

While there isn't a single unified legislation for first responders across Europe, many countries have specific laws and regulations governing the roles, responsibilities, and certification requirements for first responders.

Professional Qualifications Directive (2005/36/EC) is a legislative framework to facilitate the recognition of professional qualifications across member states. The directive promotes the principle of mutual recognition and seeks to remove unnecessary barriers to the mobility of professionals within the European Union.

This directive is not specifically tailored to address the unique requirements and competencies of FRs. The FRs, such as firefighters, paramedics, and emergency medical technicians, often fall under national frameworks and certifications specific to the field of emergency response. These certifications typically involve specialized training programs, practical experience, and adherence to specific national regulations.

5.4.1.1. *International certification scheme*

International Search and Rescue Advisory Group

INSARAG is a global network of more than 90 countries and organization under the United Nations umbrella¹⁰⁴. INSARAG deals with urban search and rescue (USAR) related issues, and aims to make emergency preparedness and response more effective by developing common standards¹⁰⁵ such as the INSARAG Guidelines¹⁰⁶. The application of these guidelines enables the cooperation of international organisations and rescue teams from various countries by following the same principles and regulations.

¹⁰³ https://ec.europa.eu/growth/single-market/ce-marking/manufacturers_en

¹⁰⁴ <https://www.insarag.org/>

¹⁰⁵ The operational minimum standard for international USAR is define in INSASRAG Guidelines Volume II, Manual C. <https://www.insarag.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/INSARAG20Guidelines20Vol20II2C20Man20C.pdf>

¹⁰⁶ <https://www.insarag.org/methodology/insarag-guidelines/>

The INSARAG USAR response framework represents all levels of response (Figure 26). It shows a structure that seeks to ensure interoperability between the different USAR response levels;

- 1) International USAR teams
In order to ensure that only qualified and appropriate international USAR resources are deployed to an emergency, INSARAG has developed INSARAG External Classification (IEC) which is a voluntary, independent peer review process of international USAR teams. The IEC defines two levels of capacity for USAR teams according to their operational capabilities: 1) Heavy, 2) Medium
- 2) National USAR teams
With regard to national USAR teams, the INSARAG Guidelines explicitly encourage member states to establish a national accreditation process (NAP) that is developed, adapted, and framed in the member state's own reality and recommends using the INSARAG Guidelines as reference¹⁰⁷.
- 3) First responders.
To assist in the development of USAR First Responders, INSARAG has developed the First Responders Training Package¹⁰⁸.

Figure 26 - The INSARAG USAR response framework and INSARAG's IEC classification and National Accreditation

- INSARAG External Classification (IEC)
 - It is to provide better understanding of the individual abilities of USAR teams making themselves available for international assistance

¹⁰⁷ It is neither desirable nor feasible for the INSARAG community to take on the responsibility of accrediting or classifying national USAR teams, this being the responsibility of the national authorities.

¹⁰⁸ <https://www.insarag.org/capacity-building/insarag-first-responder-training/>

- Details of the requirements are listed in the IEC/IER¹⁰⁹ Guidelines¹¹⁰
 - To be classified, teams must satisfy all the standards listed in the IEC/R Checklist¹¹¹
 - The USAR teams that are IEC classified since 2005 are listed at <https://www.insarag.org/iec/iec/>
 - The World Health Organization (WHO) has also started a classification for emergency medical teams since 2016 following the IEC model
- National Accreditation Process (NAP) and INSARAG Recognized National Accreditation Process (IRNAP)
 - With regard to national USAR teams, each member state's authorities have the responsibility of providing guidance and formulating standards and procedures to verify teams' compliance.
 - The difference between NAP and IRNAP
The NAP isn't an external verification, it is a national one. The IRNAP is the external verification of the national USAR System, but the IRNAP is not replacing the IEC/R of International USAR Teams.
 - NAP
 - ✓ The INSARAG Guidelines provide a very general guidance on the establishment of a national USAR team accreditation process.
 - ✓ "Recommended minimum criteria and steps for the national USAR team accreditation processes"¹¹² provides a guidance to national authorities who are in the process of establishing a national USAR team accreditation process.
 - IRNAP
 - ✓ The 2020 INSARAG Guidelines encourage the member states to go even a step further by requesting the INSARAG Recognized National Accreditation Process (IRNAP), which certifies that the USAR system in the member state is completely in accordance with the INSARAG Guidelines methodology¹¹³.
 - ✓ The INSARAG issues a certification to the national authorities who have incorporated and implemented the INSARAG methodology in their own national standards and accreditation processes. This certification will be valid for ten years from the date of issuance.

World Health Organisation (WHO) Emergency Medical Teams (EMT) initiative

¹⁰⁹ INSARAG External Reclassification (IER): The classified teams are requested to be reclassified every 5 years to maintain its classification level

¹¹⁰ <https://www.insarag.org/iec/insarag-guidelines-volume-ii-manual-c-iec-r/>

¹¹¹ [INSARAG Guidelines Vol 2 Man C Annex D1 - IEC R Checklist 2020.xlsx \(live.com\)](#)

¹¹² https://www.insarag.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/IESRP_PAREI_List_of_the_criteria_steps_for_the_national_USAR_team_accreditation_process_ENG.pdf

¹¹³ "IRNAP Guidance Note 2022" at <https://www.insarag.org/uncategorized/irnap-since-2017/>

The aim of the WHO EMT initiative is to develop a standardized approach to EMTs to improve the quality and effectiveness of the health services at national and international level, making possible a rapid deployment and coordination after a disaster occurs.

To achieve this, the EMT has developed the Blue Book¹¹⁴ with the proposed classification and minimum standards for EMTs.

To become a WHO Global EMT, the process is as follows:

Figure 27 - WHO EMT classification process¹¹⁵

The process starts submitting an expression of interest to EMT secretariat at WHO. Afterwards, a mentor is assigned. He will lead and support the applicant organization through the peer-review process towards the quality assurance designation in the Mentorship Programme and gathering the documentary evidence. Once this step is completed, the applicant organization will receive a verification site visit (by a verification team) and if successful will be considered Quality Assured and classified according to its capacity. Only applicants representing an organization that provides emergency medical services can request the registration process. The Quality Assurance is at organization level (not at individual level). The process duration is about one year and it has to be renewed each five years.

5.4.1.2. Certification scheme in Europe

A fundamental concept of the UCPM and ECPP¹¹⁶ is mentioned in 3.1.2. The ECPP includes rescue and medical teams, experts, specialized equipment, and transportation. A certification and registration procedure for the ECPP are defined to confirm that capacities in the voluntary pool fulfil all necessary requirements.

Response capacities subject to certification

The ECPP consists of a pool of voluntarily pre-committed response capacities: 1) modules, 2) technical assistance and support teams, 3) other response capacities and 4) experts. After the capacities are certified, those certified capacities are registered in the ECPP as part of the CECIS database system (Figure 28).

¹¹⁴ <https://extranet.who.int/emt/guidelines-and-publications>

¹¹⁵ <https://extranet.who.int/emt/emt-classification>

¹¹⁶ Previously referred to as the European Emergency Response Capacity (EERC). EERC renamed as the ECPP (European Civil Protection Pool) by Decision (EU)2019/420.

Figure 28 - Response capacities of the European Civil Protection Pool

In ANNEX III of Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2018/142, 21 modules and 22 other response capacities are listed.

In order to ensure that the capacities of the ECPP meet high standards and will function properly when applied in disaster response, the European Commission defines quality requirements for the response capacities, and establishes and manages a process for certification and registration of the response capacities¹¹⁷.

Legal basis - Commission Implementing Decision 2014/762/EU

- This Decision lays down detailed rules for the implementation of Decision No 1313/2013/EU
- The capacity goals, the quality and interoperability requirements, and the registration and certification procedure of the European Emergency Response Capacity (EERC¹¹⁸) are defined
- The general requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams set out in Annex II
 - For instance, the general requirements for ‘Ground forest firefighting using vehicles’ and ‘Technical assistance and support teams’ are listed in Table 5 and Table 6jError! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..
 - Based on those requirements, gaps and necessary requirements could be find
- The information elements (e.g., Self-assessment for the quality requirements, Factsheet, SOPs Guidelines, etc.) to apply for the certification and registration procedure of a particular asset set out in Annex V

Tasks	- To contribute to the extinction of large forest and vegetal fires using vehicles
Capacities	- Sufficient human resources and vehicles for continuous operations with a minimum of 20 firefighters at any time
Main components	- Firefighters trained to fulfil the above mentioned task - 4 vehicles with off road capability - Tank capacity of each vehicle of at least 2000 litres - Adaptors for hose connection including the Storz standard
Self-sufficiency	- Article 12 applies

¹¹⁷ Details are defined in Implementing Decision 2014/762/EU (chapter 5), amended by Implementing Decision 2018/142

¹¹⁸ EERC renamed as the ECPP(European Civil Protection Pool) by Decision (EU)2019/420

Deployment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Availability for departure maximum 6 hours after the acceptance of the offer - Ability to work continuously during 7 days - Deployment by land or sea. Deployment by air is only an option in well justified cases
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Table 5 - General requirements for 'Ground forest firefighting using vehicles' (source: Implementing Decision 2014/762/EU)

Tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide or arrange for; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Support for set-up and running of office o ICT support o Logistics and subsistence support o Transport support on site
Capacities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Capable of assisting an assessment, coordination and/or preparedness team, an on-site operations coordination centre, or of being combined into a civil protection module as referred to in Article 12(2)(c)
Main components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The following support components, enabling all on site operations coordination centre functions to be fulfilled, taking into account acknowledged international guidelines such as UN guidelines; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Support for set-up and running of office o ICT support equipment o Logistics and subsistence support equipment o Transport support on site - The components shall be able to be divided in different units to ensure flexibility when adapting to the needs of a specific intervention
Deployment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Availability for departure maximum 12 hours after the request

Table 6 - General requirements for 'technical assistance and support teams' (source: Implementing Decision 2014/762/EU)

ECPP certification process

The certification process is usually carried out by the European Commission, with support of experts nominated by Member and Participating States. The certification process shall include a consultative visit, a table-top exercise, and a field exercise¹¹⁹.

There is a guidelines (Commission, 2019) for the certification and registration of response capacities in the ECPP. The guidelines provide practical guidance on how to proceed for each of the phases and steps of the certification and registration process of response capacities in the context of the ECPP. The certification and registration process consists of three phases, and the certification process itself consists of three steps: 1) a consultative visit (CV); 2) a table top exercise (TTX); 3) a field exercise (FX)¹²⁰ (Figure 29).

¹¹⁹ Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2018/142 ANNEX III (2) 1

¹²⁰ The field exercise may be waived for fire-related modules, emergency temporary camps, medical aerial evacuation modules, and certain other response capacities on a case-by-case basis.

Figure 29 - Phases and steps in the certification and registration process with timeframes (Commission, 2019)

After completing each of the three steps of the certification process, a final overview report is prepared by the DG ECHO Pool certifier. This final report will integrate the key findings on the capacity with specific regard to the ECPP certification criteria, including some key recommendations for the further development of the capacity, as relevant. The final report is sent by the Commission to the offering Member State or Participating State Civil Protection authorities (Commission, 2019).

In case a capacity is considered not to fully comply yet with the ECPP certification criteria, some reiterations may be undertaken in order to give the capacity more time to make the necessary investments to comply with the European quality requirements. For capacities that do not make the necessary progress and are considered not to comply with the ECPP certification criteria, the Commission may suggest to revoke the acceptance of the application to the Pool.

While the ECPP may not directly address the certification needs of traditional first responders, it plays a role in providing certified and interoperable resources that can support emergency response operations.

5.4.1.3. Certification for training and education

The EU makes a number of courses in the UCPM's training program under the Union Civil Protection Knowledge Network. Even though the EU's Civil protection Knowledge Network itself is not a certification scheme, it can play a valuable role in supporting the development and implementation of certification schemes in the field of civil protection. The network's activities, such as its training programs, exchange of experts, scientific advice, and thematic workshops, provide essential resources and opportunities for knowledge exchange and capacity development.

The Union Civil Protection Knowledge Network

Preventing, preparing for and responding to disasters requires strong cooperation, coordination at many levels and a combination of skills and expertise. In order to fulfil those requirements, the Commission formally established the Union Civil Protection Knowledge Network with Commission Implementing Decision 2021/1956¹²¹ in November 2021. The Union Civil Protection Knowledge Network delivers on 'preparedness' for disaster through training, exercises, exchanges and other support¹²²

- Training programme¹²³
 - To strengthen cooperation and coordination Member and Participating States in the field of civil protection, the UCPM offers a training programme tailored to specific target groups
 - This training programme supplements the national training offered to experts and intervention teams by their home country or organisation to better prepare them for international deployments under the Mechanism
 - To take part in the training courses, participants must be nominated by their National Training Coordinator or National Focal Point (third countries)
- Civil protection exercises¹²⁴
 - The exercises programme provides valuable learning opportunities for UCPM teams through highly realistic training exercise scenarios
 - Modules field and table-top exercises (EU MODEX) – EU MODEX is used in the certification process in ECPP (see section 5.5)
 - Full-scale exercises
 - Other exercises
- Exchange of experts¹²⁵
 - It allows civil protection experts from UCPM Member or Participating States or additional eligible third countries to be seconded on short-term exchanges on topics like firefighting, search and rescue or crisis communication
 - Upon the successful completion of the programme, the experts and host organisations will receive a certificate of participation in the Exchange of Experts Programme
 - A certificate will be issued when all relevant exchange documents (attendance list, evaluation form, field report, etc.) have been submitted to and validated by the Programme Team
 - To participate in an exchange, the approval of National Training Coordinator (NTC) is mandatory

¹²¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32021D1956>

¹²² Lessons learnt programme, Scientific advice and innovation, Thematic workshops & conferences, Community engagement, and Partnership facilitation opportunities
https://civil-protection-humanitarian-aid.ec.europa.eu/what/civil-protection/eu-civil-protection-knowledge-network_en

¹²³ <https://civil-protection-knowledge-network.europa.eu/disaster-preparedness/union-civil-protection-mechanism-training-programme>

¹²⁴ <https://civil-protection-knowledge-network.europa.eu/disaster-preparedness/civil-protection-exercises>

¹²⁵ <https://www.exchangeofexperts.eu/>

- Lessons learnt programme¹²⁶
 - This program identifies and shared lessons and good practices for UCPM deployments and horizontal, cross-cutting activities to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of the UCPM as a whole.
 - It focuses on the whole disaster management cycle, covering prevention, preparedness and response
- Scientific advice and innovation¹²⁷
 - Through the Knowledge Network, the scientific community and operational stakeholders in disaster management have a new space to connect and share knowledge
 - The Science pillar will base its work on the achievements and activities of the European Commission's Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre
 - The Science pillar aims at putting high-quality data and analytical tools at the disposal of the UCPM Member and Participating States and the community to facilitate evidence-based decision-making and operations
- Thematic workshops & conferences¹²⁸
 - It provides learning and networking opportunities designed around specific existing or emerging needs and risks management
 - These initiatives help experts gain cutting-edge knowledge on specific topics

The EU's Civil Protection Knowledge Network can contribute to the development and implementation of certification standards and processes for civil protection professionals and organizations. The network's activities align with capacity development and knowledge sharing, which are essential components of establishing and maintaining certification schemes.

The training program offered by the Knowledge Network can include certification-focused courses, workshops, and training modules. These programs can cover the required competencies, knowledge, and skills for certification in specific areas of FRs.

The knowledge Network can also facilitate the exchange of experts between member or participating states, which can include certification experts. This enables the sharing of best practices, lessons learned, and expertise related to certification processes and requirements. The exchange program can foster a collaborative environment where knowledge and experiences regarding certification schemes are shared and refined.

Furthermore, the network's engagement with scientific networks and expertise can contribute to the development of evidence-based certification criteria and guidelines. Scientific advice and innovation play a crucial role in ensuring that certification schemes align with the latest developments in disaster management practices and technologies. This collaboration can result in the integration of emerging concepts, such as cybersecurity and emerging technologies, into the certification framework.

¹²⁶ <https://civil-protection-knowledge-network.europa.eu/eu-civil-protection-mechanism/ucpm-lessons-learnt-programme>

¹²⁷ <https://civil-protection-knowledge-network.europa.eu/knowledge-network-science>

¹²⁸ <https://civil-protection-knowledge-network.europa.eu/news-stories-events>

The thematic workshops and conferences organized by the Knowledge Network can serve as platforms to discuss and address certification-related topics. These events can bring together stakeholders, certification bodies, experts, and practitioners to exchange ideas, explore challenges, and identify opportunities for improving certification schemes in the field of civil protection.

The inclusion of a certification component into this network's activities would be highly beneficial. A certification serves as tangible evidence of the individual's or capacity's qualifications and readiness to perform specific roles and responsibilities within the UCPM or in disaster management activities. It can not only validate their knowledge and skills but also enhance their professional credibility and increase their value within the field. Therefore, the certification can act as a reliable reference for employers, organizations, and stakeholders involved in civil protection and disaster management. It provides assurance that the certified individuals and capacities have met predetermined standards and can effectively contribute to response efforts in various contexts.

Furthermore, a certification can support the mobility and interoperability of professionals within the UCPM and across different European countries. It establishes a common framework of recognized competences, facilitating cooperation and coordination during joint operations and deployments.

National Training Coordinator

- To participate in a training, exercise and exchange, the approval of National Training Coordinator (NTC) is mandatory
- The contact details for the NTCs are listed at <https://civil-protection-knowledge-network.europa.eu/system/files/2022-07/National%20Training%20coordinators%20%28NTC%29.pdf>

The National Training Coordinators of the countries involved in use cases are:

- Spain: The Directorate General of Civil Protection and Emergencies (DGPCE) through his training branch (National Civil Protection School of Spain (ENPC)) <https://www.proteccioncivil.es/>
- Italy: Civil Protection Department <https://www.protezionecivile.gov.it>
- Portugal: Portuguese National Authority for Emergency and Civil Protection (ANEPC) programme through its National Training Centre (ENB) <http://www.prociv.pt/pt-pt/PROTECAOCIVIL/ANPC/Paginas/default.aspx>
- Slovakia: Ministry of the Interior Section of Crisis Management <https://www.minv.sk/?civil-protection>
- Bulgaria: DG Fire Safety and Civil Protection (DGFSCP) - Ministry of Interior through Centre for Specialisation and Professional Training in Fire Safety and Rescue in Varna and Centre for Professional Qualification in Montana (involve in international training) <https://www.mvr.bg/gdpbn>
- Greece: General Secretariat for Civil Protection (GSCP) - Ministry for Climate Crisis and Civil Protection <https://www.civilprotection.gr>
- Norway: The Directorate for Civil Protection (DSB) <https://www.dsb.no/>
- Netherlands: Ministry of Justice and Security National Operations Center <https://www.government.nl/ministries/ministry-of-justice-and-security>
- Denmark: The Danish Emergency Management Agency (DEMA) <https://www.brs.dk/>

- Sweden: The Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency (MSB) <https://www.msb.se/>

Approval of participants in the UCPM program

The personnel provided by the countries comply with standards such as the Urban Search and Rescue (USAR) teams recognized by INSARAG, and other accredited professionals. The member countries will contribute to the UCPM professionals with recognized skills with international standards and/or under the training created by the European Commission, which after an analysis of the available skills¹²⁹ and the needs detected after carrying out an EU risk management analysis¹³⁰. Evaluations and exercises are configured both nationally and internationally to guarantee the quality of the competitions¹³¹.

We inquired about the approval procedure to European countries to find out what is the role of the certification in the approval process, and are awaiting more reply. More countries (including the countries involved in use cases) and information could be included in the next deliverable.

Spain:

The access to training and exercises is specified in the announcement of the activity in the National Civil Protection School of Spain (ENPC) website. Applicants must meet the required profile to be admitted onto the activity and those who are already serving in organisations that form part of the national civil protection system will be prioritised; firstly those that work for the central state government, then autonomous community personnel and finally city council staff, in that order. Applications endorsed by the applicant's line manager at the entity or institution where they provide their services will be prioritised over those that do not have this endorsement. The registration to the activities is managed online only. Interested parties have to be registered on the computer application before being able to apply.¹³²

Hungary:

The Hungarian NTC assess the eligibility and availability of the participants. After that, approval of their superior is needed to proceed with their registration. The eligibility can be assessed through a database that keeps record of applicants who took part in UCPM trainings ever. The database (primarily: who-when-which course) is up to date. Once a year the National Directorate for Disaster Management (NDGDM) inquires its territorial bodies whether new applicants are available. The Hungarian NTC also keep contact with other organisations (Hungarian Red Cross, General Directorate for Water Management, Budapest WaterWorks) – they also take part in the Mechanism as partner organisations with capacities. In Hungary, the disaster management (firefighting, civil protection, industrial safety) is managed by a professional law enforcement body (NDGDM), which also manages/supervisors INSARAG-certified medium and heavy USAR

¹²⁹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32014D0762> Commission Implementing Decision of 16 October 2014 laying down rules for the implementation of Decision No 1313/2013/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism and repealing Commission Decisions 2004/277/EC, Euratom and 2007/606/EC, Euratom (notified under document C(2014) 7489) Text with EEA relevance

¹³⁰ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/ES/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32013D1313>

¹³¹ https://erccportal.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ERCC-Response/CP-Pool#/how_to_contribute/certification

¹³²

https://ec.europa.eu/echo/files/civil_protection/national_disaster_management_system/spain/iii_national_school_of_cp.pdf

teams. Hence most experts selected are professional firefighters with various backgrounds, and only in some cases are civilians.

Belgium:

The Belgian NTC select participants who correspond to the profile, either at EU or national level, in the organizations responsible for emergency response abroad, give them a briefing before and a debrief after the training they participate in. Registrations are made on an online platform of the EU. There is only an EU certificate of participation so far, and no certificate at national level.

International Association of Emergency Managers (IAEM)

- The International Association of Emergency Managers (IAEM) is a non-profit educational organization dedicated to promoting the “Principles of Emergency Management”
- The IAEM created the certification program (AEM® and CEM® program) for emergency managers to raise and maintain professional standards
 - The Associate Emergency Manager (AEM®)
 - The Certified Emergency Manager (CEM®)
 - AEM® and CEM® program are internationally recognized program¹³³ that certifies achievements within the emergency management profession
 - AEM® and CEM® certification is a peer review process administered through the IAEM
- The AEM® and CEM® program is for professionals with comprehensive emergency management responsibility
- Development of the program was supported by the U.S. Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), the National Emergency Management Association (NEMA) and a host of allied organizations
- The certification program is intended only to establish education, training and experience criteria relevant to emergency management, and to certify that the IAEM certified individual has met the established criteria
- IAEM, along with NEMA, supports the Emergency Management Accreditation Program (EMAP)

The International Emergency Management Society (TIEMS)

- TIEMS¹³⁴ is a global forum for education, training and certification in emergency and disaster management
- TIEMS international expert network comprises users, planners, researchers, industry, managers, response personnel, practitioners, social scientists, and other interested parties within emergency and disaster management
- Within its network TIEMS stimulates to the exchange of information on the use of innovative methods and technologies within emergency and disaster management
- TIEMS initiates and establishes a quality certification process for emergency and disaster managers
- TIEMS International Certifications – TQC™ & TQAC™

¹³³ Even it is international program, over 90% of current holders are American ([AEM and CEM List - Current by Country by State by Last Name - June 2022 - Include in Directory \(iaem.org\)](#))

¹³⁴ Website: [Home \(tiems.info\)](#)

- TQC™ is a certification for individual emergency managers with a nationally recognized professional certification or other individuals with documented competence and experience, practical or academic, in international emergency and disaster management
- TQAC™ is a certification for individuals with proper education in emergency management but who are lacking the practical experience as required for TQC™
- TQC™ & TQAC™ only certify knowledge and competences about international standards, requirements, and best practices, necessary to create “an international common understanding” among those working with emergency and disaster management internationally
- TQC™ & TQAC™ certification process is shown in Figure 30.
 - a) To start the process for applying for TIEMS Qualification Certification, the candidate needs to answer the questions in the TQC™ & TQAC™ Application Form and submit it.
 - b) The TQC & TQAC Certification Board will evaluate the candidate’s application form, and if accepted, the candidate can continue the TQC or TQAC application process
 - c) TIEMS Academy will guide the candidates to relevant material for the TQC & TQAC certification (Figure 31)
 - d) The exam covers the Competency Areas on “International perspectives, standards, and best practices” and consists of 10 essay and 50 multiple-choice questions from 4 selected examination areas as shown Figure 32
 - e) When the candidate has met all TQC & TQAC requirements and passed the TQC & TQAC exam he/she will be awarded the TQC or TQAC Diploma
- The certification process is based on European Union Standards and includes education, participation, contribution, experience and competency with an exam to support the process of certification

Figure 30 - TQC™ & TQAC™ process (Source: [TQC TQAC 2022 Description Document 01072022.pdf \(tiems.info\)](https://www.tiems.info/01072022/Description%20Document%2001072022.pdf))

Figure 31 - TIEMS Academy and Present Courses (Source: [TQC TQAC 2022 Description Document 01072022.pdf \(tiems.info\)](#))

TQC™ & TQAC™ Curriculum & Examination

- ❑ TIEMS encourages TQC & TQAC candidates to gain exposure to the many aspects that comprise the field. The TQC & TQAC Platform with TIEMS Academy, therefore, provides references to the most important areas.
- ❑ During the TQC & TQAC Compliance Process, the Candidate must demonstrate experience or knowledge in 7 (TQC) or 3 (TQAC) Competence Areas by a Competence Areas Summary (CAS)
- ❑ However, for the TQC & TQAC examination, the focus is on 4 important areas, on which the TQC & TQAC Candidate will be tested in a proctored, "closed book"¹⁾ examination process.

Competence Area Summary Comprises

- International Perspectives
- Preparedness, Prevention, and Mitigation
- Predictions and Early Warning
- Emergency Operations
- Public Warning
- Search and Rescue
- Recovery and Reconstruction

TQC & TQAC Examination Areas

¹⁾ "Closed Books" means no use of any material like books or electronic devices, etc. for assistance during the TQC & TQAC exam

Figure 32 - TQC™ & TQAC™ Certification Examination (Source: [TQC TQAC 2022 Description Document 01072022.pdf \(tiems.info\)](#))

Cybersecurity certification for first responders

The first responders could benefit from cybersecurity certification. In today's digital age, the first responders are increasingly reliant on technology to carry out their duties. For example, firefighters may use digital systems to track emergency response times and emergency medical personnel may use digital tools to access patient medical records. All of these systems and devices are vulnerable to cyber threats, and a breach could potentially compromise the safety and security of both first responders and the public.

By obtaining cybersecurity certification, the first responders can gain a better understanding of the threats they face and learn how to mitigate them. This can help them to better protect their digital devices and systems, as well as the sensitive information they collect and transmit. For such a reason, while cybersecurity certification may not be required for all first responders, it can be a valuable asset for those who work with digital systems and devices on a regular basis.

Although it can be challenging to develop a tailored certification scheme for the first responders due to the diverse range of roles and responsibilities within this sector and the constantly evolving threat landscape, obtaining a cybersecurity certification can still be a valuable.

By doing so, the first responders can gain a better understanding of the threats they face and learn how to mitigate them, which can help them to better protect their digital devices and systems, as well as the sensitive information they collect and transmit.

Education & Training Certification

Certifications for training and education are crucial for enhancing the knowledge, skills, and competency levels of individuals involved in disaster management. While specific certifications, curriculum, and recognized certification bodies may vary between countries, the importance of standardized education and training for first responders in cross-border mass casualty incidents (MCI) is evident, as emphasized in D6.6 (Harmonization opportunities on the preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration for first aid response to multi-casualty disasters).

To establish a structured framework for assessing and validating the knowledge and skills of first aid responders, the proposed advanced education and training kit (E&T kit) in D6.6 can be integrated into the certification scheme.

D6.6 recommended incorporating the following components into the E&T kit: blended learning, virtual reality tools, and interlinked digital platforms.

- Blended learning combines traditional classroom instruction with online modules, overcoming spatial limitations
- Virtual reality tools enable responders to practice skills in realistic environments, boosting confidence in real-life situations
- Interlinked digital platforms foster collaboration, knowledge sharing, and continuous learning among responders

By incorporating these online technologies within the certification scheme, the certification scheme can enhance training, create a collaborative network, and overcome geographical limitations. In addition, the certification scheme can facilitate the establishment of digital platforms that serve as repositories of training materials. These platforms may include assessment tools for self-evaluation, identifying areas for improvement, and tracking progress.

Aligning the certification scheme with the E&T kit may ensure standardized education and training for first aid responders. It can establish a common framework, ensure comparable knowledge and skills, and enable the adoption of advanced training methodologies. Ultimately, this enhances the preparedness and response capabilities of EU Member States in dealing with cross-border Mass Casualty Incidents.

Interoperability certification

When we talk about certification, there are certifications for products, but also certifications for procedures. An interoperability certification would greatly help in multiple-victim accidents.

When a catastrophe occurs with multiple victims, a large number of organizations are involved in providing assistance. As demonstrated in the project, collaboration between organizations is crucial for the successful resolution of emergencies. This problem is even more significant when it comes to cross-border multiple-victim accidents.

Interoperability certification will ensure that organizations meet the requirements established by the interoperability standard.

An interoperability certification would assure stakeholders that the certified organization works according to a standard. This standard would ensure, for example:

- Clear definitions of its organizational structure. Command positions, dependencies, and roles.
- Definition of responsibilities and capabilities of each role.
- Data collection. Minimum data to manage the emergency.
- Implementation of compatible technologies. Transfer and exchange of data. API interfaces.
- Communication channels. Clear protocols, agreements on the communication channels to be used.
- Safeguarding data privacy and security.
- Trained personnel. Conducting drills.

Two participants in an emergency with certification would be highly interoperable and therefore highly effective and efficient, maximizing the chances of saving lives.

5.5. Certification platforms and tools

A certification platform typically refers to a digital or online system specifically designed to facilitate the certification and training of individuals or organizations. The certification platform is a set of interactive services that provides the necessary resources to support and teach at the appropriate level the content required to acquire a certification from an accredited organization. This issues, after verification of the results of the training and/or experience, a certificate. A tool is a set of resources and methodologies used by a platform to carry out the learning task.

5.5.1. Certification platform and tool in UCPM

As previously stated in Section 3.1.2.1, the UCPM was established to strengthen the cooperation among Participating States in the field of civil protection. The UCPM certification allows modules, Technical Assistance and Support Teams (TAST) and other response capacities to test and improve their team skills and capabilities to reach the high-quality international standards that enable them to register in the European Civil Protection Pool (ECPP).

EU MODEX

EU MODEX is the platform for the certification of Modules and Other Response Capacities for the European Civil Protection Pool. In addition, it has the capacity to support the INSARAG international reclassification of Urban Search and Rescue teams and a WHO certification for Emergency Medical Teams.

MODEX is funded by European Union Civil Protection with the aim of better prepare modules/capacities/civil protection authorities and experts for international deployments under the Union Civil Protection Mechanism (UCPM), to ensure a faster, coordinated and efficient response to emergencies.¹³⁵

From this platform you can perform two types of exercises:

- Table top exercise (TTX):
 - Discussion-based sessions
 - Focus on strategic decision-making and managerial preparation during a deployment
- Field exercises (FX):
 - Mobilisation / arrival
 - Operational SUMMA 112 medical services are part of the public services of the Community of Madrid. The personnel that make up the service have passed the access and training tests to work in these health resources.
 - Demobilisation

CN APELL-RO¹³⁶ is National Center Apell for Disaster Management as independent, non-governmental and not for profit NGO who has these objectives:

- To educate, train and improve specialists in technological and natural risk management
- Set up a work platform among local communities, economic stakeholders and competent authorities for emergency response

Five EU MODEX are supported by EU funding through the UCPM;

- Field exercises for emergency medical teams¹³⁷
 - These MODEX exercises are targeting medical teams of all kinds and sizes as well as laboratory capacities operating in a disaster response environment with a need for, among others, basic health care, basic and complex trauma care.
 - These medical teams are exercising together with EUCPT (European Civil Protection Team) and TAST
- Field exercises for EU Civil Protection Teams¹³⁸
 - These MODEX exercises are functional exercises for EUCPT and TAST replicating a deployment mission under the UCPM, targeting the operational, tactical and strategic levels of a mission
 - Those exercises are a perfect opportunity for experts to challenge themselves with the closest to reality situation in the response phase of the emergency or in a preparedness mission
 - All exercises include the participation of three EUCPT and three TAST and UNDAC (United Nations Disaster Assessment and Coordination) members for the outside of Europe scenario

¹³⁵ <https://10years.eu-modex.eu/what-is-eu-modex>

¹³⁶ <https://www.apell-euromodex.eu/>

¹³⁷ <https://civil-protection-knowledge-network.europa.eu/projects/field-exercises-emergency-medical-teams>

¹³⁸ <https://civil-protection-knowledge-network.europa.eu/projects/field-exercises-eu-civil-protection-teams>

- Field exercises for urban search & rescue modules¹³⁹
 - These MODEX exercises have an integrated approach for specialised modules and other response capacities to respond to consequences of serious structure collapse mainly due to the strong earthquakes when USAR modules are essential
- Field exercises flood, forest fires and CBRN¹⁴⁰
 - These MODEX exercises have an integrated approach for specialised modules and other response capacities to respond to floods, forest fires or chemical, biological, radiological or nuclear hazards
- Table top exercises for key personnel of Modules¹⁴¹
 - On the basis of an exercise scenario (such as an earthquake, flood or forest fire), the MODEX table top exercises focus on in-depth cooperation between different actors (local and international) in a disaster environment
 - Participants have an opportunity to test coordination, interoperability, procedures, communication, reporting and information management
 - These exercises are for key personnel of the different modules, i.e. Team Leader and Deputy Team Leader or Liaison Officer, together with EUCPT and TAST

For example, Turkey hosted the MODEX field exercise in November 2021. The EUCPT made up of experts from 7 different EU Member States and 13 participating capacities from 7 different countries. These included;

- Urban search and rescue teams from Turkey, France, Greece, Austria, and Bulgaria
- Emergency medical teams from Turkey and Spain
- Emergency remote pilot aerial system team from France
- Technical assistance and support team (TAST) from Italy

During this MODEX, the Italian TAST undertook the certification for the European Civil Protection Pool.

Another example, the Slovenian High Capacity Pumping module (SI-HCP) completed its certification process by participating in an EU MODEX in Romania in October 2021.

The exercises are open to countries inside and outside Europe willing to host an exercise and to Modules, Other Response Capacities, Technical Assistance Support Teams (TAST) registered in the Common Emergency Communication and Information System (CECIS) and European Civil Protection Team (EUCPT) experts. To take part in exercises, experts must be nominated by their National Training Coordinators (NTC). Modules, other Response Capacities and TAST must apply through their National Focal Points.

¹³⁹ <https://civil-protection-knowledge-network.europa.eu/projects/field-exercises-urban-search-rescue-modules>

¹⁴⁰ <https://civil-protection-knowledge-network.europa.eu/projects/field-exercises-flood-forest-fires-and-cbrn>

¹⁴¹ <https://civil-protection-knowledge-network.europa.eu/projects/table-top-exercises-key-personnel-modules>

ECPP certification assessment tool

The certification and registration process should be seen as one key element of the broader quality assurance of European response capacities. To provide this quality assurance, there is an assessment tool¹⁴². In this tool, quality requirements for the ECPP are listed under the four sub-topic: 1) Preparedness; 2) Self-sufficiency; 3) Interoperability; 4) Coordination (Figure 33).

For instance, the quality requirements for interoperability are shown in Figure 34. These requirements are quite high level. The reason of these high level requirements is that the assessment tool should be flexible in its application. But, complementary requirements could be suggested according to the needs.

Figure 33 - Quality Requirements for the ECPP

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https://ercportal.jrc.ec.europa.eu/DesktopModules/ResponseCapacity/Documents/Template%20ECPP_Certification%20Tool_Dec2019.pdf

3a- INTEROPERABILITY

Area evaluated		Rating: E/S/B/NA		
		CV	TTX	FX
Language	Personnel in the team management function speak sufficient English for operations			
Compatibility of personnel and equipment	The team can assist other teams with equipment if requested			
	The team can provide logistical support to other stakeholders or teams			
	At working sites, the team is integrated in the emergency response structure and interoperable			
	Equipment is compatible with other teams equipment standards			
Command and control structures / reporting	The command and control function of the team can adapt to LEMA demands, if necessary			
	The team management is aware of the coordination international structures			
	The team make use of standardised reports and templates			
Communications and IT tools	The team has the 'ability' to communicate effectively with their home country			
	The team has the 'ability' to communicate effectively within their team members			
	The team has the 'ability' to communicate effectively with external partners			
Procedures and Plan of Action (PoA)	The team develops a structured PoA with the basic information: assessment of the situation; development of strategies to achieve objectives; team composition and organisation; assignment of resources; management of ongoing operations; identification of accomplishments; logistics and communications; safety and security; media management; other additional resources if required.			
	The team share appropriate information of the PoA with other actors and provide regular reporting to the coordination structures on progress and shortfalls			
	The team members are regularly informed and briefed on the main topics of the PoA			
	The team management is regularly assessing the situation and reflecting the updates in the plan of action			
	There is a well defined team composition with clear requirements for every role to implement the PoA			
	There is flexibility to reassigned tasks if necessary			
	Tactics are developed and adapted to changing circumstances			
	The PoA considers the possible interaction with other actors (local and international)			
Safety and security (S&S)	The S&S function is clearly identified in the team structure			
	A S&S plan is prepared and updated during the mission			
	The team members are regularly informed and briefed on the main topics of the S&S plan			
	The S&S plan considers the possible interaction with other actors (local and international)			

Figure 34 - Example of certification assessment tool for ECPP – Interoperability (source: ECPP Certification Process Assessment Tool)

5.5.2. Technologies and equipment

There are many private companies that provide a certification platform. They provide customized services for the equipment, but it is fragmented according to the technologies and equipment, and are not accepted across the Europe. Some of those platforms support the certification process rather than issue the certification. For example, ARMATURE FABRIC¹⁴³ is cloud-based software for accreditation, certification, audit management, and continuous quality

¹⁴³ <https://armaturecorp.com/>

improvement. It has been developed to make it easier for organizations to manage and monitor their accreditation and certification activities. It would be useful for getting a certification of the first responder enablers if that kind of software platform could be introduced in. Especially for complex systems, a definite advantage may be expected.

The Notified body (see section 3.1.1) may also be considered as the certification platform if they provide a specific procedure for the certification.

NANDO¹⁴⁴ (New Approach Notified and Designated Organisations) Information System

- The Member States, EFTA countries (EEA members) and other countries with which the EU has concluded Mutual Recognition Agreements (MRAs)¹⁴⁵ and Protocols to the Europe Agreements on Conformity Assessment and Acceptance of Industrial Products (PECAs) have designated Notified Bodies, established per directive.
- List of Notified Bodies can be searched on the NANDO Information system website
- The lists include the identification number of each notified body as well as the tasks for which it has been notified, and are subject to regular update

Based on such existing software and information system, a way to establish an integrated certification platform for the first responder enablers may be suggested.

5.5.3. Operation of emergency response

Certification regarding the operation of emergency response is related to training, as the aim is to ensure and certify that attendees have reached a certain level of knowledge after training.

5.5.3.1. Emergency Medical Services

SUMMA 112 medical services are part of the public sanitary services of the Community of Madrid. The personnel that make up the service have passed the access and training tests to work in these health resources. The professionals of this service are familiar with the procedures to be put in place in the event of a disaster and are trained to intervene and coordinate with other services and international resources.

The Community of Madrid has a USAR team (ERICAM) which is the one that would go out specifically to work in international natural disasters (mainly in locating and rescuing victims in collapsed structures) although they have also been activated in large fires outside their autonomous community.

5.5.3.2. Civil Protection

UCPM

UCPM offers self-instructed e-learning modules accessible upon registration on the platform: <https://ucpm.e-learning.cc>. To take part in the training courses, participants must be nominated by their National Training Coordinator or National Focal Point (third countries).

¹⁴⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/nando/index.cfm>

¹⁴⁵ https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/goods/international-aspects-single-market/mutual-recognition-agreements_en

Spain

The ENCP provides a training platform called SAFE where professionals of the Civil Protection and Emergency Services can access to the training activities and obtain/manage their certificates. The access to this platform requires a previous register process.

5.5.3.3. Red Cross

Red Cross EU is a membership office representing the 27 National Red Cross Societies in the UE, the Norwegian Red Cross, the Icelandic Red Cross and the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC)¹⁴⁶. Each organization is independent and offers specific solutions about skills in each country.

As auxiliaries to their national authorities, they play a key role in disaster management planning and response mechanisms.

As organization, The Red Cross trains professionals at a national level, allowing them to participate in first aid and emergencies.

For example, Red Cross Spain has online platform to certificate different level of education¹⁴⁷.

5.5.3.4. Commercial quality management and certification platforms

Many platforms are available to help organisations manage quality management system (QMS) compliance where processes, procedures and personnel skills must be documented. The platforms in Table 7 contains examples of different software packages that help organisations with accreditation, certification, training and compliance.

The main types of platforms described in the table are certification or training platforms for personnel, and platforms that helps accreditation and auditing organisations.

Platform type	Platform name	Platform description
Certification of employees	Mettl https://mettl.com/	General purpose certification software with security and proctoring features. Type of certification covered by the platform ranges from financial certification, language certifications, government certification, skill certifications, safety certification and IT certification. Data hosting on AWS on localized servers in Europe, China and India.
Training	Real training www.realtraining.no	Virtual training for fire prevention.
Training and certification	Medicore Medical Services https://www.medicore.ie/	Training courses accredited by a broad range of training bodies including the Pre-Hospital Emergency Care Council, Irish Heart Foundation, FETAC and Health & Safety Authority. The training programmes can be delivered on-site or in the company training centre. Also possible to do blended learning. Located in Dublin, Ireland.

¹⁴⁶ <https://redcross.eu/>

¹⁴⁷ <https://www2.cruzroja.es/formate>

Management and monitor of accreditation and certification activities	ARMATURE Fabric™ https://armaturecorp.com/armature-fabric/	Offer a software package for accreditation, certification, audit, and continuous quality improvement needs. The ARMATURE Fabric supports data collection and workflow management related to accreditation and certification.
Inspection, Audit, Certification, and Standards Software	Intact Platform https://intact-systems.com/	The Intact Platform is cloud and on premise Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) solution for audits, assessments, certification, accreditation, and standards worldwide. The platform offers functionality to handle the business side of the organization, but claims to handle any Standard and Audit Service with modular features and a scalable architecture.
Compliance software package	Qualtrax https://www.qualtrax.com/	Cloud based compliance software that helps organizations with ISO standard compliance and audits through managing documentation, automating business processes, training management, and ensuring critical industry regulations are addressed. Main modules: -Accreditation management -Document management -Process management -Testing and Training
Certification management software	CredHQ™ https://agilutions.com/certification-and-credentialing-software/credhq/	Certification management software for helping certification organizations manage the customer's certification processes. The platform also includes a credential engine for managing courses and track progress of the credentialing process.
Cryptographic assets, certificate management and PKI as-a-Service	Crypto-Agility Platform™ https://www.keyfactor.com/platform/	Digital certificate as-a-service platform that helps organizations automate, manage and deploy certificates. The platform can manage digital keys and certificates for large cloud based systems down to embedded IoT devices.
Accreditation and compliance management	CompWALK https://compwalk.com/	The CompWALK platform includes accreditation services to help accreditation organizations manage, safeguard and assess accreditation operations for clients. The platform also offers compliance and certification management to help conduct inspections, compliance operations and certification.

Table 7 - List of different commercial certification platforms

5.6. The need for new conformity assessment criteria

Test facilities rely on well-defined conformity assessment criteria as the foundation for their evaluation processes. These criteria guide the selection of test parameters, the conduct of tests, and the collection of relevant data to determine if a product or service meets the required standards.

Emergency response technologies are constantly evolving, which means that the criteria for certification also need to evolve accordingly. The existing assessment framework, while robust, might not encompass the full spectrum of challenges and capabilities inherent in modern SAR. Thus, the integration of new conformity assessment criteria may address emerging dimensions of effectiveness, adaptability, and sustainability.

Implementing new conformity assessment criteria in disaster management can indeed be challenging due to the inherent diversity of situations, technologies, and stakeholders involved in disaster scenarios. The challenges in implementing new conformity assessment criteria in disaster management include:

- **Diverse Scenarios** - The field of disaster management encompasses a wide range of incidents, including natural disasters and human-made events. Different types of disasters require varied equipment, technologies, and approaches. Developing a one-size-fits-all set of criteria can be complex due to the diverse nature of emergencies.
- **Rapidly changing technologies** - The field of disaster management is influenced by rapidly evolving technologies. New criteria must account for emerging technologies and adaptability to changing circumstances.
- **Interdisciplinary Nature** - Disaster management involves multiple disciplines, including emergency response, medical care, engineering, communications, logistics, and more. Criteria need to address this interdisciplinary nature.
- **Local context** - Criteria must consider the specific needs and resources of the local context, including geographical factors, cultural differences, and available infrastructure.
- **Cross-border cooperation** - Collaboration among various organisations is essential in disaster response. Criteria need to facilitate interoperability and coordination across these entities.
- **Resource constraints** - Some regions or organizations might have limited resources, making it challenging to meet certain criteria, especially if they require significant financial or technical investments.
- **Training and skills** - Implementing new criteria might require training personnel to meet the new standards, which could pose logistical challenges.

Given these challenges, it's crucial to develop new conformity assessment criteria in a way that allows for flexibility, adaptability, and scalability. While implementing new conformity assessment criteria in disaster management is undoubtedly complex, it can lead to more standardized, efficient, and effective response and recovery efforts. Balancing the need for uniformity with the flexibility to accommodate diverse scenarios will be a key consideration in designing and implementing such criteria.

5.6.1. Product conformity assessment criteria

In response to the dynamic landscape of emergency response, it's imperative to establish new conformity assessment criteria for equipment. These criteria ensure that tools used in disaster

management can meet the demands of evolving scenarios. The following criteria could be proposed:

- **Interoperability and Compatibility**
Evaluate the product's ability to seamlessly integrate with other tools and systems, enabling efficient communication and data exchange during disaster operations. Harmonized conformity in this aspect guarantees that disparate tools from different sources can work cohesively during critical situations.
For instance, interoperability is crucial for communication systems used by different agencies in disaster response. During a forest fire incident, firefighters, law enforcement, and medical teams from various organizations need to communicate seamlessly. Harmonized conformity assessment criteria ensure that their radios, communication protocols, and frequencies are compatible, enabling effective coordination and information sharing.
- **Compatible encryption methods and security measures**
It can ensure that sensitive information shared between agencies/organizations remains secure and protected from unauthorized access.
- **Standardized protocol**
It can facilitate smooth data transmission and reducing the risk of miscommunication.
- **Rapid Deployment and Mobility**
Assess the product's ease of transportation, setup, and deployment, ensuring swift response to emergencies regardless of location. Harmonized conformity ensures that equipment can be quickly moved and utilized, reducing response time, and enhancing overall efficiency.
- **Resilience and Durability**
Consider the product's capacity to withstand harsh environmental conditions, ensuring reliability during extended operations in challenging terrains. Harmonized conformity sets benchmarks for equipment robustness, making certain that tools can function reliably in adverse conditions.
- **Adaptability and Modularity**
Examine whether the product can be adapted or customized to suit different disaster scenarios and response strategies. Harmonized conformity here facilitates the development of flexible tools that can cater to a range of emergency situations.

5.6.2. Technology conformity assessment criteria

Modern emergency response heavily relies on technology, requiring new conformity assessment criteria that reflect the fast-paced advancements. These criteria ensure that technologies remain effective, secure, and capable of seamless integration. The following criteria may be proposed:

- **Cybersecurity and data integrity**
Evaluate the technology's resilience against cyber threats and unauthorized access, safeguarding sensitive information during disaster situations.
- **Real-time analytics and decision support**
Assess the technology's ability to process real-time data and provide actionable insights to aid decision-making during dynamic disaster situations.
- **Scalability and flexibility**

Examine whether the technology can scale up or down based on the scope of the disaster, adapting to both localized incidents and larger-scale emergencies.

- Human-machine interaction

Consider the user-friendliness and accessibility of the technology, ensuring that operators can effectively utilize it under high-stress conditions.

By incorporating these criteria, the certification scheme not only aligns with the latest technological advancements but also contributes to more resilient and adaptable emergency response ecosystems.

5.6.3. Operation conformity assessment criteria

The effectiveness of disaster management operations depends on well-defined procedures and collaboration among personnel. New conformity assessment criteria for operation address the human and procedural aspects of disaster response. The following criteria may be proposed:

- Training and competency - Evaluate the training programs for emergency response personnel, ensuring they possess the necessary skills to handle diverse disaster scenarios.
- Community engagement and communication - Assess the strategies in place for involving affected communities in disaster preparedness and response efforts, promoting transparency and trust.
- Cross-border coordination - Examine the protocols and mechanisms for cross-border coordination, promoting seamless collaboration and resource sharing.
- Ethical considerations and cultural sensitivity - Ensure that disaster response operations respect ethical guidelines, human rights, and cultural sensitivities, particularly when dealing with diverse populations.

In addition, harmonized conformity assessment criteria are essential in disaster management, where consistency, interoperability, and standardized practices are crucial for effective response and mitigation efforts. The harmonized conformity assessment criteria can provide a structured and standardized approach to disaster management certification, enabling efficient response, enhancing coordination, and ultimately contributing to more effective and resilient disaster preparedness and mitigation efforts.

6. Sustainability in certification and evaluation

Sustainable development can be defined based on the UN definition (UN, 1987) as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”. This is expanded further into 17 sustainable development goals that were adopted by all UN member states in 2015. For SAR and disaster response goal 2, 3, 6, 9, 11, 13, 14, 15, 16 and 17 can be relevant (see Figure 35)

Figure 35 - The 17 sustainable development goals (sdg.iisd.org)

Sustainability in the context of disaster response encompasses using resources efficiently and economically at the same time performing actions that seek to limit the consequences of the disaster at hand. A disaster response that performs the necessary actions in a timely fashion with effective use of sufficient resources should benefit the people and society that is affected by the disaster as well as limit negative environmental effects from the disaster and from the disaster response. How sustainable the emergency response operation is will also be dependent upon the resilience planning of the community (Homsy, Liao, & Warner, 2019). The resilience of a community impacts the ability to remain functional or recover quickly when facing a disaster. A more resilient society might impact sustainability and sustainability might impact resilience (Homsy et al., 2019).

An assumption is that well planned and organized disaster response in a community which has invested in resilience will score higher on sustainability. Communities where the building codes demand earthquake resistant or earthquake proof buildings will have less demanding disaster response operations than communities without such building codes.

Technology can impact the ability to efficiently conduct search and rescue operations during disaster response by giving accurate data from the scene of the disaster. It is critical that the first responders and disaster response coordinators gain situational awareness and understanding as early as possible in an emergency response situation. Aerial drones, rovers, pre-installed and deployable sensors, cameras, and reporting systems for people on the scene can help the response team to plan and execute an effective response. Sensor systems for detecting and localization of fire and explosions in tunnels will give critical information to first responders (Kim, Son, Kim, Song, & Lee, 2018). Drones for 3D mapping of a disaster zone can affect both efficiency and effectiveness as explored in research (Zwęgliński, 2020), but there is still a need to study exactly how and if these drones can increase efficiency and effectiveness. Testing and evaluation of how the technology affects disaster response is not straightforward, disasters are often

wider international pursuit of the underlying policy goals and secure a competitive advantage for first-mover industries.”

6.2. The human element

Equipment and tools for SAR and ER personnel must be functional under the demanding circumstances during disaster response. The environmental conditions can be though and can render unfit equipment useless. A handheld tablet designed for enhancing situational awareness and audio/visual communication can be useful in disaster response situations but might be impossible to use in an open boat searching for people at sea in large wave, strong wind, and water spray. Even certified industrial grade rugged IP67+ tablets or tablets with military specifications might not even be useful in the conditions where it is needed.

It is not always enough that the product is certified according to a specific product standard, but the product should also be subject to requirements and criteria for usability, accessibility, and human-system interaction.

The ISO 9241 standard for “Ergonomics of human-system interaction” gives both requirements and recommendations for ensuring human-centred design through the life cycle of the product or system. The usability of the system can be tested through usability conformance tests which is offered by different test labs. Figure 37 shows the process of usability conformance test and Figure 38 shows the assessment process leading up to certification based on the ISO 9241 series.

Figure 37 – Usability conformance test process as offered by TÜV Austria Cybersecurity Lab

Figure 38 – Certification process for User Experience and Usability (TÜV Austria Cybersecurity lab)

6.2.1. Elements of human centred design certification

The definition of usability of a product or system is defined as the “extent to which a system, product or service can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified context of use” (ISO 9241-210, 2019). With this definition, the usability of a product or system is dependent upon the context which it is used.

As shown in (chapter of operational certification/requirements) the different technologies can have both certification requirements for the technical properties of the product as well as certification requirements for operating a system. With usability certification, the context of use must be taken into account as shown in the flow diagram of the usability conformance test process in Figure 37.

6.2.2. Principles of human-centred design

The relevance of human-centred design for SAR and emergency response products and systems seems foremost to be the focus on the interaction between users, tasks, and the environment. For SAR and ER products and systems the user is often in a stressful situation, in less than optimal environmental conditions doing tasks that might have serious impact on life or death for people involved. This highlights the importance of testing and evaluating in real operational contexts for the certification to hold any real value.

Different user groups might have different requirements, different contexts, and environments of use, which should be taken into account during certification. This is not unique for SAR and Emergency response products and systems but has significant importance for how usable and effective a particular solution is when used in these demanding operations.

6.2.3. Stages of human-centred design

The human-centred design is broken down into for main parts (ISO 9241-210, 2019);

- 1) Understanding and specifying the context of use (see ISO 9241-11 for details)

- a. Describe context of use, stakeholders, user groups, environment (HW, SW, physical, social, organizational etc.)
- 2) Specifying the user requirements
 - a. Requirements derived from user needs and context, need for user interaction and ergonomics, usability requirements and performance criteria, requirement trade-offs.
- 3) Producing design solutions
 - a. Designing to meet the requirements, different design proposals, user feedback early in the design process, iterative design, sample prototypes and user-centred evaluation and feedback in the design process.
- 4) Evaluating the design
 - a. User-centred evaluation, measure usability performance and satisfaction, field validation, inspection based evaluation before user testing, long term monitoring with follow-up evaluation.

These points are in line with any quality focused development process based on quality leadership standards (ISO9000, 2015), but will also impact the sustainability aspect. Products and systems developed by following the human-centred design principles from ISO9241 will directly support two key areas of sustainability; economic and social sustainability. The economic sustainability is ensured by the strong focus on the needs and requirements of the users which also includes cost-effectiveness and quality of the solution. This will in turn increase the likelihood of continuation of use and less waste. The social sustainability aspect is primarily related to the product or system's effectiveness for saving life and limiting further injuries or damages.

6.3. Interoperability of facilities for the certification

The concept of interoperability ensures that the diverse range of technologies, equipment, and operational practices involved in emergency response can seamlessly communicate and collaborate. As part of the certification process, the interoperability of these components is important for efficient emergency response ecosystem.

Interoperability involves the different systems, devices and people accessing, sharing and working in a coordinated manner using data and information at intersections between organizations and public entities at all levels with the aim of optimizing the portability of information and training and training services.

The interoperability of facilities implies complete equivalence in carrying out all training, tests and evaluations for the same training, providing the same guarantees. The result is obtaining a recognizable certification without the place of certification being a relevant aspect.

One of the characteristics of interoperability is to allow completing the training and/or complementing skills with additional training between different entities. This generates the need to guarantee the security of sensitive information and generate secure digital certificates. Along the same lines, a uniform recognition of the necessary skills for training agents must be guaranteed in order to guarantee uniform training.

From EC, a list of available capacities is available and published by the resources provided by each participating country (Figure 5) with standard classification. The acquisitions of these capacities are developed under the same international standards, or development of the published UCPM modules; creating an international standard as part of an international training catalogue.

In the following subsections, existing test facilities for certification will be explored, addressing how they contribute to ensuring the interoperability of the evaluated elements.

6.3.1. Existing test facilities for the certification

The test facility should provide an objective and independent evaluation for the compliance of product/service/system with the relevant standards and regulation. To ensure that the test facilities have the necessary expertise, independence, and impartiality to carry out the conformity assessment procedure, the test facilities need to be accredited by a competent accreditation body (it has been explained in section 3.4). The accredited test facilities help to ensure the consistency and reliability of the certification process. The accredited test facilities are subject to regular audits and assessments to ensure that they maintain their competence and comply with the relevant accreditation standards.

There are many test facilities available for getting certification of product/service/system, and some of international test facilities are listed as follows: UL, TÜV Rheinland, DEKRA, KIWA (<https://www.kiwa.com/en/>), THALES(<https://www.thalesgroup.com/en>). In addition, the test facilities (in Europe) that can issue the certification for a drone are listed as follows; ALTER TECHNOLOGY(www.altertechnology.com), CerTrust (www.certrust.eu), Applus+ (www.appluslaboratories.com), NavCert(www.navcert.de) and TÜV Rheinland(www.tuv.com/safety)

6.3.1.1. EU Declaration of conformity

To place a product on the EU market, a manufacturer is requested to evidence that the product meets all the applicable requirements. This process includes testing, inspection and certification.

This process is carried out by the manufacturer unless some specific product categories which requires the involvement of a conformity assessment body (CAB).

The list of the existing CABs within Europe can be consulted on the New Approach Notified and Designated Organisations (NANDO) website¹⁴⁹.

6.3.1.2. European Union Testing Facilities for market surveillance

Market surveillance authorities perform appropriate checks on the characteristics of products to guarantee non-food products on the EU market complies with the proper regulations. To do this checks, the EC is working on the creation of European Union Testing Facilities (EUTFs). At this moment, the EC has just started a call for expression of interest (July 2022) to determine the entities that will be designated EUTFs for the Radio Equipment sector.

6.3.1.3. Cybersecurity certification laboratories

International level

Under the international agreement CCRA, IT products/systems are evaluated and certified by independent licensed laboratories that are listed on the Common Criteria webpage¹⁵⁰.

¹⁴⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/nando/>

¹⁵⁰ <https://www.commoncriteriaportal.org/labs/>

European level

Under the current European agreement SOG-IS, the list of Certification Authorities and Information Technology Security Evaluation Facilities (ITSEF) per country can be consulted at the SOG-IS portal¹⁵¹.

National level

The following table summarises some of the National ITSEF within Europe.

Country	Certification Authority	ITSEF list available at:
France	ANSSI	https://www.ssi.gouv.fr/en/certification/common-criteria-certification/licensed-itsef/licensed-itsef-list/
Germany	BSI	https://www.bsi.bund.de/EN/Themen/Unternehmen-und-Organisationen/Standards-und-Zertifizierung/Zertifizierung-und-Anerkennung/Listen/Liste-CC-ITSEC-Pruefstellen/liste-cc-itsec-pruefstellen_node.html
Italy	OCSI	https://www.ocsi.gov.it/index.php/laboratori/lvs-accreditati.html
Netherlands	NSCIB	https://www.tuv-nederland.nl/common-criteria/itsef.html
Norway	SERTIT	https://sertit.no/evaluation-and-certification/it-security-evaluation-facilities-itsefs/
Spain	CNN	https://oc.ccn.cni.es/en/accreditation-of-laboratories/accredited-laboratories
Sweden	CSEC	https://www.fmv.se/verksamhet/ovrig-verksamhet/csec/evaluering-och-certifiering/evalueringsforetag/
Belgium	BELAC	https://economie.fgov.be/en/themes/quality-and-safety/accreditation-belac/accredited-bodies
Denmark	Center for Cyber Security	-
Slovakia	NBU	https://www.nbu.gov.sk/en/cyber-security/audit/list-of-auditors/index.html
Portugal	CNCS	-
Bulgaria	Bulgarian Defence Ministry	-
Greece	NCSA	-

Table 8 - National ITSEF in Europe

6.3.1.4. Data Spaces certification laboratories

International Data Spaces Certification implements security criteria defined in the Cloud Computing Compliance Criteria Catalogue (C5) and the CSA Cloud Controls Matrix.

¹⁵¹ https://www.sogis.eu/uk/status_participant_en.html

Regarding the certification for International Data Spaces Association (IDSA), SQS is the European accredited laboratory for the validation of components according to their standards.

It offers different services according to the required needs¹⁵²:

- Independent validation services of different commercial IDSA components for trusted data sharing applications
- Support to developers and European companies in service certification across different sectors (logistics and transport, development of medical and pharmaceutical products, etc.)
- Evaluation report preparation for IDSA certification.

6.3.1.5. Testing facilities for Artificial Intelligence (AI)

The Digital Europe Programme is an EU funding programme focused on bringing digital technology to businesses, citizens and public administrations.¹⁵³

Under this programme, the EC foresees to co-fund with Member States a limited number of Testing and Experimentation Facilities (TEFs)¹⁵⁴, both physical and virtual facilities, to optimize the development and deployment of AI within Europe, supporting the integration, testing and experimentation of AI-based technologies (including validation and demonstration).

The proposal is for these TEFs to be open sites for all technology vendors to test their AI-based products and solutions in real-world environments at scale. They will be focused on four sectors:

- Agri-food
- Manufacturing
- Healthcare
- smart cities and communities

Although TEFs have similarities to Open Innovation Test Beds, their main difference is the exclusive use for AI-based solutions by providing tests in a real environment.

It is important to mention that these TEFs will be used with solutions from Technological Readiness Level (TRL) six to eight. So, they are not replacing Certification Bodies in any case.

Once validated and with a proper TRL level, the product/service should be ready to be deployed at an end-user site (e.g. “test before invest” activities of a European Digital Innovation Hub (EDIH)).

When the European Parliament and the Council adopt the AI Act¹⁵⁵, FET will be able to provide infrastructures and environments for testing under the supervision of the competent national authorities, supporting certification activities if required.

¹⁵² <https://www.sqs.es/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Brochure-IDSA-SQS.pdf>

¹⁵³ [The Digital Europe Programme | Shaping Europe’s digital future \(europa.eu\)](#)

¹⁵⁴ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/activities/testing-and-experimentation-facilities>

¹⁵⁵ <https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/>

6.3.2. Capabilities in test facilities

In order to ensure a comprehensive evaluation and certification process, the test facilities must possess a wide range of capabilities and resources. These capabilities are essential for conducting thorough assessments to determine whether a product or system meets the required standards and regulations. Some capabilities used in accredited test facilities include:

- Specialized testing equipment such as EMC (Electromagnetic Compatibility) testing equipment¹⁵⁶, structural testing equipment¹⁵⁷, fire-safety testing equipment¹⁵⁸, and so on.
- Engineers, scientists, and technicians with expertise in various domains, such as electrical safety, materials science, software security, and so on.
- For the cybersecurity, advanced cybersecurity testing tools¹⁵⁹ that facilitate the identification and assessment of security weaknesses.

New capabilities has been implemented to enable comprehensive evaluations, cost savings, and the ability to adapt to evolving technologies. For instance, in the case of the automotive industry, simulation techniques are utilized in crash testing. Instead of conducting physical crash tests for every design iteration, test labs employ simulation software to replicate and analyse various crash scenarios. In this way, simulation enables test labs to assess a wide range of scenarios, including rare or extreme events that are challenging to replicate physically. This feature can be effectively utilized in the field of disaster management. By using simulation in the certification process, the test labs may reduce the cost and time associated with physical tests, as virtual simulations can be performed more rapidly and at a fraction of the expense. In addition, it allows for a more thorough evaluation of different design iterations, helping manufacturers refine their products for better safety performance.

In addition, accredited test facilities must continuously innovate and adapt to keep pace with emerging technologies. These new and cutting-edge technologies, such as AI, IoT, blockchain, 5G, and more, are not only transforming various industries but also reshaping the disaster management field and the way products and systems function. Furthermore, these new technologies can also serve as valuable capabilities. For instance, IoT devices equipped with sensors are being used in test facilities. For automotive crash testing, IoT sensors embedded in crash test dummies and vehicles provide real-time data on impact forces, allowing engineers to assess safety measures more accurately. Blockchain provides a secure and tamperproof ledger for recording test results, certifications, and compliance data. This technology ensures transparency and traceability throughout the certification process, helping to establish trust among stakeholders¹⁶⁰.

In disaster management test facilities, the need for new capabilities is driven by several important reasons:

- Advanced early warning systems – emerging technologies can enable more advanced early warning systems that provide timely and accurate information about impending

¹⁵⁶ <https://www.ul.com/services/testing/emc-testing>

¹⁵⁷ <https://www.appluslaboratories.com/global/en/what-we-do/services/structural-testing>

¹⁵⁸ <https://www.appluslaboratories.com/global/en/what-we-do/services/fire-testing>

¹⁵⁹ <https://www.cobalt.io/blog/top-20-penetration-testing-tools-for-cybersecurity>

¹⁶⁰ <https://ts2.space/en/the-future-of-renewable-energy-certificates-how-blockchain-is-changing-the-game/>

- disasters. Test facilities need to evaluate the reliability and effectiveness of these systems to ensure they can provide life-saving alerts and information.
- Data analytics and prediction – AI and machine learning can process vast amounts of data to predict disaster patterns and assess the potential impact. Test facilities must have the capability to test and validate these predictive models to enhance disaster preparedness.
 - Communication and coordination – IoT and 5G technologies facilitate real-time communication and coordination among disaster response teams. Ensuring the seamless integration and functionality of these communication systems is crucial for effective disaster management.
 - Rescue and recovery technologies – Robotics and drones equipped with AI can assist in SAR operations during disasters. These technologies need to be rigorously tested to ensure they can operate reliably in harsh and unpredictable conditions.
 - Resilience of critical infrastructure – Blockchain technology can enhance the resilience of critical infrastructure by improving data integrity and security. Test facilities should evaluate the effectiveness of blockchain solutions in safeguarding essential services during disasters.
 - Cybersecurity – With the increasing reliance on digital systems for disaster management, cybersecurity becomes paramount. Advanced cybersecurity testing tools are necessary to identify and address vulnerabilities in disaster management systems.
 - Training and simulations – Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) can be used for training and simulating disaster scenarios for response teams. Test facilities should have the capability to assess the realism and effectiveness of these training tools.
 - Regulatory compliance – As emerging technologies are integrated into disaster management strategies, regulatory standards may evolve. Test facilities must stay current with these regulations to ensure compliance and reliability.

Based on these needs, new capabilities in the test facilities could be suggested to enhance the rigor of disaster management certification processes:

- Disaster-specific simulation modelling – The development of advanced simulation models tailored to specific disaster scenarios, such as earthquake, wildfires, or oil-spill at the sea. These simulations serve as rigorous testing grounds for evaluating the efficacy of disaster management technologies and strategies.
- IoT Integration verification protocols – The establishment of comprehensive testing protocols aimed at assessing the seamless integration of IoT devices and sensor networks within disaster management infrastructures. This verification process ensures the reliability and cohesiveness of data collection, communication, and response mechanisms during crisis situations.
- AI evaluation framework – The formulation of comprehensive evaluation frameworks intended for examining AI-powered disaster prediction models and decision support systems. This encompasses the assessment of accuracy, reliability, and adaptability to dynamically changing disaster conditions.
- Blockchain resilience validation – The development of methodologies to ascertain the resilience of blockchain-based disaster data repositories and sharing platforms. This thorough validation process ensures data integrity and security even during chaotic disasters.

- Human-Machine interface usability and efficacy assessment – The establishment of testing methodologies designed to evaluate the usability and effectiveness of human-machine interfaces, especially in high-stress disaster scenarios. These assessments are facilitated through the utilization of virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) testing environments.
- Autonomous disaster response system testing – The formulation of testing criteria and benchmarks for evaluating autonomous disaster response systems, including UAV, UGV, USV, and robots. This evaluation entails assessing their navigational capabilities within disaster-stricken environments and their efficacy in delivering aid.
- Multi-modal communication systems evaluation – The development of standardized protocols for the evaluation of multi-modal communication systems, encompassing satellite communication, 5G networks, and mesh networking. The objective is to ensure uninterrupted and reliable communication channels throughout disaster scenarios.
- Remote sensing technology validation – The comprehensive evaluation of remote sensing technologies, such as satellite imaging and drones, for their utility in disaster reconnaissance, damage assessment, and resource allocation.
- Cybersecurity stress testing – The rigorous examination of cybersecurity measures through stress testing procedures to identify vulnerabilities within disaster management systems and to gauge their resilience against potential cyberattacks during crisis conditions.
- Cross-border coordination simulations – The creation of simulation scenarios aimed at evaluating the efficacy of cross-border coordination and communication during disaster response efforts, thereby identifying areas for enhancement and refinement.
- Disaster data analytics capability – The development of advanced data analytics capabilities geared towards processing and dissecting vast datasets generated during disaster events. This analytical proficiency enhances decision-making and resource allocation during crisis management.
- Resilience certification standards – The formulation of certification standards with a specific focus on the resilience of disaster management systems and technologies under adverse conditions. This certification ensures the continued functionality of these systems even in situations where critical infrastructure may be compromised.

While these suggested new capabilities primarily focus on enhancing disaster management and certification processes, their careful implementation can also contribute to sustainability by minimizing the environmental impact of disaster responses. For example, advanced data analytics can lead to more efficient resource allocation, reducing waste and environmental strain, while autonomous response systems can help minimize risks to human responders in environmentally sensitive areas.

6.3.3. Enhancing sustainability in certification schemes through joint usage of test laboratories

As industries face growing pressure to demonstrate environmental responsibility without compromising quality and safety, the integration of joint laboratory usage emerges as an innovative solution. Using test laboratories collaboratively offers the benefits of sharing resources, expertise, and infrastructure to conduct tests, experiments, and evaluations needed for certification or regulatory compliance.

While there are collaborative efforts in disaster management, there is a lack of cooperation specifically when it comes to test facilities within the certification process. There are potential benefits of introducing joint usage of test facilities in disaster management certification.

Shared use of testing facilities mitigates the need for redundant investments in equipment and infrastructure. This may lead to significant cost savings and efficient utilization of resources across multiple organizations. In addition, collaboration fosters the exchange of best practices, insights, and innovation. Different organizations bring diverse perspectives, leading to enhanced testing methodologies and improved disaster management solutions. Moreover, collaboration encourages the development of unified standards and protocols that streamline certification across organizations. The harmonization ensures consistent quality and performance in disaster management solutions.

In the aviation industry, aircraft must undergo rigorous testing and certification processes to ensure they meet safety and performance standards set by regulatory authorities like the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) in the United States or the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) in Europe. An example of collaborative test facility usage is the International Consortium of Aeronautical Test Sites (ICATS)¹⁶¹, which aims to support the industry by enabling the development, testing, and eventual certification of UAS/RPAS for operation in non-segregated airspace, aligning with the regulations set forth by their respective governing bodies.

In the case of drones, required tests may vary depending on the type and intended use of the drone. Some examples of the tests are as follows:

- **Environmental test**
To evaluate the drone's resistance to various weather conditions such as rain, wind, temperature extremes, and humidity
- **Radio frequency test**
To ensure that the drone's wireless communication systems comply with relevant standards and regulations for electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) and radio equipment
- **Mechanical test**
To evaluate their durability and strength, such as drop test, vibration test, and impact test
- **Battery test**
To evaluate the safety and performance of the drone's battery system, including its capacity, charging and discharging characteristics, and resistance to overcharging or overheating
- **Flight test**
To assess the drone's flight characteristics and performance under various conditions, such as altitude, speed, wind, and weather conditions

Drone testing facilities, especially those equipped for comprehensive environmental, mechanical, and flight testing, can be expensive to establish and maintain. By sharing these facilities, drone manufacturers, researchers, and regulatory bodies can significantly reduce their individual costs. In addition, the drones need to comply with safety and regulatory standards. Joint facilities can help ensure that all drones undergo consistent and standardized testing procedures, making it easier to meet regulatory requirements. Furthermore, Joint facilities can

¹⁶¹ <https://icatestsites.wordpress.com/about/>

bring together experts from various fields, such as aerospace engineering, robotics, and telecommunications, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and innovation.

ATLAS(Air Traffic Laboratory for Advanced unmanned Systems)¹⁶² is a test flight centre which offers the international aerospace community and aerodrome equipped with excellent technological-scientific facilities and airspace ideally suited to the development of experimental flights with unmanned aerial vehicles. ATLAS offers a controlled environment and segregated airspace for testing, simulations, and validation of technologies related to UAVs, including aspects such as air traffic management (ATM), navigation technologies, monitoring, certification, and pilot/operator qualification. While ATLAS itself may not be a collaboration of test facilities, it serves as a collaborative space for multiple stakeholders to work together on UAV-related research and technology development.

Collaboration between oil spill test facilities offers practical solutions to specific challenges by leveraging the strengths of each facility, sharing resources, expertise, and knowledge, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of oil spill research and response efforts:

- Simulating realistic environmental conditions, including wave patterns, temperature, and salinity, is difficult and often beyond the capabilities of a single facility. Collaboration allows facilities to specialize in replicating specific environmental aspects. For example, one facility may focus on wave simulations, while another concentrates on water temperature control. Combining these specialized capabilities results in more accurate and comprehensive testing environments.
- Maintaining and upgrading test facilities can be costly, and securing funding is an ongoing challenge. Collaborative efforts enable facilities to share financial burdens. They can jointly apply for grants and pool resources for equipment upgrades and maintenance, ensuring sustainability.
- Oil spill research is multidisciplinary and may require specialized knowledge. Collaborative teams can involve experts from various disciplines. Facilities can focus on their areas of expertise and collaborate with others to address interdisciplinary challenges effectively.
- Effective communication and coordination are important but can be hindered by institutional barriers. Collaboration can foster communication and coordination. Regular meetings, shared resources, and collaborative research efforts break down barriers and promote seamless communication among facilities and stakeholders.

In the context of cybersecurity, while physical test facilities play a role in cybersecurity research and testing, the primary advantage of joint usage in this field may be the collaborative sharing of data, threat intelligence, and expertise. These advantages enhance the ability of organizations and communities to detect, respond to, and defend against threats effectively. This collective approach fosters a sense of community resilience and preparedness, contributing to the overall cybersecurity posture and disaster resilience of the industry and society.

The usage of two or more labs working together for certification and information sharing can be highly beneficial. For instance, in the context of disaster response technology certification, two specialized labs come together to enhance disaster management capabilities. Lab A, specializing in drone and aerial technology testing, collaborates with Lab B, which focuses on communication and networking equipment for disaster response. Together, they embark on joint testing

¹⁶² <https://atlascenter.aero/en/>

endeavours, simulating real disaster scenarios to evaluate the effectiveness of drone communications systems in relaying vital information to ground stations. Furthermore, this partnership extends to the certification of interoperability between communication equipment from Lab B and drones and sensors from Lab A, ensuring seamless integration of technologies. Additionally, the labs work collaboratively to establish robust information sharing protocols, facilitating the exchange of critical data between aerial assets and ground communication systems, ultimately enhancing disaster response and management efforts.

7. Gaps and opportunities

In this deliverable, existing certification scheme and initiatives are explored to identify gaps and challenges in the certification for the first aid response enablers. Afterward, opportunities are suggested to prompt sustainable certification, accreditation and homogeneity assessment.

7.1. Technologies and equipment for emergency response

The following table shows the gaps detected during the information compilation of the task regarding the technologies and equipment for emergency response:

Identification of gaps			
Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G3.5-1	Lack of information about dedicated standard and certification of the equipment/system for the FRs	Professional experience	Even in case of the existing equipment/system for the FRs, it is not easy to identify which laws, standards and certification this equipment/system are in compliance with
G3.5-2	Lack of laws, standards and certification for novel technology	Professional experience	Advanced technologies for the FRs have been actively developed. In case of novel technology (e.g., Unmanned Surface Vehicle, Unmanned Ground Vehicle, wearable, etc.), there is a lack of relevant laws and standards. Accordingly, certification is also lacking.
G3.5-3	Lack of information on relevant certification for the first response enablers	Professional experience	It is not clear whether specific certification is needed or not for the first response enablers
G3.5-4	Lack of harmonized certification scheme for the first response enablers	Professional experience	The UCPM provides the assessment tool for the certification, but it may not sufficiently cover the novel technologies
G3.5-5	Difficult to introduce the common certification scheme the first response enablers	Professional experience	The equipment/system for the FRs are quite diverse in technology, concept of operation, application area and performance, so it is difficult to identify common technical/functional requirements for the common certification scheme
G3.5-6	Challenges from complex systems for the first responders	Professional experience	The certification scheme needs to cover not only the product itself but also software, data protection and cybersecurity certification

Identification of gaps			
Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G3.5-7	Necessity of new evaluation procedure and modifications on the evaluation facilities	Professional experience	As novel technologies have been introduced in the emergency response, new evaluation procedure and modifications on the evaluation facilities are necessary
G3.5-8	The accreditation for new evaluation facilities needs to be considered	Professional experience	If new evaluation facilities are introduced in the certification process, it needs to be accredited by the accreditation body
G3.5-9	Need to establish the technical and functional requirement for first response enablers	Professional experience	In the certification process, to define the requirements to be satisfied is important. Especially, to define necessary requirements should take precedence for novel technologies
G3.5-10	Lack of communication channel between stakeholders in certification process	Professional experience	There are several information sharing programs in UCPM, but there is not much information about the certification
G3.5-11	Difficulties to implement the data protection certification mechanism under article 42 GDPR	Professional experience	GDPR entered into application on May 25th 2018 but the concrete application of article 42 is still missing
G3.5-12	Complex technology training	Professional experience	Acquiring the necessary skills to mitigate new risks requires the use of advanced technology
G3.5-13	Cybersecurity recertification system may slow down upgrades	Literature	software providers may be reluctant to produce regular updates for their products/systems because of the time/cost of the recertification process
G3.5-14	The proposed Act on AI is focussed for high risk AI only	Literature	Medium and lower risk AI systems have only limited mandatory information duties.
G3.5-15	SAR not prepared to keep information registered	Professional experience	It necessary to recover all information from SAR after some malfunction or something similar
G3.5-16	Little cooperation and joint usage of test facilities	Professional experience	Test labs have their own facilities and operate as businesses, so there might be a lack of interest for joint usage and cooperation
G3.5-17	Lack of standardized cybersecurity criteria and best practices for certification		This may lead to inconsistencies in evaluating the security of emerging technologies, making it difficult to ensure a uniform level of cybersecurity

Identification of gaps			
Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G3.5-18	Interoperability and integration security		Certification schemes should account for the security aspects of integrating emerging technologies with existing systems, ensuring that the integration doesn't introduce new vulnerabilities or compromise the security of connected systems
G3.5-19	Need a more thorough risk assessment		Traditional certification processes often focus on static assessments. In the context of cybersecurity, there's a gap in incorporating dynamic risk assessment to evaluate the technology's resilience to evolving threats.
G3.5-20	Responding to rapid Technological Advancements		The certification process needs to address the challenge of keeping up with the rapid advancements in technology, ensuring that new equipment and systems are evaluated against the latest standards

Table 9 - Gaps related to certification of technologies and equipment for emergency response

G3.5-1: Lack of information about dedicated standard and certification for the equipment/system for the first responders

- While reviewing the certification for the SAR equipment, one of the challenges is checking for existence of relevant laws and standard
- The certification scheme is built based on the laws and standards, so identification of the relevant regulations and standards is essential
- Even for the existing SAR equipment and system, it is difficult to identify which laws and standards are complied with this SAR equipment/system
- Taking the drone as an example, there are regulations and standards for the drone, but it is undefined whether these regulations and standards are adequate in disaster situations or not
- The current market situation is challenging in terms of certification costs and the amount of paperwork required. There is a lack of clarity in identifying the roles and tasks required for the different certification processes, which can increase certification costs by increasing working hours, retesting fees and referral fees within the certification procedure.

G3.5-2: Lack of actual laws and standards for novel technology

- Advanced technologies for the first responders have been actively developed
- In case of novel technology (e.g., Unmanned Surface Vehicle, Unmanned Ground Vehicle, wearable, etc.), there is no laws and standards yet

- In the initiative projects, the certification process could not be carried out because the certification is applicable when there is a known standard or specification that is either nationally or internationally recognised
- Instead of the certification, they go through the validation process. It involves testing a product to ensure that it meets a pre-determined specification. The validation will eventually lead to the certification

G3.5-3: Lack of information about which certification should be obtained

- Many products require CE mark before they can be sold in the EU, and CE mark is obligatory depending on the products
- In case of the equipment for the FRs, it is not clear whether specific certification other than CE mark is needed or not
- There are dependencies between equipment and its use that can mean different CE Mark requirements: A smartwatch used for fitness purposes does not serve as medical purpose and does not require certification under Medical Devices Regulation (MDR). However, if the intended purpose is to diagnose or monitor a disease, the device is classified as a medical device and requires certification under MDR.

G3.5-4: Lack of harmonized certification scheme for the equipment/system for the FRs

- In UCPM, there is assessment tool to be used for certifying resources in the European Civil Protection Pool
- In this assessment tool, novel technologies (include unmanned system) are not considered

G3.5-5: Difficulty in establishing harmonized certification scheme for the equipment/system for the first responders

- There are various equipment and system for the first responders, so harmonisation of certification scheme is a complex task
- One of important aspects is to maintain the flexibility in harmonized certification scheme to account for different technologies and means of operation

G3.5-6 Challenges from complex systems for the first responders

- One of the objectives for certification is to reduce risk through the adequate conformity assessment and evaluation
- For instance, in order to enhance safety and build trust in Unmanned system (UAVs, UGVs, USVs, etc.), not only product itself but also software quality and operating skills should be thoroughly evaluated
- In addition, some acceptable level of security and privacy should be achieved based on the regulations and the standards.
- In this context, it is important to establish customized criteria for the system in disaster situations

G3.5-7: new evaluation procedure and modifications on the evaluation facilities are necessary

- As novel technologies have been introduced in the emergency response, new evaluation procedure and modifications on the evaluation facilities are necessary

G3.5-8: The accreditation for new evaluation facilities needs to be considered

- The evaluation facilities (e.g., test laboratories) need to be accredited by the accreditation body to ensure that the evaluation facilities have the technical capacity to perform their duties.
- If new evaluation facilities are introduced in the certification process, it needs to be accredited by the accreditation body

G3.5-9: Need to establish the technical and functional requirement for first response enablers

- The certification demonstrates that the subject to be certified have been evaluated to show compliance with necessary safety or performance requirements
- To define the requirements to be satisfied is essential in the certification process
- Especially, it is important for the novel technologies

G3.5-10: Lack of communication channel between stakeholders in certification process

- The Union Civil Protection Knowledge Network provides several programs to share knowledge among different experts and to connect local and international stakeholders, governmental and non-governmental organisations, political, scientific, and technical experts
- However, sharing information about the certification is insufficient

G3.5-11: Difficulties to implement the data protection certification mechanism under article 42 GDPR

- GDPR entered into application on May 25th 2018, but certification bodies have still to be identified or have still to start developing certification procedures
- Article 42 does not provide mechanisms of consistency with existing certification mechanisms.

G3.5-12: Use of advanced technological equipment

- High training time in new devices and technologies with previous technological skills
- Consistent training across all facilities that require this new competency

G3.5-13: Cybersecurity recertification system may slow down upgrades

- Software updates to improve the security of products/systems are of vital importance, as technology is advancing at a rapid pace. The cyber security recertification system must be sufficiently agile and affordable to encourage software vendors to recertify their updated systems and ensure such updates with a corresponding recertification.

G3.5-14: The proposed Act on AI is focussed for high risk AI only

- Due to the strong divergence of Member States' views on AI, the proposed EC Act of AI doesn't introduce voluntary certification schemes for medium and low risk AI systems, as it was done in the GDPR and the European Cyber Security Act. (Kees Stuurman, 2022)

G3.5-15: Lose information after malfunction

- The new technological solutions are characterized by the advanced treatment of information, at the functionality level as well as that of the person receiving safety and rescue. These technological solutions must have in mind the need to safeguard vital

and operational information after any incident, be it fortuitous or due to human causes.

G3.5-16: Little cooperation between test facilities

- Test labs have their own facilities and operate as businesses, so there might be a lack of interest for joint usage and cooperation

G3.5-17: Lack of standardized cybersecurity criteria and best practices for certification

- This gap underscores the absence of universally accepted and well-defined criteria that guide the evaluation of cybersecurity measures for various technologies or systems
- Without standardized cybersecurity criteria, different certification bodies or organizations may use varying benchmarks, leading to inconsistencies in evaluating the security posture of emerging technologies, products, or services. This lack of consistency can create confusion and hinder the comparability of certified solutions.

G3.5-18: Interoperability and integration security

- This gap is a crucial consideration in the certification process, particularly when emerging technologies are being integrated into existing system.
- To prevent unintended consequences that might compromise the effectiveness, safety, or security of the entire system, a thorough certification process in this regard contributes to a more robust and resilient emergency response ecosystem.

G3.5-19: Need a more thorough risk assessment

- Dynamic risk assessment is needed to continuously and adaptively assess risks as they evolve, particularly in the context of cybersecurity.
- Traditional certification schemes tend to follow static assessments. These assessments are often conducted at a specific point in time, typically during the initial evaluation of a technology or system. While static assessments provide valuable insights into the security posture of a system at a given moment, they may fall short when it comes to addressing the dynamic nature of cybersecurity threats.

G3.5-20: Responding to rapid Technological Advancements

- Emerging technologies evolve quickly, and certification schemes must be able to adapt to new security threats, vulnerabilities, and best practices, ensuring that certified technologies remain secure as they progress.

The following table summarizes the opportunities detected during the information compilation of the task regarding the technologies and equipment for emergency response:

Opportunities				
Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities				
ID	Related gaps	Opportunity name	Type of input	Justification
OP3.5-1	G3.5-1	Collect, organize and present certification requirements for SAR equipment	Professional experience, rules and regulations	Technology providers need easy access to certification requirements for SAR equipment and efficient certification procedures to innovate and get equipment to market quicker
OP3.5-2	G3.5-1	Gathering the laws and standards information related to first aid response enablers in database	Professional experience	The laws and standards are essential to the certification, so finding the relevant laws and standards is a fundamental and important task in the certification process
OP3.5-3	G3.5-1	Demonstrate that the application of the existing regulation/certification scheme to novel technologies is adequate	Professional experience	Until the regulations and standards are established, manufacturers may apply relevant existing laws/standards/certification to their new product. So, it is necessary to evaluate that existing ones are enough
OP3.5-4	G3.5-10	Arrange communication channel between stakeholders in the certification process	Professional experience	In order to increase efficiency, the stakeholders in the certification process need to communicate each other from the beginning of the development
OP3.5-5	G3.5-10	Establish online information sharing site	Professional experience	A positive effect can be expected if all stakeholders can easily access to the information about the certification
OP3.5-6	G3.5-9	Identify that requirements of the first aid response enabler and organize the data for further reference	Professional experience	The evaluation procedures and criteria vary according to the enablers. It would be useful if there is well organized requirements according to the enablers
OP3.5-7	G3.5-7	Suggest customized conformity assessment methodology for SAR	Professional experience	From the economic aspects, the utilization of customized conformity assessment methodologies (e.g., simulation, virtual reality) could save

Opportunities				
Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities				
ID	Related gaps	Opportunity name	Type of input	Justification
		equipment/system in order to save time and cost		expenditure in the certification process
OP3.5-8	G3.5-6, G3.5-7	Suggest measures for that conformity assessment can be carried out along with development process	Professional experience	To enhance the efficiency of the certification process, the conformity assessment needs to be carried out from the early stage of development
OP3.5-9	G3.5-2, G3.5-3	Build a database of useful information from the initiative projects for novel technologies	Professional experience	Well organized information will be useful for further reference
OP3.5-10	G3.5-12	New tested technology	Professional experience	Use of technology with experience in the field under the same context of operation
OP3.5-11	G3.5-13	Lighten the resources in cybersecurity recertification	Literature	The use of automatic tests could reduce the resources required in the cybersecurity recertification process
OP3.5-12	G3.5-14	Include medium and low risk AI certification schemes in the proposed Act on AI	Literature	The working groups for Act on AI should promote the AI certification schemes for medium and low risk AI systems, expanding the certification market
OP3.5-13	G3.5-15	Security for novel technological devices	Professional experience	Protect and recover information after some incident
OP3.5-14	G3.5-16	Possible joint usage of facilities for certification.	Professional experience	Propose mechanisms for collaboration between test facilities to get increased capacity and quicker certification process
OP3.5-15	G3.5-17	Collaboration between stakeholders related to cybersecurity		Through collaboration between cybersecurity experts, technology developers, regulatory bodies, and certification organizations, robust, up-to-date, and universally recognized cybersecurity criteria for certification can be established

Opportunities				
Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities				
ID	Related gaps	Opportunity name	Type of input	Justification
OP3.5-16	G3.5-18	Data flow and interfaces		Certification scheme can consider the security of data flows and interfaces between the new technology and existing systems
OP3.5-17	G3.5-18 and 19	A thorough Risk assessment		A comprehensive risk assessment could identify potential security risks when new technologies interface with legacy systems

Table 10 - Opportunities related to certification of technologies and equipment for emergency response

OP3.5-1: Based on feedback from companies developing and producing SAR related products, one reoccurring concern was the difficulty to identify which standards to certify the products against. Valuable time could be lost by spending time and resources on certification that possibly are not necessary or realising too late in the development that a certain certification is required. An opportunity would be to offer an updated and maintained certification tool that guides the developers through the certification process for different SAR equipment and systems.

OP3.5-2: The laws and standards are essential to the certification, so finding the relevant laws and standards are fundamental and important task. Efficiencies could be made if the information related to first aid response enablers are gathered systematically in database.

OP3.5-3: It takes a long time to establish new regulation and standard for novel technologies. Naturally, this sets back the establishment of the certification scheme. Until the regulation and standard are established, manufacturers may apply relevant existing laws/standards/certification to their new product. In this case, it needs to be investigated that whether the application of the existing one is adequate or not. The result of this investigation could be referenced in the establishment of new certification scheme later. In this process, if existing resources are utilized for the new certification, then the sustainability is increased.

OP3.5-4: Even though there is no certification scheme for the novel technologies until the end of the development, the planning of the certification should start early because certification is a complicate process that involves products design and regulation/standard. In order to increase efficiency, the stakeholders in the certification process need to communicate each other from the beginning of the development.

OP3.5-5: Even there are several information sharing programs in UCPM (see section 5.4.1.3), finding information about the certification is not easy. It would be useful to establish an easy-to-access online community that is open to public.

OP3.5-6: For reliable evaluation, the evaluation procedures need to be specified objective way based on the clearly established criteria. These criteria are identified in accordance with the requirements to be met. It would be useful if there are well organized requirements according to the enablers.

OP3.5-7: As novel technologies are introduced in the first responder enablers, new conformity assessment methodologies are needed. In addition, from the economic aspects, the utilization of customized conformity assessment methodologies (e.g., simulation, virtual reality) could save expenditure in the certification process.

OP3.5-8: To enhance the efficiency of the certification process, the conformity assessment needs to be carried out from the early stage of development

OP3.5-9: There are several initiative projects related to the novel technologies for the first responders. They did not directly deal with the certification, but there is useful information for further reference in the certification process such as requirements to be satisfied in emergency response, users' needs, validation methodologies for the novel technologies, etc. Resources and time could be saved by using the database.

OP3.5-10: The constant development of technology is motivated by the response to the new needs identified in risk management, to mitigate or eliminate them. For commissioning and deployment in operation / training, it is considered necessary to previously have the relevant international certificates and that the facilities and their personnel have the recognized skills for their use.

OP3.5-11: To encourage software vendors to update and recertify their products/systems from a cybersecurity point of view, the recertification process should use automated testing to lighten the resources dedicated to the process. (J. L. Hernandez-Ramos, Jan.-Feb. 2021)

OP3.5-12: AI systems have a potentially serious impact on fundamental rights. The proposed EC Act on AI leaves a wide range of AI-systems unregulated concerning this risks. There is an opportunity to explore these lower AI certification schemes to expand the market related to certification in this area and contributing to promote what EC calls an "ecosystem of trust".

OP3.5-13: Have security elements that prevent leakage of any type of information to unrecognized people and/or devices. It is recommended to have an information storage of all types of attempts to access the device.

OP3.5-14: Possible joint usage of facilities for certification. As EC points out on the TEFs FAQ webpage¹⁶³, it is expected to connect TEFs with Data Spaces to enable joint collaboration between the two mechanisms. To guarantee security between certificates, it is convenient to apply standards such as ISO 17090:2021 Health informatics — Public key infrastructure; where a scheme of interoperability requirements is provided to establish a secure communication of health information based on digital certificates.

OP3.5-15: To build a robust cybersecurity framework, it requires collaboration among technology developers, cybersecurity experts, regulatory bodies, and end-users to create effective and resilient cybersecurity measures.

OP3.5-16: It is important to verify that data exchanged between components is encrypted, authenticated, and protected against tampering or interception.

OP3.5-17: A thorough risk assessment is necessary to uncover potential security concerns when integrating new technologies with legacy systems. The certification scheme should evaluate the

¹⁶³ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/faqs/testing-and-experimentation-facilities-tefs-questions-and-answers>

impact of integration on data integrity, confidentiality, availability, and overall system resilience. In addition, dynamic risk assessment in the context of cybersecurity ensures that technology remains resilient to evolving threats by recognizing the need for continuous evaluation and adaptation, thus enhancing the overall security posture of systems and networks.

7.2. Operation for emergency response

The following tables show the gaps and opportunities detected during the information compilation of the task regarding the operation for emergency response:

Identification of gaps			
Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G3.5-21	EU Drone regulations leaves it up to the national state to specify regulations for using drones in disaster response	EU legislation	Could create a problem in cross border situations if there are different national requirements
G3.5-22	Required specific experience and expertise to operate unmanned system	Professional experience	A certification scheme that verifies the ability to operate complex unmanned systems is needed
G3.5-23	There is no certification for operating UAVs in UCPM	literature	UAVs have started to be actively used in the disaster situation, but a certification scheme has not been established yet
G3.5-24	Identification of new competencies	Professional experience	Development of new skills needed to respond to new risks
G3.5-25	Standardization operation procedures	Professional experience	SOPs Development to unify procedures
G3.5-26	Lack of common European certification for pre-hospital emergency medical personnel	Literature	Efficient cross-border cooperation requires medical staff with comparable knowledge and comparable services provided between countries, but their education varies drastically within European countries
G3.5-27	Training and Qualification		There's need for certification schemes and standards to ensure that FRs are adequately trained and qualified to operate capabilities effectively, especially in high-stress situations
G3.5-28	Budget Constraints		Each organization and agency involved in first aid response may have budget limitations, and may be in a different economic situation. This may cause potential gaps in compliance.
G3.5-29	Evolving Threats		As new threats and emergency situations emerge, there may be a challenge in

Identification of gaps			
Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			adapting the certification criteria to address these evolving scenarios
G3.5-30	Cross-disciplinary Knowledge		Effective certification scheme of emerging technologies requires expertise from various disciplines, including technology, disaster management, ethics, and public safety. A gap may exist in bringing together these diverse knowledge area.
G3.5-31	Long-term viability		Some emerging technologies may become obsolete quickly, while others could have long-term value. The certification scheme should address the balance between encouraging innovation and ensuring that certified technologies remain relevant over time
G3.5-32	Global consistency		Given that disasters can have international implications, achieving global consistency in certification/standard for emerging disaster management technologies can be challenging due to varying regulatory environments and cultural considerations.
G3.5-33	Human factors in cybersecurity		Some certification schemes might overlook the human factors in cybersecurity, including user training, secure development practices, and incident response readiness, all of which are crucial for a comprehensive security posture.
G3.5-34	Training and skill updates		The certification scheme should facilitate ongoing training and skill updates for first responders. Ensuring that certified responders stay current with best practices and the latest techniques is crucial for effective emergency response.
G3.5-35	Legal and liability considerations for certified FRs		Establishing clear guidelines on legal responsibilities, liabilities, and insurance aspects for certified first responders during emergency operations is essential to prevent legal hurdles in cross-border operations

Table 11 - Gaps related to certification of operation in emergency response

G3.5-21: The EU has adopted a legislative package. A basic regulation sets the main rules regarding the design, production, maintenance, certification and operation of unmanned aircraft. This EU framework does not apply to drones carrying out police, search and rescue, firefighting, border control and coastguard or similar activities and services undertaken in the public interest. The national state needs to specify regulations for using drones in disaster response.

G3.5-22: In an unmanned system, the skill of the operator is one of the important factors. Comprehensive understanding (communication system, cyber security, etc.) of the system is required. It is necessary to establish the minimum qualifications required for them and to evaluate them.

G3.5-23: There is a lack on the protocols such as certification, training, deployment, flight operations and integration. It is considered that this situation is not sustainable with a deficit of experience and associated misunderstanding of the legislation potentially leading to unacceptable risks being created within the UCPM by allowing the use of UAV in emergency response context.

G3.5-24: The development of new technologies requires a constant update of the training and requirements of the staff, being increasingly demanding and transversal. The new technologies must consider the skills of the emergency and rescue teams to create their procedures for use, maintenance and learning. Consequently, it can be a barrier in the homogenization of the development of necessary competencies between countries under the same identification of risks. On other hand, the use of different drone vehicles in the operations could be a barrier which make slow preparation of the resources.

G3.5-25: Each professional team needs to unify procedures to work well like a team in a border scenario. It's important to know different roles, responsibilities, communications and resources in each moment of the operations.

G3.5-26: Cross-border co-operation in multi-casualty accidents, requires pre-hospital emergency medical personnel to have comparable knowledge and to provide comparable services between countries, but their education varies drastically within European countries. Although there are initiatives to standardise and certify a common classification within Europe (WHO EMT classification and certification process and UCPM pool for EMTs), these staff are only involved when WHO/UCPM mechanisms are activated. Moreover, certification is at the organisational level, not at the individual level.

G3.5-27: This gap highlights the importance of having comprehensive certification schemes specifically focused on training FRs to effectively operate capabilities, especially in high-stress emergency situations. The certification scheme can ensure that FRs are well-prepared to handle the capabilities (include new technologies) effectively, enhancing their ability to save lives and manage emergencies, even in the most challenging and stressful situations

G3.5-28: Some emerging technologies can be expensive to implement and maintain, and many disaster management agencies may have limited budgets. Like any certification procedure, certifying requires resources. It needs to be considered that the process is affordable and accessible, especially for smaller technology providers or disaster management agencies with limited budgets.

G3.5-29: In the context of cybersecurity, evolving threats refer to the continually changing and adaptive tactics used by cybercriminals and malicious actors to exploit vulnerabilities in digital systems, networks, and software. As cybersecurity threats evolve, the value of maintaining a dynamic and up-to-date certification scheme becomes evident.

G3.5-30: Creating a robust certification framework for emerging technologies demands the collective knowledge of experts from a variety of fields, including technology, disaster management, ethics, and public safety. Potential challenges may arise when trying to harmonize these distinct knowledge domains.

G3.5-31: Finding the right balance between promoting innovation and ensuring long-term relevance is important. To foster innovation, certification scheme should acknowledge the ever-changing nature of emerging technologies. This can be achieved through adaptable criteria that permit swift updates or re-evaluation of certified technologies as they advance.

G3.5-32: Achieving global consistency in certification and standards for disaster management technologies is a complex task due to the diverse regulatory environments, cultural considerations, and legal frameworks present around the world. It requires careful navigation of these challenges while prioritizing the development of technology solutions that are effective, adaptable, and sensitive to local needs and conditions. International collaboration and a commitment to harmonization are essential for addressing these challenges and promoting global resilience in the face of disasters.

G3.5-33: For effective cybersecurity certification, the full spectrum of human factors, secure development practices, and incident response readiness need to be considered. Overlooking these aspects can lead to an incomplete understanding of an organization's cybersecurity posture and potentially leave critical vulnerabilities unaddressed.

G3.5-34: The certification scheme for first responders is important in maintaining and enhancing the effectiveness of emergency response teams. Beyond simply certifying individuals for their initial training and skills, it should be designed to encourage and support continuous learning and skill development throughout their careers.

G3.5-35: Harmonization of guidelines for legal responsibilities, liabilities, and insurance aspects for certified first responders during cross-border emergency operations is crucial to ensure a seamless and legally compliant response. The harmonized guidelines may ensure that responders understand their roles, authorities, and their legal duties, regardless of where the emergency occurs.

Opportunities				
Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities				
ID	Related gaps	Opportunity name	Type of input	Justification
OP3.5-18	G3.5-22	Harmonize certification requirements for DRONE operation in disaster response between national states	Professional experience, rules and regulations	Clarity is needed for drone operators in cross-border situations
OP3.5-19	G3.5-25, G3.5-23	Improve staff skill	Professional experience	Use correctly equipment and improve teamwork
OP3.5-20	G3.5-24	Harmonization of procedures and operations	Professional experience	Better effectiveness related with international border scenario
OP3.5-21	-	Perform international test with the use cases and technology solutions built on Valkyries	Professional experience	It will improve the overall performance of the results with the fine-tuning of ideas and technological proposals through the test
OP3.5-22	G3.5-25	European certification for pre-hospital emergency medical personnel	Literature	The creation of a common European certificate for pre-hospital emergency medical personnel would make cross-border cooperation more efficient
OP3.5-23	-	New certification schemes are business opportunity for CABs	Professional experience	As new certification schemes emerge, the portfolio of services and tools that CABs can offer is expanding
OP3.5-24	G3.5-27	Customized Training programs that can be used in certification procedure		Develop training programs tailored to the specific technologies that FRs will be using.
OP3.5-25	G3.5-27	Utilize new capabilities		Incorporate new capabilities that mimic the high-stress environments FRs may face. It allows FRs to practice using the

Opportunities				
Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities				
ID	Related gaps	Opportunity name	Type of input	Justification
				technology under pressure, improving their effectiveness and decision-making skills
OP3.5-26	G3.5-27	Include Hands-on Training in the certification procedure for FRs		Practical experiences build confidence and helps FRs become familiar with the new technologies
OP3.5-27	G3.5-27	Incorporating continuous learning into the certification scheme for FRs		“continuous learning” is an essential aspect of ensuring that FRs remain proficient in using new technologies and are prepared to handle evolving challenges in emergency situations
OP3.5-28	G3.5-27	Establishing consistent training and qualification requirements for FRs across different regions		Standardization ensures that all FRs meet a uniform level of expertise, regardless of their deployment location
OP3.5-29	G3.5-28	Cost-effective certification		Find cost-effective strategies that provide significant value in terms of skills, knowledge, and improved capabilities while aligning with limited budgets
OP3.5-30	G3.5-29	Post-certification monitoring		Ongoing monitoring may ensure that certified enablers remain reliable and safe for use in emergency situations.
OP3.5-31	G3.5-30	Interdisciplinary training programs		Develop interdisciplinary training programs and educational courses that bring together experts from technology, disaster management, ethics, public safety, and other relevant fields.

Opportunities				
Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities				
ID	Related gaps	Opportunity name	Type of input	Justification
OP3.5-32	G3.5-30	Interdisciplinary advisory committees		Establish advisory committees composed of experts from different fields to provide guidance to certification bodies.
OP3.5-33	G3.5-30	Ethical and social impact assessments		Integrate ethical and social impact assessments into the certification process. This involves evaluating not only the technical aspects of a technology but also its potential ethical, legal, and societal consequences.
OP3.5-34	G3.5-31	Flexible certification criteria		Develop certification criteria that are adaptable and can be updated as technologies evolve.
OP3.5-35	G3.5-32	International cooperation and harmonization		Dedicated forums and working groups can be established to foster international partnerships and collaborations among governments, regulatory bodies, and relevant international organization, with the aim of aligning disaster management technology standards.
OP3.5-36	G3.5-33	Integrate Human-centric training and awareness		Develop and implement regular cybersecurity training and awareness programs for end-users. Focus on educating them about recognizing and mitigating security threats, including phishing, social engineering, and safe online behavior.
OP3.5-37	G3.5-34	Implementing lifelong learning, ongoing assessment, and a supportive organizational culture in		Implement mandatory continuing education requirements for first responders to ensure that they stay up-to-date with the latest techniques, technologies, and

Opportunities				
Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities				
ID	Related gaps	Opportunity name	Type of input	Justification
		certification scheme		best practices in emergency response.
OP3.5-38	G3.5-35	Creating effective harmonized guidelines for certified FRs during cross-border emergency operations		Effective harmonized guidelines are essential for promoting seamless and legally compliant cross-border emergency response. It facilitates cooperation, reduce legal uncertainties, and enhance the overall effectiveness of emergency operations, ensuring the safety and well-being of both FRs and affected communities.

Table 12 - Opportunities related to certification of operation in emergency response

OP3.5-18: Interoperability is important when the first responders cooperate with each other in cross-border disaster situations. Harmonisation of certification requirements for drone operation could increase the interoperability in cross-border disaster situations.

OP3.5-19: Have professional staff with high technological qualifications to be able to use new solutions within an international border context. Training in these solutions provides an additional quality to the personnel involved in this type of activity, being also useful in a national or local context.

OP3.5-20: It's necessary working with same procedures across international borders. Also, all devices used need to have same basis functions and all participants need to know how to proceed with them.

OP3.5-21: Perform test international with the necessary properties for use cases and technology solutions built on Valkyries. It will improve the overall performance of the results with the fine-tuning of ideas and technological proposals

OP3.5-22: Common certification of pre-hospital emergency medical personnel would be a mechanism to establish, maintain trust between stakeholders and increase the effectiveness of cross-border cooperation in mass casualty incidents, as it would ensure comparable expertise and operation between countries. Indeed, a common certification process is a key element to ensure the quality of European response capabilities. A certification system for pre-hospital emergency medical personnel should be developed at European level, based on the WHO EMT classification and focusing on people.

OP3.5-23: The new certification schemes represent a business opportunity for CABs, as they can expand their service portfolio and develop new assessment tools and services.

OP3.5-24: Tailored training programs should cover the operation, maintenance, troubleshooting, and safety protocols for each technology.

OP3.5-25: New capabilities that can be used in the certification procedure for the FRs include: realistic simulation, Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), Mixed Reality (MR).

OP3.5-26: Incorporating hands-on training into the certification procedure ensures that first responders are not just theoretically qualified but are also genuinely prepared to utilize the technology as an essential tool in their emergency response toolkit. This practical experience empowers them to act decisively and efficiently, ultimately saving lives and minimizing the impact of disasters.

OP3.5-27: Incorporating continuous learning into the certification scheme ensures that FRs remain competent, adaptable, and resilient in the face of changing technology, regulations, and emergency scenarios, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of emergency response efforts.

OP3.5-28: Standardized training ensures that FRs develop consistent skills, knowledge, and best practices. This consistency is crucial for effective collaboration and interoperability during joint operations involving multiple agencies or FRs from different countries. Collaboration among regulatory bodies, training institutions, and regional authorities is essential to establish and maintain standardized training and qualification requirements.

OP3.5-29: To find a cost-effective certification, following strategies could be considered:

- Online training – Online options often have lower costs compared to in-person training, and they can be more flexible in terms of scheduling
- Collaboration – Collaborating with other agencies or organizations can be considered. Pooling resources can make it more cost-effective to access certification programs
- Customized training – Customized training packages (for instance, tailored contents to specific needs) can make the training more efficient and cost-effective
- Long-term planning – While there may be upfront costs, if the certification leads to improved efficiency, better disaster management, or increased funding opportunities in the long run, it can justify the initial investment

OP3.5-30: Technology and the nature of emergencies can change over time. New threats or vulnerabilities may emerge that were not initially considered during the certification process. Ongoing monitoring allows organizations to stay ahead of evolving threats, address wear and tear, incorporate user feedback, maintain compliance, continuously improve, and adapt to the changing nature of emergencies.

OP3.5-31: Developing interdisciplinary training programs and educational courses involves a holistic approach that integrates expertise from various fields, fosters collaboration, and prepares education participants to tackle the complex challenges posed by emerging technologies.

OP3.5-32: To establish effective advisory committees, experts from diverse fields relevant to the certification process may be gathered. This can include individuals with expertise in technology, ethics, public safety, disaster management, legal matters, and any other relevant domains. These committees play a crucial role in enhancing the credibility, transparency, and ethical considerations of the certification process.

OP3.5-33: By integrating comprehensive ethical and social impact assessments into the certification process, certification bodies can promote responsible and ethical technology development while safeguarding against potential harms and negative consequences for society

at large. This approach aligns with the broader goal of ensuring that emerging technologies are not only technically sound but also socially beneficial.

OP3.5-34: Regularly reviewing and revising criteria with input from experts and stakeholders helps certification bodies ensure that their assessments remain relevant, thorough, and responsive to the evolving needs and challenges of technology certification. This adaptability is crucial for maintaining the credibility and effectiveness of certification programs in a dynamic technological environment.

OP3.5-35: The establishment of dedicated forums and working groups is a proactive step in addressing the complexities of disaster management standards on an international scale. These platforms facilitate cooperation, knowledge sharing, and alignment among governments, regulatory bodies, and international organizations to ensure that disaster management technologies are effective, interoperable, and responsive to global challenges.

OP3.5-36: By integrating human-centric training and awareness into the intersection of cybersecurity certification and disaster management, organizations and communities can develop a more comprehensive and resilient approach to addressing the evolving challenges posed by cybersecurity threats and disasters.

OP3.5-37: Implementing mandatory continuing education requirements with regular training and skill assessment intervals ensures that first responders remain well-prepared and up-to-date in their field. It is a proactive approach to keep responders competent and capable of handling the ever-evolving challenges of emergency response effectively.

OP3.5-38: Well-structured and universally agreed-upon sets of rules and procedures can guide how different countries or regions work together during cross-border emergency situations. These guidelines ensure that all actions taken during an emergency response are in line with the laws and regulations of the involved jurisdictions. In addition, these guidelines can also serve as assessment criteria within certification schemes.

7.3. Concluding remarks and Insights

In this comprehensive exploration of certification schemes and operational aspects related to first aid response enablers and emergency response, we have uncovered a multitude of gaps, challenges, and opportunities that are crucial for advancing the field of emergency technology and enhancing response capabilities.

From the certification perspective, we have identified significant challenges, including the lack of dedicated standards and certifications for equipment and systems used by FRs. The absence of clear regulations and standards complicates the certification process, especially for novel technologies like drones and unmanned systems used in disaster scenarios. Furthermore, harmonization within certification schemes is a complex task, given the diverse range of equipment and systems used by first responders. Striking a balance between standardization and flexibility in certification is paramount.

Complex systems for FRs demand thorough evaluation beyond just the product itself. Considerations for software quality, operator skills, security, and privacy are vital components of an effective certification process tailored to disaster scenarios. Additionally, establishing new evaluation procedures and accrediting evaluation facilities are critical for adapting to the introduction of novel technologies in emergency response.

The need for clear technical and functional requirements for first response enablers, especially for emerging technologies, cannot be overstated. Certification must demonstrate compliance with essential safety and performance requirements through a robust set of criteria.

Effective communication among stakeholders in the certification process is essential. While information sharing programs exist, there is a clear need for a more accessible and comprehensive online community dedicated to certification-related knowledge exchange.

In the operational domain, we have identified challenges related to regulations for UAVs, operator skills, and the absence of protocols governing certification, training, deployment, and integration of emerging technologies. These challenges pose operational risks and hinder collaboration among response teams.

Moreover, the rapid development of new technologies necessitates continuous training and skill updates for response personnel to ensure they are equipped with the necessary skills and procedures for using and maintaining these technologies.

Cross-border cooperation in emergency situations demands standardized procedures, communication protocols, and capabilities among response teams. Achieving consistency in knowledge, services, and certification across countries is essential for a seamless response during multi-casualty accidents.

The dynamic nature of cybersecurity threats underscores the importance of maintaining up-to-date certification schemes, and achieving global consistency in certification and standards for disaster management technologies requires international collaboration and harmonization.

In conclusion, addressing these gaps and seizing the opportunities presented in both certification and operational aspects is pivotal to enhancing the readiness and effectiveness of emergency response teams in a rapidly changing technological and operational landscape. By developing comprehensive certification frameworks, promoting ongoing training, and fostering collaboration, we can better equip our responders to save lives and mitigate the impact of

disasters, regardless of their complexity or origin. The road ahead requires a concerted effort to establish a robust and responsive certification framework that meets the demands of a dynamic technological and operational environment.

8. Future work

In the complex domain of emergency management, the insights from this deliverable may offer a foundational perspective. However, considering the continuous evolution of this sector and the integration of digital technologies, further research and proactive developments are essential. The areas of focus for upcoming initiatives:

- **Interoperability certification** – With disasters often requiring multi-agency collaboration, especially in cross-border scenarios, there's a pressing need for interoperability certification. This would encompass clear definitions of organizational structures, communication protocols, data privacy and security, and other key components that ensure seamless coordination between different entities during emergencies.
- **Cybersecurity in disaster management** – As emergency response integrates more digital tools and platforms, the potential cyber vulnerabilities increase. The development and standardization of cybersecurity certifications need to be prioritized, ensuring that emergency response technologies are not just functional, but also secure against cyber threats.
- **Test facilities and emerging technologies** – As technologies such as AI, IoT, unmanned vehicles, and advanced communication platforms continue to emerge, there is a pressing need to rigorously test them. It's crucial to enhance test facility capabilities to effectively evaluate the safety, reliability, and real-world performance of these cutting-edge tools.
- **Certification for Data practices** – The role of big data in emergency response is important, and ensuring secure and ethical data collection and utilization is crucial. Certification schemes could cover aspects like real-time data analytics, data privacy, and the protection of sensitive information.
- **Sustainability in Certification** – While there's been progress in sustainable certification practices, there's still room for improvement. This includes the exploration of cost-effective strategies, collaboration methodologies, and long-term planning to make certifications more accessible and sustainable.
- **Ethical implications in Certification** – As diverse technologies integrate into emergency response, certifications should include ethical considerations. This means not only certifying that technologies are effective but also ensuring they are ethically sound, with no unintended societal implications. Certifications should involve rigorous assessments that gauge the ethical impact of deploying new technologies.

By focusing on these areas in the certification landscape, the emergency management sector can strengthen its approach, ensuring the ideal balance of technology, ethics, and user-centricity.

9. Annex A – Glossary

Acronym	Description
AED	Automated External Defibrillators
AEM	Associate Emergency Manager
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALT	Accelerated Lifecycle Testing
CAB	Conformity Assessment Body
CASCO	ISO's Committee on Conformity Assessment
CB	Certification Body
CBRN	Chemical, Biological, Radiological, Nuclear
CCRA	Common Criteria Recognition Arrangement
CCTV	Closed Circuit Television
CE	Conformité Européenne
CECIS	Common Emergency Communication and Information System
CEM	Certified Emergency Manager
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
COTS	Commercial-off-the-shelf
CPR	Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation
CPS	Cyber-physical systems
CSP	Cloud Service Provider
CV	Consultative Visit
CSPCERT WG	Cloud Service Provider Certification Working group
DG ECHO	Directorate-General for European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations
DSC	Digital selective calling
DTIC	Defence Technical Information Center
EA	European cooperation for Accreditation
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
EC	European Commission
ECCG	European Cybersecurity Certification Group
ECPP	European Civil Protection Pool
EDIH	European Digital Innovation Hub
EEA	European Economic Area
EERC	European Emergency Response Capacity
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
ELT	Emergency Locator Transmitters
EMAP	Emergency Management Accreditation Program
EMT	Emergency Medical Team
ENCP	Escuela Nacional de Protección Civil
ENISA	European Network and Information Security Agency

Acronym	Description
EPIRB	Emergency Position Indicating Radio Beacon
ERCC	Emergency Response Coordination Centre
ERNICIP	European Reference Network for Critical Infrastructure Protection
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
EUCA	European Cybersecurity Act
EUCC	European Union Cybersecurity Certification
EUCPT	European Union Civil Protection Team
EUCS	European Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Services
EUTFs	European Union Testing Facilities
FEMA	Federal Emergency Management Agency
FITCEM	Fixed Time Common Evaluation Methodology
FR	First Responder
FX	Field Exercise
GA/R	General Aviation/Rotorcrafts
GEMMA	Global Emergency Management System
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HF	High Frequency
IAEM	International Association of Emergency Managers
IAF	International Accreditation Forum
IACS	Integrated Administration and Control System
IAMSAR	International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue
ICAO	International Civil Aviation Organization
ICT	Information Communications Technology
IDS	International Data Spaces
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEC	INSARAG External Classification
IECEE	International Electrotechnical Commission for Electrical Equipment
IMO	International Maritime Organization
INSARAG	International Search and Rescue Advisory Group
IOP	Interoperability Processes
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Ingress Protection
IRNAP	INSARAG Recognized National Accreditation Process
ISCOM	Istituto Superiore delle Comunicazioni e tecnologie dell'Informazione
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IT	Information Technology
ITSEF	Information Technology Security Evaluation Facilities
ITU	International Telecommunication Union

Acronym	Description
MBR	Maritime Broadband Radio
MCPTT	Mission Critical Push-To-Talk
MF	Medium Frequency
MILS	Multiple Independent Levels of Security
MLA	Multilateral Recognition Arrangement
MODEX	Modules field and table-top exercises
MPEG	Moving Pictures Expert Group
MRAs	Mutual Recognition Agreements
NAB	National Accreditation Body
NANDO	New Approach Notified and Designated Organisations
NAP	National accreditation process
NB	Notified Body
NCCA	National Cybersecurity Certification Authorities
NEMA	National Emergency Management Association
NIS	Network and Information Security
NLF	New European Legislative Framework
NSM	National Safety Authority (in Norway)
NTC	National Training Coordinator
OSC	On-scene coordinator
PLB	Personal Locator Beacon
RED	Radio Equipment Directive
RCC	Rescue Coordination Centre
RF	Radio Frequency
SAR	Search And Rescue
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SOG-IS MRA	Senior Officials Group Information Systems Security Mutual Recognition Agreement
SOLAS	International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea
SOP	Standard Operational Procedures
SORA	Specific Operation Risk Assessment
SQuaRE	Software Product Quality Requirements and Evaluation
TAST	Technical Assistance and Support Teams
TCCA	The Critical Communication Association
TEFs	Testing and Experimentation Facilities
TETRA	Trans European Trunked RAdio
TETRAPOL	Terrestrial Trunked Radio Police
TIEMS	The International Emergency Management Society
TOP	Test Operations Procedure
TQAC	TIEMS Qualification Associate Certification
TQC	TIEMS Qualification Certification
TTX	Table-Top Exercise
UAS	Unmanned Aircraft Systems

Acronym	Description
UCPM	Union Civil Protection Mechanism
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicles
UN	United Nations
USAR	Urban Search and Rescue
USV	Unmanned Surface Vehicle
VHF	Very High Frequency
VTT	Virtual Testing Technologies
WHO	World Health Organisation

Table 13 - Glossary

10. Annex B - Questionnaire for Map of certification

Map of Certification initiatives and Test facilities

This questionnaire is for evaluating the “map of certification initiatives” which is completed in Task 3.5.

Detailed information is provided below to help you evaluate. Please refer to it when necessary.

The questionnaire begins on page 6.

“T3.5 Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities” aims to investigate current certification framework and initiatives and identify gaps and opportunities and to reduce the time from research to certification, as well as enhancing their sustainability.

The certification is defined as “conformity assessment by a third-party body related to products, processes, systems or persons”. The certification could help facilitate interoperability in cross-border disaster situations. By using equipment, procedures, and training program that have been certified by a common certification scheme, different organizations can be assured that they are using compatible systems and that they can effectively coordinate their operations.

The scope of the certification for first responders in Task 3.5 is set to;

1. Equipment
2. Technologies
3. Operation

You can find three categories (1. Equipment, 2. Technologies and 3. Operation) in attached excel file “the map of certification”¹⁶⁴.

On the page 7, you can find an overview of certification/standard related to disaster management.

1. Equipment
 - CE mark is important concept related to the product certification in Europe
 - CE mark indicates that the product conforms to the relevant health, safety, and environmental protection standards set by the EU
 - CE mark does not indicate that the product has been certified by a third-party certification body, so it should not be considered a certification scheme in itself.
 - Test facilities for CE mark
 - A notified body
 - ✓ It is an organisation designated by an EU country to assess the conformity of certain products before being placed on the market.
 - ✓ The European Commission publishes a list of such notified bodies¹⁶⁵

¹⁶⁴ Certification schemes are established based on related regulations and standards. Therefore, “Legislation/Standard” are also included in this map of certification.

¹⁶⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/nando/index.cfm>

- Example of the process to obtain the CE mark for UAV
 - 1) Determine the applicable directives and standards for the UAV – “*Regulation (EU) 2019/945 on unmanned aircraft systems and on third-country operators of unmanned aircraft systems*”
 - 2) Verify that the UAV complies with the essential requirements
 - 3) Third-party certification is required for UAV, so select a notified body and submit the necessary documentation and samples for testing
 - 4) If the UAV passes the conformity assessment, the notified body will issue a certificate of conformity
 - 5) Affix the CE mark to the UAV

- The manufacturer should also keep in mind that the requirements for obtaining the CE mark may vary depending on the product category and the intended use, and that compliance with other applicable regulations, such as those related to cybersecurity or data privacy, might also be necessary.

- For UGVs and USVs, which do not have specific applicable regulations. The manufacturer needs to identify the applicable directives or regulations that may be relevant to the UGV and USV ¹⁶⁶. For instance, directives such as Electromagnetic Compatibility Directive (2014/30/EU), Radio Equipment Directive (2014/53/EU), Low Voltage Directive (2014/35/EU) might be applicable to the UGVs and USVs.

2. Technology

- As technology continues to advance, more and more devices are connected to the internet. This means that it is becoming more important to ensure that these devices are secure and that they have been tested and certified to meet certain standards.
- The European Union Agency for Cybersecurity, ENISA, is the Union’s agency dedicated to achieving a high common level of cybersecurity across Europe
- ENISA is currently developing
 - EUCC: the Common Criteria based European cybersecurity certification scheme dedicated to Information and communication technology(ICT) products
 - EUCS: the Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Services
 - EU5G: the certification for network devices and identification
- Common Criteria(CC)
 - CC is an internationally recognized standard for evaluating the security capabilities and features of information technology products
- Test facilities – ITSEF(Information Technology Security Evaluation Facility)
 - Under the current European agreement SOG-IS, the certification authorities and ITSEF per country are listed up at the SOG-IS portal¹⁶⁷

¹⁶⁶ It might be useful to consult with a notified body, which can provide guidance on the applicable regulations and conformity assessment procedures.

¹⁶⁷ https://www.sogis.eu/uk/status_participant_en.html

3. Operation

- 1) First responder – Generally, first responders are required to have a certain level of education and training in emergency response procedures, as well as any necessary technical or specialized skills required for their specific role.
- INSARAG External Classification (IEC)
 - It is a peer review process that evaluates the national urban search and rescue teams of countries
 - The objective of the IEC is to assess the level of preparedness, coordination, and response capacity of the national urban search and rescue teams to natural and man-made disasters.
 - IEC is not a certification scheme, but it provides an internationally recognized system for classifying and validating USAR teams that can be called upon for deployment in the event of an international disaster.
 - The INSARAG Guidelines on External Classification provides detailed information on the process of external classification, including the criteria and procedures that are used to assess USAR teams
- EMT(Emergency Medical Teams Global Classification)¹⁶⁸
 - EMT Global Classification is an external peer review evaluation mechanism that assesses EMT compliance against internationally agreed guiding principles and core and technical standards.
 - World Health Organization (WHO) Emergency Medical Teams (EMT) Initiative¹⁶⁹ provides the EMT Global Classification
 - This is a global initiative launched by the WHO to strengthen emergency medical response during outbreaks and disasters.
 - The initiative aim to improve the quality and accountability of emergency medical teams by establishing minimum standards for their training, equipment, and deployment.
 - The initiative also aims to establish a global registry of emergency medical teams to facilitate coordination and response during emergencies.
 - KIMEP(Knowledge and Information Management Emergency Platform): Tool for the EMT Initiative
 - Classification and Minimum Standards for Emergency Medical Teams¹⁷⁰
- There is no harmonized certification scheme for first aid responders across Europe

¹⁶⁸ The classification process is primarily focused on evaluating and categorizing the capacities and capabilities of emergency response teams or organizations based on established criteria and standards. It aims to assess their level of preparedness and ability to respond effectively to emergencies and disasters. Therefore, the classification process can provide valuable information to guide the development of a certification scheme, such as identifying the skills and knowledge areas that are critical to emergency response and disaster management.

¹⁶⁹ <https://extranet.who.int/emt/>

¹⁷⁰ [Guidelines and Publications | EMT \(who.int\)](#)

- Many European countries have their own certification schemes (this can create challenges in coordinating and deploying response teams in cross-border situations)
- The ECPP has certification process for certain types of resources, including rescue teams and equipment, for international deployment during disasters.
 - ✓ To participate in the ECPP, rescue teams/equipment are required to meet specific certification criteria, but this process does not constitute a formal certification scheme¹⁷¹
 - ✓ ECPP serves as a mechanism for assessing the readiness and capabilities of rescue teams/equipment in emergency response
- A harmonized certification scheme for (first aid responders) across Europe could align the different EU Member States, enabling them to work in a more effective way.

2) Cybersecurity

- Cybersecurity is becoming an increasingly important issue for emergency services, as they rely on technology and data to carry out their work. For example, emergency services may use computer systems to manage incident response, communication networks to coordinate operations, and databases to store sensitive information about individuals. Any breach of these systems could compromise the safety and security of both responders and the public they serve.
- While there is no specific certification program for cybersecurity in the context of first responders, there are general cybersecurity courses and certifications that can be useful for those working in emergency services. For example, courses on cybersecurity risk management, incident response, and data protection can provide valuable knowledge and skills for emergency services professionals.
- CISSP (Certified Information Systems Security Professional)
 - CISSP is a globally recognized certification that validates expertise in various domains of information security
 - It is offered by the International Information System Security Certification Consortium (ISC)^{2 172}
 - CISSP covers a wide range of topics, including security and risk management, asset security, security architecture and engineering, communication and network security, identity and access management, security assessment and testing, security operations, and software development security
- Creating a harmonized European-wide cybersecurity certification framework faces several challenges and complexities, which can arise from various factors including legal, technical, organizational, and cultural aspects. Therefore, any

¹⁷¹ Formal certification schemes aim to provide official recognition of compliance with predefined standards and criteria across various domains

¹⁷² <https://www.isc2.org/>

such initiative would require careful planning, collaboration, and a clear understanding of the diverse factors at play across the European landscape.

3) UAV

- In Europe, the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA)¹⁷³ has established the European drone regulations, which include the requirement for drone operators to obtain a certificate or license, depending on the category of operation
- The drone pilot needs to complete the necessary online training, pass a pilot exam and get a valid remote pilot competency certificate (valid for 5 years)
- EASA collaborates closely with National Aviation Authorities¹⁷⁴ to ensure harmonization and consistency in the regulation of civil drones across Europe¹⁷⁵

4) UGV and USV

- There is no certification scheme for UGVs/USVs operators
- UGVs and USVs are a more limited range of applications (their roles primarily encompass areas such as robotics research, military operations, and specific industrial applications) compared to UAVs
- The relatively niche market for UGVs and USVs may have contributed to the slower development of certification
- Existing certifications related to robotics or unmanned systems may cover certain aspects relevant to UGVs and USVs

¹⁷³ <https://www.easa.europa.eu/en>

¹⁷⁴ <https://www.easa.europa.eu/en/domains/civil-drones/naa>

¹⁷⁵ EASA provides overarching regulations and standards at the European level, while NAAs adapt and implement these regulations within their national frameworks

Questionnaire for “Map of certification initiatives and Test facilities”

1. Organisation type
 - Academia
 - Industry
 - First responder
 - Other
2. What is your level of confidence for the topic of certification?
 - Expert
 - Pretty good
 - Some knowledge
 - Not confident at all
3. Evaluate the following areas about current certification scheme for PRODUCTS in emergency response (from 1 (low) to 10 (high))
 - a. General (1 – 10)
 - b. Efficiency (1 – 10)
 - c. Transparency (1 – 10)
 - d. Adaptability (1 – 10)
 - e. Alignment with technological advancements (1 – 10)
 - f. Clarity of criteria (1 – 10)
 - g. International /European harmonization (1 – 10)
 - h. Stakeholder engagement (1 – 10)
4. Evaluate the following areas about current certification scheme for TECHNOLOGY in emergency response (from 1 (low) to 10 (high))
 - a. General (1 – 10)
 - b. Efficiency (1 – 10)
 - c. Transparency (1 – 10)
 - d. Adaptability (1 – 10)
 - e. Alignment with technological advancements (1 – 10)
 - f. Clarity of criteria (1 – 10)
 - g. International /European harmonization (1 – 10)
 - h. Stakeholder engagement (1 – 10)
5. Evaluate the following areas about current certification scheme for OPERATION/PROCEDURES in emergency response (from 1 (low) to 10 (high))
 - a. General (1 – 10)
 - b. Efficiency (1 – 10)
 - c. Transparency (1 – 10)
 - d. Adaptability (1 – 10)
 - e. Alignment with technological advancements (1 – 10)
 - f. Clarity of criteria (1 – 10)
 - g. International /European harmonization (1 – 10)
 - h. Stakeholder engagement (1 – 10)
6. What is your level of acceptance (from 1 to 10) with the provided map of certification for first responders?
7. Are there any additional standards or criteria you believe should be included in the certification scheme for product/technology/operation of emergency response?

Thank you for taking the time to help us!

Map of Certification/Standard

No.	International Legislation/Standard	International Certification
INT01	IEC International Standard	IECEE
INT02	ICAO Annex2(Rules of the Air) and Annex11(Air Traffic Services)	
INT03	ISO 21384-2:2021 Unmanned aircraft systems-Part2:UAS components	
INT04	IEC 62368-1:2023 Audio/video, information and communication technology equipment	
INT05	IEC 60601-1-11 Medical Electrical Equipment-Part 1-11	
INT06	ISO 10993-1:2018 Biological evaluation of medical devices	
INT07	IEC 62304-2006 Medical device software-Software life cycle processes	
INT08	OGC standards	OGC Compliance Program
INT09	Common Criteria(CC)	
INT10	ISO/IEC 23894:2023 Information technology - Artificial intelligence - Guidance on risk management	
INT11	ISO/IEC 30162:2022 Internet of Things (IoT) – Compatibility requirements and model for devices within industrial IoT systems	
INT12	ISO 27001	
INT13		ioXt
INT14	INSARAG Guidelines on External Classification	INSARAG External Classification
INT15	Classification and Minimum Standards for Emergency Medical Teams	The EMT Global Classification
INT16	Model UAS Regulations and Advisory Circulars from ICAO	
INT17	Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UAS) for Humanitarian Aid and Emergency Response Guidance	
INT18	ISO 21384-3:2019 Unmanned aircraft systems-Part3:Operational procedures	
INT19		CISSP

No.	European Legislation/Standard	European Certification
EUR01	Regulation (EU) 2019/945	CE Mark
EUR02	Regulation (EU) 2019/947	
EUR03	EMC Directive(2014/30/EU)	CE Mark
EUR04	Radio Equipment Directive(2014/53/EU)	CE Mark
EUR05	Product Safety Directive (2001/95/EC)	CE Mark
EUR06	Machinery Directive (2006/42/EC)	CE Mark
EUR07	Medical Devices Regulation (EU) 2017/745	CE Mark
EUR08	General Product Safety Regulation (EU) 2023/988	CE Mark
EUR09	Low Voltage Directive (2014/35/EU)	CE Mark
EUR10	Personal Protective Equipment Regulation (EU) 2016/425	CE Mark
EUR11	General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679	CE Mark
EUR12	TETRA	TCCA's Interoperability Certification Process
EUR13	ETSI EN 301 893	
EUR14	ETSI EN 300 019	
EUR15	ETST EN 300 386	
EUR16	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community Directive (2007/2/EC)	
EUR17	CEN/TC 287 Geographic Information	
EUR18	AI Act. (in process)	
EUR19	ETSI EN 303 645	
EUR20	Cybersecurity Act.	EUCC
EUR21	Professional Qualifications Directive(2005/36/EC)	
EUR22	Union Civil Protection Mechanism (2014/762/EU)	ECPP

	No.	Legislation/Standard	Certification	Product				Technology					Operation			
				UAV	UGV	USV	Wearable	Communication	GIS	AI	IoT	Cybersecurity	First Responders	UAV	Cybersecurity	
International	1	IEC International Standard It provide guidelines, specifications, and requirements for various aspects of electrical and electronic systems, equipment, and components	IECEE IECEE is the conformity assessment scheme for electrotechnical equipment and components.	x	x	x	x	x	x							
	2	ICAO Annex2 (Rules of the Air) and Annex11 (Air Traffic Services)	ICAO provides guidance and standards for drone, but these are not binding certification schemes	x												
	3	ISO 21384-2:2021 Unmanned aircraft systems-Part2:UAS components	IEC/ISO standards provide specifications, guidelines, and best practices to ensure consistency, quality, and safety in various areas. While many IEC/ISO standards have their own certification schemes, some do not yet. In this case, it's possible that certification bodies or organizations may develop certification programmes or schemes that use IEC/ISO standards as a reference or basis for certification.	x												
	4	IEC 62368-1:2023 Audio/video, information and communication technology equipment		x	x	x	x									
	5	IEC 60601-1-11 Medical Electrical Equipment-Part 1-11														
	6	ISO 10993-1:2018 Biological evaluation of medical devices														
	7	IEC 62304:2006 Medical device software-Software life cycle processes														

	No.	Legislation/Standard	Certification	Product				Technology					Operation				
				UAV	UGV	USV	Wearable	Communication	GIS	AI	IoT	Cybersecurity	First Responders	UAV	Cybersecurity		
International	8	OGC standards It enable different geospatial systems and technologies to work together seamlessly, facilitating the sharing and integration of geospatial data across various platforms and applications	OGC Compliance Program This provides confidence that a product will seamlessly integrate with other compliant solutions regardless of the vendor that created them						x								
	9	Common Criteria(CC) CC defines a standardized methodology for conducting security evaluations, including the development of security requirements, testing procedures, and evaluation criteria.	- No harmonized certification scheme - Most of European countries have national certification scheme based on Common Criteria(CC)					x	x	x	x	x					
	10	ISO/IEC 23894:2023 Information technology - Artificial intelligence - Guidance on risk management								x							
	11	ISO/IEC 30162:2022 Internet of Things (IoT) – Compatibility requirements and model for devices within industrial IoT systems										x					
	12	ISO 27001 Information security management systems						x	x	x	x	x					
	13		ioXt The ioXt certification Program provides a framework for evaluating the security of IoT devices.									x					

	No.	Legislation/Standard	Certification	Product				Technology					Operation			
				UAV	UGV	USV	Wearable	Communication	GIS	AI	IoT	Cybersecurity	First Responders	UAV	Cybersecurity	
International	14	INSARAG Guidelines on External Classification	INSARAG External Classification(IEC)											x		
	15	Classification and Minimum Standards for Emergency Medical Teams	The EMT Global Classification											x		
	16	Model UAS Regulations and Advisory Circulars" from ICAO													x	
	17	Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UAS) for Humanitarian Aid and Emergency Response Guidance: This guidance aims to facilitate the responsible and effective use of UAS in emergency response operations														x
	18	ISO 21384-3:2019 Unmanned aircraft systems- Part3:Operational procedures														x
	19		CISSP (Certified Information Systems Security Professional)													

	No.	Legislation/Standard	Certification	Product				Technology					Operation					
				UAV	UGV	USV	Wearable	Communication	GIS	AI	IoT	Cybersecurity	First Responders	UAV	Cybersecurity			
European	1	Regulation (EU) 2019/945 This regulation establishes technical specifications and standards that UAS manufacturers and operators must comply with.	CE Mark	x														
	2	Regulation (EU) 2019/947 This regulation covers aspects such as operational categories, operational limitations, remote pilot qualifications and training, registration and identification of UAS, and operational authorizations for specific categories of UAS operations														x		
	3	EMC Directive(2014/30/EU)	CE Mark	x	x	x	x											
	4	Radio Equipment Directive(2014/53/EU)	CE Mark	x	x	x	x											
	5	Product Safety Directive (2001/95/EC)	CE Mark	x	x	x	x											
	6	Machinery Directive(2006/42/EC)	CE Mark	x	x	x	x											
	7	Medical Devices Regulation (EU) 2017/745	CE Mark														x	
	8	General Product Safety Regulation (EU) 2023/988	CE Mark	x	x	x	x											
	9	Low Voltage Directive (2014/35/EU)	CE Mark	x	x	x	x											
	10	Personal Protective Equipment Regulation (EU) 2016/425	CE Mark														x	
	11	General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679	CE Mark	x	x	x	x											

	No.	Legislation/Standard	Certification	Product				Technology					Operation				
				UAV	UGV	USV	Wearable	Communication	GIS	AI	IoT	Cybersecurity	First Responders	UAV	Cybersecurity		
European	12	TETRA It is a digital mobile radio standard developed specifically for public safety and emergency services across Europe.	TCCA's Interoperability Certification Process(IOP): It was developed to enable a truly open multi-vendor market for TETRA equipment and system						x								
	13	ETSI EN 301 893 5 GHz RLAN; Harmonised Standard covering the essential requirements of article 3.2 of Directive 2014/53/EU						x									
	14	ETSI EN 300 019 Environmental Engineering (EE); Environmental conditions and environmental tests for telecommunications equipment						x									
	15	ETST EN 300 386 Telecommunication network equipment; Harmonised Standard for ElectroMagnetic Compatibility (EMC) requirements						x									
	16	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community Directive (2007/2/EC)								x							
	17	CEN/TC 287 Geographic Information								x							
	18	AI Act. (in process)									x						

	No.	Legislation/Standard	Certification	Product				Technology					Operation			
				UAV	UGV	USV	Wearable	Communication	GIS	AI	IoT	Cybersecurity	First Responders	UAV	Cybersecurity	
European	19	ETSI EN 303 645 CYBER; Cyber Security for Consumer Internet of Things: Baseline Requirements Cybersecurity Act.									x		x			
	20		EUCC the Common Criteria based European cybersecurity certification scheme dedicated to Information and communication technology(ICT) products					x		x		x				
	21	Professional Qualifications Directive(2005/36/EC) This directive is not specifically tailored to address the unique requirements and competencies of FRs. It is primarily focuses on the recognition of qualifications for regulated professions. It emphasizes the importance of harmonizing certification standards and facilitating the mobility of certified professionals across European countries													x	
	22	Union Civil Protection Mechanism (2014/762/EU)	ECPP												x	x

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